

SONNET – SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY TRANSITIONS

Co-creating a rich understanding of the diversity, processes, contributions, success and future potentials of social innovation in the energy sector

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Research report on ‘Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways’ in the United Kingdom

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About SONNET: SONNET is a research project that aims to develop an understanding of diversity, processes, contributions and future potential of social innovation in the energy sector. It is co-funded by the European Commission and runs for three years, from 2019-2022. The SONNET consortium consists of 12 partners across Europe, including academics and city administrations. For more information, please visit our website: <https://sonnet-energy.eu>

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1 FOREWORD

SONNET (Social Innovation in Energy Transitions) brings diverse groups together to make sense of how social innovation can bring about a more sustainable energy sector in Europe. The project aims to co-create a rich understanding of the diversity, processes, contributions, successes and future potentials of social innovation in the energy sector (SIE). We define SIE as a combination of ideas, objects and/ or actions that change social relations and involve new ways of doing, thinking and/ or organising energy. An example is organising under cooperative principles to generate renewable energy. As part of this work, we make use of an embedded case study approach to build a better understanding of the development of diverse SIE-fields (e.g. participatory incubation and experimentation, framings against specific energy pathways, local electricity exchange) and their SIE over time. Our research questions that frame the case study work are:

- How do SIEs and SIE-fields emerge, develop and institutionalise over time?
- How do SIE-field-actors and other field-actors interact with the 'outside' institutional environment and thereby co-shape the SIE-field over time?
- What are the enabling and impeding factors for SIE-field-actors and other field-actors to conduct institutional work and change the 'outside' institutional environment?

A SIE-field is an arena/space that includes a specific SIE as well as SIE-field-actors working on it and other field-actors enabling and/or impeding it. In this arena/ space these actors take one another and their actions into account and have a shared (but not necessarily consensual) understanding of a SIE and of their relationship to other actors. They recognise (but not necessarily follow) shared norms, beliefs and rules. SIE-fields are often not homogenous but are composed of actors with diverse and contradictory aims and interests. An example: The UK cooperative energy field includes SIE-initiatives and SIE-field-actors (e.g. Brighton Energy Co-op, Cooperative UK, Community Energy England, UK Government, City of Brighton), who have a shared understanding of an SIE, which exists as 'organising under cooperative principles to generate renewable energy'.

The structure of this report is as follows. Section 2 provides a summary of the SIE-field relevant for this report and lists some key insights. Section 3 outlines the boundaries of the SIE-field and shows how it has been studied in the country context. Section 4 shows a visual development of the SIE-field. Section 5 tells the historical development of the SIE-field over time, including analytical/ interpretive reflections from the SONNET researchers and quotes from the actors involved in the field developments. Section 6 outlines key research findings, providing answers to the three research questions. Section 7 outlines recommendations for policymakers based on the findings. Finally, Section 9 outlines the methodological approach and includes a more detailed timeline of the SIE-field and its actors.

The following boxes are used within the report:

2 FRAMINGS AGAINST FOSSIL FUEL ENERGY PATHWAYS

In SONNET, we investigate the development of the SIE-field called ‘framings against fossil fuel energy pathways’ e.g. narratives, discourses, etc. derived from anti-fossil groups and movements over time. Behind these framings can be multiple actors, e.g. NGOs, informal groups and networks, local initiatives and residents that work locally, regionally, nationally but also internationally and aim to change societal debates about fossil fuel-based energy pathways. The framings that they develop can contain problem descriptions linked to the extraction of fossil fuels e.g. biodiversity destruction but sometimes also alternative futures e.g. non-hierarchical ways of organising sustainable lifestyles. In the UK, several policy changes have occurred in this SIE-field over the past years (e.g. deadline for the phase-out of coal and moratoriums on fracking) that could be interpreted as major achievements to stop fossil fuel extraction and consumption in the UK. The historical account in section 5 shows that the story is not as straightforward as it might seem at first sight.

Key insights

For the SONNET project, the SIE-field ‘framings against fossil fuel energy pathways’ is particularly interesting because through its long history including differing forms of resistance in the SIE-field, it reveals a number of important issues for social innovation in energy transitions (SIE). In particular, it illustrates that:

- In comparison to other SIE (e.g. cooperative energy production, as defined by the SONNET team), ‘framings against fossil fuel energy pathways’ draw attention that low carbon energy transitions are not only grounded in creating alternative relations, networks, technologies, etc. but also disrupting existing ones. This might not be a new insight but what the historical account makes visible is that first, there still are discourses, regulations, policies and invested interests, keeping the fossil fuel industry alive in the UK (although climate targets have been set) and second, anti-fossil fuel activities cannot be purely based on framings surrounding technological replacements (i.e. renewables for coal) but also consider broader climate justice issues.
- Similar to other SIE, ‘framings against fossil fuel energy pathways’ rely on people getting involved in a diverse set of activities (e.g. legal cases, mobilising and direct action) that require a steep learning curve to build up knowledge, competences and skills over time. The amount of emotional work and stamina required should also not be underestimated, given that most of the people involved in this SIE have spent years and years on trying to influence the path of the fossil fuel industry. It also is worth recognising how deeply people’s lives have been changed by getting involved in ‘framings against fossil fuel energy pathways), becoming highly engaged in broad social and political issues.
- Anti-fossil fuel framings (e.g. anti-fracking, anti-coal and anti-investment in fossil fuels) have been mainly held together by national NGOs (e.g. Friends of the Earth), providing local, regional and national support. In addition, most of the campaigners have had affiliations to several groups and/ or organisations, sometimes crossing over

with, for instance, anti-fracking and anti-coal. This made it easy for them to support each other and exchange strategies. Other interactions between anti-fracking, anti-coal and divestment activities have also frequently occurred on an 'ad hoc' basis. For instance, in 2017, an energy symposium was carried out at an anti-fracking camp, inviting anti-coal and divestment campaigners.

3 Introduction to ‘framings against fossil fuel energy pathways’ in the UK

In SONNET, we investigate the development of the SIE-field and its SIE (see box ‘SIE changing social relations’) called **‘framings against fossil fuel energy pathways’** e.g. narratives, discourses, activities, etc. derived from anti-fossil fuel groups and movements over time. The SIE-field can feature lobbying initiatives and campaigns against fossil fuel that advocate for political changes and protests against mainstream fossil fuel energy pathways. The framings that they develop can contain problem descriptions linked to the extraction of fossil fuels but sometimes also alternative futures. The aim of creating these framings is to implicitly or explicitly change dominant (societal) debates about existing fossil fuel energy pathways, influence policymaking and/ or stop fossil fuel extractions.

The boundaries of the SIE-field are therefore defined by framings that are being produced and are grounded in anti-fossil fuel energy pathways. In SONNET, we have drawn on the work of Bolsen and Shapiro (2017) and Wittmayer et al. (2019) to define what we mean by **framings**. Bolsen and Shapiro (2017:1) consider framings to be a ‘communicative process’, for them ‘framings involve making certain considerations salient as a way to simplify or shape the way in which an audience understands a particular problem and its potential solutions’. Wittmayer et al.’s (2019) have created a definition of narratives of change as ‘sets of ideas, concepts, metaphors, discourses or story-lines about societal transformation’. For instance, a prominent framing against fracking has been ‘dark satanic drills in a green and pleasant land’ (Williams and Sovacool 2019). In addition, we have included all types of framings against different **fossil energy sources** (including oil, coal, natural gas and more generally fossil fuels). These are non-renewable resources that are either important and/ or extracted through drilling and mining and then burnt to produce electricity or refined for use as fuel for heating. Although the SONNET project mainly concentrates on examining SIE developments in relation to electricity and heat, this report does not draw clear distinctions around fossil fuels being used for electricity and/ or other forms of energy consumption. We study this SIE-field in Poland, the Netherlands and **United Kingdom** (UK).

Most of the UK’s electricity is produced by burning fossil fuels, mainly natural gas (42% in 2016) and coal (9% in 2016 and 3% in 2020). A very small amount is produced from other fuels (3.1% in 2016). 21% of the electricity came from nuclear reactors. Renewable technologies e.g. wind, wave, marine, hydro, biomass and solar made up 24.5% of electricity generated in 2016. There are around 36 power stations (more gas than coal) in the UK. This report concentrates on framings against fossil fuel energy pathways. It has mainly been grounded in anti-coal, anti-onshore oil and gas (including anti-fracking and wider anti-gas-fired power stations)¹ and anti-investments into fossil fuels (i.e. derived from fossil fuel divestment i.e. stopping stocks, bonds or investing into fossil fuel companies) narratives. More framings against particular fossil fuel energy pathways (for

¹ The term ‘fracking’ is politically contested and defined differently across political contexts (Brock 2020). From 2010 onwards, most framing activities have been carried out around anti-fracking in the UK. But in 2016, the UK government introduced a definition of fracking which is very narrow, excluding many drilling projects. To be able to mark this shift, before 2015, I refer to the activities as anti-fracking and after 2015, they are described as anti- onshore oil and gas in this report.

instance, against tar sand) exist. These boundaries seem to make sense in the UK because all represent the most dominant framings against fossil fuel energy pathways over the past ten years. They also allow for diverse histories, actors' relations, activities, etc. to emerge to build a better understanding of the SIE-field called framings against particular fossil fuel energy pathways. Over the past year, there is an increasing recognition of neocolonialism in European coal consumption (see for instant the activities derived from 'Still Burning'², highlighting post-colonial entanglements), this report briefly touches upon these activities. Conducting the empirical work in the UK, it became clear that boundaries between framing activities (such as campaigning, lobbying and protesting) are not always straightforward. This report therefore concentrates on all types of activities as forms of framings. In the next three paragraphs, I briefly introduce the policy and energy context for framings against fracking, onshore oil and gas, coal and investments in fossil fuels in the UK.

SIE changing social relations

In SONNET, we are interested in studying diverse social innovation in energy (SIE). We define SIE as 'a combination of ideas, objects and/ or actions that change social relations and involve new ways of doing, thinking and/ or organising energy'. As part of this work, we have identified seven different types of SIE (for more information see <https://sonnet-energy.eu/typology/>), including one called 'campaigns against specific energy pathways'. Here, social interactions (and changes to social relations) that aim to bring about changes in the energy system are often based on 'conflicts' (rather than cooperation, exchange and competition) and make use of novel ways of ideas and thinking about energy issues (whilst making use of objects and actions) to stop particular energy pathways. The SIE therefore is based on different framings (but also includes protesting and lobbying work) derived from different groups and organisations that aim to stop the extraction of fossil fuels. This includes framings derived from anti-coal, anti-onshore oil and gas (fracking) movements and the divestment movement. We are particularly interested in the content, construction and performativity of these framings and their emergence and development over time. People involved in 'framings against energy pathways centred on fossil fuels' have had to be inventive, resilient and persistent over the past years because of powerful state and energy companies' efforts 'to facilitate the suppression of protest' (see Brock 2020:1).

During World War I and World War II, legislation was introduced to enable oil and gas companies to further explore **onshore oil and gas** (hydrocarbons) due to the UK's need to produce its own oil to help war efforts. Onshore oil and gas activities started to accelerate again after the 1979 oil crises, as domestic production became more important for the UK government. Over the last decade, the extraction of onshore oil and gas — particularly through hydraulic fracturing — has been contentious and controversial, not least in the UK. UK proponents emphasise the potential economic, security and environmental benefits of onshore oil and gas, while opponents stress the incumbent environmental, health and climate risks associated with these extractions and operations. Opponents can be local groups (e.g. Preston New Road Action Group and Frack Free Isle of Wight (now renamed Don't Drill The Wight)), regional network organisations (e.g. Weald Action Group and Frack Free

² For more information on 'Still Burning' see <https://stillburning.net>

Lancashire) and national organisations (e.g. Reclaim the Power, Friends of the Earth UK and Green Party). The UK government has promoted the extraction of onshore oil and gas over the past years. A licence is required by the Oil and Gas Authority, which grants rights to explore and extract onshore oil and gas. The rights granted do not include any rights of access overground, and the licensees must also obtain any consent under current legislation, including planning permissions. Despite promising geological estimates and strong support from the highest levels of UK government, public support for shale gas has declined over the recent years³. Growing opposition and protest have marked development since 2013 (e.g. Cotton et al. 2014). In November 2019, the UK government halted fracking in England with immediate effect. The decision was taken after a scientific study warned it was not possible to rule out “unacceptable” consequences for people living near fracking sites. The report, undertaken by the Oil and Gas Authority (OGA), also warned it was not possible to predict the magnitude of earthquakes fracking might trigger. The UK government said it would not agree to any future fracking “until compelling new evidence is provided” (...) that proves fracking could be safe. This moratorium has not stopped all onshore oil and gas activities in the UK.

The decline of the **coal** industry started due to increasing social, political and economic pressures in the late 1950s in the UK (Turnheim and Geels 2013). It was signified by pit closures and triggered the 1984-85 miners strikes. Some of the areas are still economically marked by the decline today. Coal has been entwined with places where communities spanning generations have been formed and held together through coal (e.g. Johnstone and Hielscher 2017), what has been termed the moral economy of coalmines (Gibbs 2021). Following the privatisation of the coal industry in 1994 and deindustrialisation of coal areas, the ownership of all coal resides with the Coal Authority which grants licences for coal exploration and extraction. In 1999, the Coalfields Regeneration Trust was created as a charity organisation in order to support the local population and subsidise projects for coalfields communities. In 2016, the Camp for Climate Action was set up as a week-long protest based just miles from the coal-fired power station Drax, in Yorkshire. More recently, specific policy announcements have been made to phase out coal by 2025 (Department of Energy and Climate Change (DECC) 2015). Calls for a ‘Just Transition’ has emerged to learn from 1950s. This notion is particularly strong in Scotland where the local government has set up a ‘Just Transition Commission’. Considering the UK’s dropping reliance on coal for electricity from 70% in 1990 to less than 3% today (BEIS 2020), the prime minister announced in February the decision to bring forward the phase out of coal to October 2024. The last deep coal mine, North Yorkshire’s Kellingley Colliery, closed on the 18th of December 2015. However, open cast mining has continued in some parts of the UK and plans for expansion have proven contentious, including several campaigns, local groups (e.g. United Valleys Action Group and Keep Cumbrian Coal in the Hole) and actions opposing coal developments in the UK (Greenpeace 2013). Some of the local groups are held together by a grassroots network organisation the ‘Coal Action Network’. Some of the other organisations are Greenpeace UK, Friends of the Earth UK and Reclaim the Power (i.e. a direct action network). Another example of a local group is the ‘Protect Pont Valley’ group (located in County Durham, North England) which has been fighting planning applications for the coal site for

³ See Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy (BEIS) Public Attitude Tracker

the past 30 years. The most recent planning application was rejected in 2011 but the coal company appealed in 2011 and 2013.

The **divestment** movement started in the summer of 2011 in the United States (US). Fossil fuel divestment campaigns emerged on six campuses with students urging the university administrations to turn endowment investments in the fossil fuel industry into investments in clean energy. By spring 2012, 50 US universities had divestment movements and continued to grow globally. The grassroots climate campaign 350.org that was co-founded by Bill McKibben launched its divestment campaign, supporting and joining forces with students organising the divestment movement. Their 'Go Fossil Free: Divest from Fossil Fuel!' campaign aimed to 'revoke the social licence of the fossil fuel industry' (350.org). Between 2012-2018, the movement grew considerably and there were fossil fuel divestment campaigns in hundreds of universities worldwide, including dozens in the UK, as well as local authorities and other institutions. The divestment movement has been coordinated mainly by two organisations in the UK: 1) People & Planet, who coordinate the student movement and work closely with the National Union of Students and 2) 350.org, who work with local councils and pension funds. Many of the groups involved are student organisations, although religious organisations, local and regional governments and other public bodies have also divested, or have been targeted by divestment campaigners. Over the past few years, the student divestment movement has become smaller, after seventy-eight of the UK's 154 public universities signed up to divest from fossil fuel in 2020 (see Bergman's (2018) study on the divestment movement in the UK).

Although it is possible to argue that there is a longer history of framings against fossil fuel energy pathways in the UK, this report examines the recent history, starting from 2010s to around now. This timeframe goes back far enough to include the beginnings of the divestment movement and increasing activities against onshore oil and gas (including fracking). Considering that much has happened within this SIE-field over the past ten years and some might argue that anti-coal, anti-fracking and divestment deserve to be studied in-depth in their own right, there are clear limitations to this report. The focus of the historical account in section 5 is based on (and partly limited by) the people that I was able to interview, number of documents and websites I could examine (I could have definitely consulted more) and the time I had to conduct the research (1.5 months) (for more details see methodology in annex 1). For instance, I have spoken to more people who have been involved in anti-onshore oil and gas than anti-coal and divestment (see section 9 for more details). My interviews around anti-fracking/ anti-onshore oil and gas have mainly been with people involved in local and regional activities (in particular in Sussex (including the Isle of Wight) and Lancashire). My interviews around anti-coal and divestment included two local groups and national organisations. The interviews with the people involved in the initiatives provided a good overview of their emergence and development over time and the influence of wider regulatory, social and policy changes. I have also gained an overview of national developments through reviewing the recent academic social science energy literature (where a vast amount of literature has been written about 'fracking' but less so on coal and divestment) and examining several websites (e.g. Coal Action Network and DrillOrDrop.com) (for more details see section 9). It is possible to argue that some of these activities are extremely well documented by people, who are dedicated to researching and documenting framings against fossil fuel energy pathways in the UK (often in their spare time). Some of these websites provide a far more detailed

historical account about particular movements and activities than I am able to do in this report (for onshore oil and gas, for example, see DrillOrDrop.com).

One of the main aims of this report is to examine the possible interlinkages between these activities and wider policy, regulatory, social and cultural influences, and to be able to write up a case study report that can be used for a comparative analysis of similar activities and framings in the Netherlands and Poland.

The initiatives that mainly feature in this report are: 1) The **Weald Action Group** is ‘an umbrella for local groups campaigning against all forms of extreme extraction of oil & gas across the Weald and the Isle of Wight in the South East of England’ (see Weald Action Group website). The aims are to support other community groups through providing training, facilitating networking, getting involved in lobbying and campaigns. I have spoken to members from **Isle of Wight and Balcombe groups**, who are part of the Weald Action group. 2) Two local groups based in Lancashire (North England): **Preston New Road Action Group** is a ‘residents’ organisation trying to help save our community and the planet from fossil fuel extraction by fracking’ (see Preston New Road Action Group website) and **Roseacre Awareness Group** is a community organisation which aims to engage in planning applications, public inquiries and any other statutory processes to protect the local and surrounding area from any exploration of oil and gas and at the same time to work to bring together residents and work in partnership with like-minded organisations (see Roseacre Awareness Group). 3) **Fossil Free Sussex** is ‘part of a wider national Fossil Free campaign led by People and Planet, which aims to pressure universities to remove their investments from fossil fuel industry (known as divestment)’. They are a local group at the University of Sussex. (See Students’ Union website, University of Sussex). 4) **Coal Action Network** (and the **Campaign to Protect Pont Valley** – led by local campaigners and residents and works with the Coal Action Network) ‘works for an end to coal-fired power generation, coal extraction and coal imports in the UK, and justice for communities affected by the UK’s current and historical coal consumption and mining’ (see Coal Action Network website).

The historical account in section 5 is structured around five phases to encapsulate all types of framings and activities. They provide an overview of developments of framings against fossil fuel energy pathways in the UK over time and are therefore structured around framings, policy changes and national events. Here, I often write about anti-onshore oil and gas (including anti-fracking), anti-coal and divestment in turn, whilst trying to tease out some of the interlinkages (or not). These changes and events have been chosen based on what the interviewees felt were key ones over time, which means that some might be missing from the historical account. After the interviews, I tried to ground these changes and events in the existing literature. The overall historical account is accompanied by stories from individual initiatives and their historical developments (see green boxes in section 5). These stories provide depth to the overall historical account, for instance, showing how policy decisions influenced their developments. At the end of some of the phases, I have added boxes (red ones) that reflect on existing framings and their changes. Finally, the blue boxes make a link between the data collection during the fieldwork and how we try to analyse and conceptualise the work as part of the SONNET project. The aim is to also engage the reader in some of the analytical steps.

4 Timeline of framings against fossil fuel energy pathways

The below timeline does not show all of the relevant events and sites of activities connected to framings against fossil fuel energy pathways in the UK over the last ten years. It is supposed to give a ‘flavour’ of different events, activities and sites. For a more detailed timeline see Annex 2.

Timeline for SIE-field: Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways

5 Emergence and development of framings against fossil fuel energy pathways over time

Phase 1 Some new emerging framings against anti-fossil fuels around 2010 - 2012

Around 2010, some new anti-fossil fuel campaigns emerged in the UK: anti-fracking and anti-investment into fossil fuels (i.e. divestment), mobilising diverse people. Other anti-fossil fuel campaigns that have had a long history in the UK continued during this time.

Fracking started in the UK

The first fracking⁴ activities for shale gas went ahead relatively unnoticed in Lancashire, North England (Interviewee 7); however, anti-fracking protests already took place. For instance, Frack Off (a grassroots direct action campaign) campaigners had installed anti-fracking banners on a drilling rig at the Cuadrilla site at Banks, Lancashire. In 2011, Cuadrilla Resources had to suspend their first operations to frack for shale gas following two earthquakes near Blackpool. These earthquakes in the Fylde coastal area, caused by the operation triggered a moratorium (i.e. temporary ban) on fracking in the UK. It was clear that this was meant to be a temporary ban, because George Osborne (at the time, Chancellor for the Exchequer) unveiled the UK government's gas generation strategy in 2012, including the Conservative government's 'dash for gas' plans. At the same time, the Royal Society and Royal Academy of Engineering conducted a joint report, which concluded that the risks of fracking could be effectively managed if operational best practice was ensured through regulation (The Royal Society/ Royal Academy of Engineering 2012).

The divestment movement arrived in the UK

In addition to anti-fracking, the fossil fuel divestment movement started up in 2012 in the UK. It has called for a 'financial shift of removing investments from fossil fuels as a strategy to reduce greenhouse gas emissions' (Bergman 2018:1). The divestment movement originally began, when student activists launched campaigns in six universities in the US to divest their endowments from coal in 2011. These activities were partly spurred on by an article called 'Global Warming's Terrifying New Math' written by Bill McKibben, who became a co-founder of 350.org. 350.org (a climate advocacy group) joined forces

⁴ The idea of fracking (i.e. 'cracking open the rock (typically shale), using water and chemicals pumped at high pressure, propping the cracks open with particles such as sand' (Sanderson 2016) to get out oil and gas) dates back to 1862. In the 1940s, explosives were replaced with high-pressure blasts of liquids, and so 'hydraulic' fracking became the usual practice in the oil and gas industry. It was not until the beginning of the 21st century that two key developments sparked current fracking activities. One was the use of a particular fracturing liquid and the other the possibility of horizontal drilling, increasing the productive potential of each well. These technological advancements and an influx of investment led to an increase of activities of the onshore oil and gas industry, in particular in the US but also in the UK.

with the student activists to start up the Go Fossil Free campaign, whose goal is to get institutional leaders to immediately freeze any new investment in fossil fuel companies and divest from direct ownership and any commingled funds that include fossil fuel public equities and corporate bonds within 5 years. The campaign also came over to the UK. In 2012, student activists at People & Planet (the UK's largest student campaigning organisation) began campaigning for the University of Manchester, University of East Anglia and University College London to stop investing in fossil fuel companies. Activities included, for instance, talking to the university's management groups, organising debates with students and staff members, and conducting protest activities (i.e. bike rides). At the time, it was a bottom-up movement, largely grounded in university student groups, although later on, it spread to other institutions.

The fight against coal continued, grounded on a long history in the UK

Other anti-fossil fuel activities continued during this time. Since 2005, there had been a surge in the number of planning applications to opencast coalmine in the UK - including 43 new opencast coalmines applications in 2011. 'The government was on the verge of investing in new coal fired power stations' (Interviewee 11). In response the Coal Action Network⁵ was created and an increasing local community resistance emerged (Coal Action Network 2015). For instance, Coal Action Scotland organised an outdoor skill share at the anti-coal camp of Mainhill and Happen Wood in Scotland. Different blockades and acts of sabotage against machinery had been taking place at the opencast coalmines, bringing attention to new coal developments. 'Unlike a lot of environmental direct action over the last decade, which has focused on one-off spectacular mass actions, Mainhill Solidarity has been targeted and continuous, building momentum over time' (Peace News 2010). In 2010, protesters associated with Mainhill Solidarity Camp were arrested after a six months occupation of an opencast mining site. A planning application also went in for the Bradley opencast coalmine, Durham, North England. Actions against this site highlight the long record of local actions against coal – see box for more details.

Campaign to Protect Pont Valley, Durham, North England

The long history of anti-coal and multiplicity of activities to stop coal extraction can be exemplified by what has happened at the Bradley mine in the Pont Valley area (Durham, North England). The area has been recovering from the loss of jobs caused by the closure of the deep pits over the past decades, but opencast coalmining has continued. The local community has fought to stop coalmining in the area over 50 years, trying to object to several planning applications for opencast coalmining. More recently, in 2009, the UK Coal's (coal company) planning application to Durham County

⁵ The Coal Action Network 'works for an end to coal-fired power generation, coal extraction and coal imports in the UK, and for justice for communities affected by the UK's current and historical coal consumption and mining' (Coal Action Network website). They started up around 2008 when about 40-50 opencast coalmine applications were submitted, and it looked like 'the government was on the verge of investing in new coal fired power stations' (Interviewee 11). It used to be run by volunteers but over the last few years has been able to employ 1-3 part time members of freelance staff. They try to support local communities in their efforts to stop opencast coalmines by providing learning, knowledge and networking opportunities (Interviewee 11). In 2015, they wrote up the 'Ditch Coal' report.

Council for the Bradley mine was unanimously rejected. Local people had formed a community group, The Pont Valley Network. They created the 'No Opencast Today or Tomorrow' (NOTT) campaign to fight the planning application. They were supported by the Coal Action Network. UK Coal appealed the Council's decision, which led to a three-week public inquiry in October and November 2011. Following the inquiry, the inspector upheld the council's decision, but UK Coal refused to take no for an answer and appealed to the high court in June 2013. The high court overturned the inspector's report leading to another three-week public inquiry, which took place in October 2014. Local people, who spoke out against the mine, attended both appeals. In June 2015, the company (i.e. UK Coal) gained permission to mine the site, despite going into administration during the application processes (Coal Action Network 2015). Then, nothing happened for several years. Please see Annex for the full Bradley coalmine historical narrative.

Looking at the time between 2010-2012, at first sight, it might seem that these anti-fossil fuel activities developed separately from each other. Some activities just started up whilst other ones were continuing. But this might not be the full story. There are several aspects that overlap between them that I try to briefly point out in the box 'interactions between actors in the SIE-field' (but they also become transparent when reading the next sections of the historical account).

Interactions between actors in the SIE-field and relations between different framings

The SONNET team is interested in studying the changes of social relations within existing energy transitions in Europe. Within this SIE-field (named 'framings against fossil fuel energy pathways') in the UK, some social relations, the ones between campaigners, have been built on some longstanding organisations - environmental organisations (e.g. Greenpeace and Friends of the Earth) and existing national grassroots direct action groups (e.g. Frack Off and Reclaim the Power) – who have organised and supported national, regional and local anti-fossil fuel campaigns over the last decades. They therefore hold some of the anti-fracking, anti-coal and divestment activities together, in particular, by supporting local groups to set up their own campaigns, providing information about anti-fossil fuel, taking on court cases against certain policy decisions and organising direct action (i.e. not all organisations get involved in similar ways).

Moreover, a campaigner that might formally work for divestment organisations can also informally get involved in organising anti-fracking events (Interviewee 5). Most of the interviewees had affiliations to several groups and organisations. Because of this, ways to organise, mobilise, lobby, take direct action, etc. are transferred between people, organisations, and locations (even across borders). Although there are some clear differences between the framings (anti-fracking, anti-coal and divestment), the SIE-field is held together by some of the people who get involved in several anti-fossil fuel activities.

'So it was almost two different bits of the movement that operated with different cultures and different constraints. But there was a significant overlap in personnel. And, you know, there was a kind of similar analysis of the fossil fuel industry... its role in the climate crisis, what needs to happen to it, that was informing both of those kind of approaches

that, you know, very different approaches in terms of style, tactics, et cetera...' (Interviewee 5, talking about anti-fracking and divestment).

Interactions between anti-fracking, anti-coal and divestment activities have also frequently occurred on an 'ad hoc' (Interviewee 11) basis. For instance, in 2017, an energy symposium was carried out at an anti-fracking camp, inviting anti-coal and divestment campaigners. Sometimes, there have also been exchanges between anti-fracking and anti-coal camps. 'And in fact, while we were during the camp at Bradley [anti-coal camp] there was the camp at Preston New Road [anti-fracking camp] at the same time. It was a lot more established and well known so groups of people came down for the weekend to have a bit of a holiday from Preston New Road and came to a different camp' (Interviewee 11). More frequently, upcoming news is shared between people (and organisations) across their social media accounts to increase the visibility of each other's activities.

What also becomes apparent (and also later on in the historical account) is how an increasing public discourse around climate change also provided a space for more groups to emerge, for instance, Fridays For Future and Extinction Rebellion, which have created an awareness and got involved in several anti-fossil fuel activities in the UK.

Short summary

The first phase of framings against fossil fuel energy pathways makes visible that there are diverse sites of opposition. These are linked to different types of protest sites where banners can be flown and blockages can be erected to stop the fossil fuel industry, council chambers where industry planning applications are being decided and potential objections can be submitted, and court rooms where legal challenges against the industry can be fought (or the other way around), just to mention a few. When reading the rest of the historical account, it becomes apparent that regulatory and policy developments have highly influenced framings against fossil fuels in the UK over the past ten years but also the level of national reporting about these issues and wider public discourses.

Phase 2 Local mobilisations and continuations surrounding anti-fossil fuel around 2013-2014

In the period between 2013 and 2014, several local anti-fossil fuel groups emerged and developed in rural areas where oil and gas companies started to gain planning permission to do their exploration work. Local groups also started to form at universities where student groups tried to persuade the management group to divest from fossil fuels. Groups had to come together, learn about anti-fossil fuel and decide on how they would frame their activities and position themselves. Although some coal companies went into liquidation, local groups needed to continue their work against new planning applications for opencast coalmines. Local activities were supported by grassroots organisations and national non-governmental organisation (NGOs). During this time, anti-fracking increasingly gained national media attention whereas the divestment

movement and anti-coal activities, for different reasons took place rather under the radar (i.e. not gaining the same national media attention).

Moratorium on fracking is lifted: Time to increase the mobilisation?

In 2013, the temporary ban on fracking was lifted under the condition of stricter seismic control. The UK government's support for fracking continued, with Prime Minister David Cameron stating 'Britain can't afford to miss out on shale gas' (The Telegraph 2013). He argued that the industry would create new jobs, cut customers' energy bills and provide money for local neighbourhoods. Osborne announced tax breaks for fracking firms (Abdo 2013; Brock 2020), in addition to eligibility for full tax relief on capital expenditure (Gosden 2013). Increasing critical voices towards the extraction of shale gas were dismissed by George Osborne arguing that 'of course there are proper environmental regulations there to protect local communities, but that shouldn't be an excuse for having to spend years trying to get planning permission' (as reported by Hayhurst 2013). Seven environmental charities (e.g. Friends of the Earth, WWF and Greenpeace) critiqued the Conservatives support for fracking, stating that it would raise unrealistic expectations. Andy Atkins (executive director of Friends of the Earth) argued that there is a 'deeply troubling trend among our political elite to disregard [British public] views and favour vested interests. Nothing exposes this more clearly than the appetite of our politicians to start fracking' (as reported by Hayhurst 2013). At the time, research had already been conducted to uncover the links between the government and industry,

'Fracking is embedded in a complex web of personal and institutional relationships and vested interests that transcend state institutions, fracking firms, and investors. In 2013, under David Cameron's government and at the height of the governmental push to develop a fracking industry, Mobbs mapped some of these links' (Brock 2020:3, for more research see Mobbs 2013).

At the same time, people who lived in oil and gas licenced areas started to receive letters through their door, or heard from their neighbour and/ or the local/ national newspaper that explorations might happen in their area. People started to inform themselves about drilling and fracking for shale gas by inviting speakers (e.g. from the US), looking at existing publications on the topic, and getting in touch with scientists (e.g. geologists) and campaigners from Friends of the Earth. In some places, oil and gas companies set up information meetings. Local people set up their own groups, events, giving presentations to their neighbours about their research and/ or setting up film evenings. The local groups soon realised what was entailed in the learning process.

'So, the way we split our group, we actually had different groups doing different things. I headed a subgroup which was media and communications, somebody else headed up a group called planning, where they look at the planning and things specifically, we had another group who looked at things like noise and you know, so we split the work up' (Interviewee 7).

In addition to finding out about the technology, geology, etc., information needed to be gathered about the planning system, regulations surrounding the oil and gas industry, policy developments, environmental assessment (and measurement

equipment), etc. Most people started off just wanting to inform themselves about the drilling process and its industry but soon after researching the topic wanted to find ways to stop these activities. This also happened in Balcombe (West Sussex, South England) – see box to read up more about the early experiences in Balcombe.

(Photo derived from DrillOrDrop.com)

Groups in Balcombe, West Sussex, South England

In April 2010, Cuadrilla Resources Ltd. (an oil and gas exploration and production company founded in 2007) was granted planning permission to drill an exploratory oil and gas borehole at the Balcombe site. One of the residents explained how they heard about the developments, 'we were on the train home from London when we noticed the article: 'Oil and gas company Cuadrilla to frack in Balcombe'. Fracking? In our village? It was December 2011 and we were still innocents. Back home we searched on the internet tales from America and from the Fylde region of Lancashire, where a well had been fracked by Cuadrilla earlier that year, causing an earthquake. We gathered in TV rooms and watched Gasland' (McWhirter, 2015:85). A meeting was organised in the Balcombe Village Hall where the Brighton Energy Coop (local energy cooperative) and Cuadrilla gave presentations in 2012. 'The whole village was there and they were all quite angry about it' (Interviewee 8). A poll showed that the majority of people who participated would oppose any further applications for exploration or extraction of hydrocarbons in Balcombe. During the meeting, it also became visible that some of the residents were worried about (and against) protestors from Brighton (local city nearby) arriving into their village. 'Balcombe is almost feudal, with farms, woodlands and many houses belonging to the one family, and rented to their workers. That family had leased its field to Cuadrilla. Rifts developed between friends, even within families' (McWhirter

2015:85).

A lot of local residents started to engage with the existing literature on the extraction of shale gas, the planning application process (possibilities to object to them) and other ways to stop the development e.g. writing letters to the prime minister, inviting speakers from e.g. Poland and Canada to speak to local residents, and holding public meetings and informing other residents. Two local groups emerged No Fracking in Balcombe (NoFIBS) and Frack Free Balcombe Resident Association (FFBRA) where membership has in parts overlapped. One of the main differences has been their stand on direct action. NoFIBS did not necessarily object to direct action whereas FFBRA did not want to engage in it. FFBRA was instead keen to stop the development by submitting objections to planning applications, lobbying politicians, organising polls in the village, taking a letter to Downing Street, and submitting legal challenges. For instance, in 2014, Cuadrilla submitted a planning application to West Sussex County Council to carry out flow testing and FFBRA submitted an objection. The planning permission was granted in the same year and FFBRA started legal proceedings in the High Court in a judicial review (i.e. a kind of court case, in which someone challenges the lawfulness of a government decision) of the decision. Although FFBRA won the right to challenge the decision in court, they lost the judicial review at the end of the year.

‘On 10 June 2013, three enormous lorry loads of drilling rigs arrived, from the nearby motorway junction, thundering past our primary school and homes to a drill site just south of the village, beside an ancient woodland’ (McWhirter 2015:86). Camps and protest outside the site spread out along the verge. The village was split about welcoming more protestors. As one of the interviewees explained, ‘we were blamed by the established people in the village for calling these people in. But we didn’t call these people in. But we did get very involved with the people at the camp... we got involved with being down there all the time, taking food and providing things that people needed’ (Interviewee 8). In August 2013, actions were held at the Reclaim the Power (a UK based direct action network fighting for social, environmental and economic justice) camp that around 200 people attended. Direct action consisted of, for instance, marches, wheelchair blockades, erection of camps, lock-ins and celebrity visits/ participants (e.g. Vivienne Westwood and Caroline Lucas (only Green Party MP)).

Sussex Police officers were very present and arrested several campaigners, including Caroline Lucas, who in addition to other campaigners was charged with obstructing the highway and a public order offence. ‘I’d never covered public order policing, never covered demonstrations before. So, this was astonishing to me. And I saw all these policemen march down the road. And at that point, a large number of campaigners, protesters went and sat on a log outside the entrance to the site and there was a kind of standoff... And I was astonished by this... And I was seeing police officers basically behaving like the paramilitaries. And why would the police do that in support of an industry? And why would people who were sitting on this log risk a criminal record to prevent this industry operating?’ (Interviewee 1). The campaigners were all acquitted of the charges in 2014. The protests made it into the national and international news. Please see Annex for the full Balcombe narrative.

Some people have argued that anti-fracking resistance really took off in Balcombe in 2013, when mass protests involving mass arrests made the headlines (Brock 2020).

‘And I think the Balcombe protests, which were on national television and in national newspapers where people could see what was happening, suddenly switched on people across the country to something that, you know, some people were concerned about. It switched people on to what the industry was hoping to do’ (Interviewee 1).

‘I guess the Balcombe events because that was obviously huge and again, I was not there but I feel like they really turned it into a national issue. And it was close enough to London to matter to the national newspapers. And Caroline Lucas [the only Green MP] got arrested all of that’ (Interviewee 2).

More camps were established to protest outside drilling sites in Lancashire, East Yorkshire, Nottinghamshire and Cheshire. Being aware of the increasing media attention to fracking activities, oil and gas companies started to apply for and were granted injunctions (i.e. a judicial order restraining a person from beginning or continuing an action threatening or invading the legal right of another) against ‘persons unknown’ trying to avoid further protest at drilling sites based on experiences in Balcombe. As argued by (Brock 2020:2),

‘Drilling companies and state actors have engaged in a diversity of tactics derived from counterinsurgency – to manage resistance and win the ‘hearts and minds’ of the population, from ‘greenwashing’ in schools to the brutal policing of dissent. Such policing has included the criminalisation of land protectors, targeting campaigners as ‘domestic extremists’, physical abuse, and entering public-private security partnerships with local police forces which involve the ‘outsourcing’ of police communication to drilling companies. Such actions are complemented by the contracting of large public relations (PR) firms, sponsorships of sports clubs and school competitions, and influencing local so-called democratic procedures.’⁶

For example, at the Preston New Road drilling site (in Lancashire, North England) injunctions have been put in place and extended for slow walking, lock-ons and obstructions of the highway. Several NGOs (such as Friends of the Earth) have launched legal proceedings to reduce the scale of these injunctions at different sites. They have been ‘criticised as assaults on the human right to meaningful protest under sections 10 and 11 of the Human Rights Act 1998’ (Brock 2020:11).

⁶ It is beyond the scope of this report to outline policing issues and industry and government interlinkages in greater depth. This is not to say that these are not extremely important topics. Some detailed research work has been conducted on these issues. For more information see the work by, for instance, Netpol 2018; Brock 2020; Hayhurst 2014.

Power and power relations (power over)

The concept of 'power over' relates to actors having power over others in social innovation in energy (SIE) related processes. There has been a wealth of research, in particular conducted by campaigners that have studied the political economy surrounding fracking (Brock 2020). Researching the fossil fuel industry (and in particular anti-fracking) Brock (2020:2, drawing on the work of Mobbs 2013) has argued that 'fracking is embedded in a complex web of personal and institutional relationships and vested interests that transcend state institutions, fracking firms, and investors... Fracking opposition is fuelled by this display of corporate power, as well as disillusionment about the lack of democratic decision-making, resource control and the role of the police in protecting extractive interests'. A very similar argument has also been made by McWhirter (2015:89), a resident and campaigner from Balcombe, 'we understand the opposition – the might and wealth of an oil and gas industry determined to prolong their dominion in the face of climate change. We have weathered misinformation in the right-wing press, and propaganda from a misguided government heavily lobbied and influenced by the oil and gas industry. We now face new laws that will speed up and facilitate permits for the industry, while removing individual and community rights; 'regulators' seemingly intent on pushing through government policy at all costs, ignoring the weight of the public opinion; government and industry bribes to councils and communities of £100,000 per well, 1% share of profits; the right to keep local business tax on oil exploitation for local use; poor regulations, self-monitoring by industry; a high rate of misshapes in the few UK wells already drilled' (McWhirter 2015:89). Several interviewees pointed out that they started off looking at the industry with open minds but as soon as they had conducted more research on the topic and tried to engage in lobbying activities, they wanted to take action against the industry (Interviewee 3,6,8). One of the interviewees talked about how she lost faith in the media, authorities and government through getting involved in the activities (Interviewee 8).

Divestment movement: A simple campaign?

For the divestment movement, this was a period where campaigners started to realise that taking actions to make universities divest might actually work (Interviewee 5). In 2014, the University of Glasgow became the first university in the UK to commit to fully divesting from fossil fuel industry companies. Full divestment meant the relocation of around £18 million of existing investments over a 10-year period. The decision was taken after a longer consultation period between the Glasgow University Climate Action Society and the University Investment Committee (University of Glasgow 2017).

'You get the first UK University divestment in October 2014, which is Glasgow. And I think that was the point at which everyone was kind of like, wow, like this could actually happen like a couple of years of campaigning on this where we have not had many wins' (Interviewee 5).

Several interviewees talked about the 'clarity' (Interviewee 3), 'simplicity' (Interviewee 10) and 'tangibility' (Interviewee 11) of the divestment campaign (and the arguments that it has been based on). There was a 'primary actor to blame' (i.e. the

fossil fuel industry) and key actors who can do something about it (i.e. organisations that invest in fossil fuel, e.g. universities). These two ingredients could be combined with a clear demand for organisations to stop investing in fossil fuel companies.

'I think the real beauty of divestment was that it was a very clear, reproducible, like campaign aim that spoke to a whole load of people. And I think, you know, the positive thing was that it made a very effective kind of argument, like, OK, these companies there are to blame. Obviously, there's room for nuances and complexities' (Interviewee 5).

'I suppose the tag line is that people are saying - I think it's really good because it makes a tangible difference and it creates that link between the system we live in, that has created a lot of the climate change and natural destruction. It's finding a good target and actively moving that money, it's something that anyone can do' (Interviewee 9).

Several campaign packages (i.e. outlining the key aspects of running a campaign) have been created over the years so that a campaign could be run at any university in the UK (see for instance the Divestment Creative Action Manual produced by People in Planet in 2014). One of the interviewees said that the 'campaign strategy could be taken to pretty much any part of the world and any town, any city. If you've got an institution that makes investments, you can run a campaign like this' (Interviewee 5). Many campaigns have started with petitions to make fellow students aware of the issues. Creative stunts, for instance, sit-ins, occupations, cycle demonstrations, occupations and marches were used to keep up the momentum. These activities have been combined with lobbying activities, which has meant talking to the university management and/or investment team and making clear demands. Students who got involved derived less from the hard-left but have been rather more liberal climate or sustainability conscious (with little previous experience around campaigning and direct action).

The simplicity of the campaign also was one of the key critiques of it. It was considered to be naïve and taking a hard-line stance, whilst said to have little influence on fossil fuel finance (Bergman 2018). The divestment movement has partly been aware of the shortcomings of their campaign. Rather than trying to bankrupt the industry (which they realised would not have been achievable), the main aims have been to create the political conditions to delegitimise the industry (i.e. undermine their social licence) and 'confront corporate power and change the narrative around climate change' (Bergman 2018:2).

Parts of the movement tried to establish the idea of reinvestment into their campaign. For instance, in 2013, 350.org published a reinvestment guide for university campaigners, arguing that endowments should be reinvested in 'climate solutions', but this framing did not really establish itself fully in the movement. The term 'ethical' investment was coined but as pointed out by one of the interviewees, people's ethics vary (Interviewee 9).

'I think it'd kind of ebbed and flowed [reinvestment idea], I think it has always been there from the beginning, but I think in some respects at the beginning it was hard to invest your money because investment managers weren't providing financially alternative investments. So, it was like a bigger step for people to move their money and actively reinvest in something greener' (Interviewee 9).

There have also been parts of the movement, who have linked the idea of divestment explicitly to economic arguments, pointing out that fossil fuel companies and their assets are currently overvalued, as much of their reserves will not be extracted if climate targets are to be met. The economic risk is that fossil fuel reserve and infrastructure values might fall drastically at some point due to being unusable i.e. becoming stranded assets; this could severely affect the global economy as the 'carbon bubble' bursts (Ansar et al. 2013). The financial argument has existed but did not spread in the movement.

'Personally, I don't feel like I knew the financial arguments super strongly, and the main argument that I used was, "You're not going to lose any money, so you might as well move the money." I wasn't using so much the argument of stranded assets and the carbon bubble, although I think it has been used by other investors and definitely helped the conversation' (Interviewee 9).

Even though several framings around the reasons and potential impacts of divestment emerged (creating a more liberal and radical view and several in between), one of the core arguments remained and has frequently been used to exclude the fossil fuel industry from organisations investment portfolios as a way to limit damage to their reputation and legitimacy.

The fight against opencast coalmine continued but mainly under the national radar

Opposition to opencast coalmines continued to grow in the UK during this period. Each planning application for an opencast coalmine led to community opposition groups forming. This meant gathering objections for planning applications and potentially providing evidence during planning meetings. Different to the anti-fracking activities, most of the applications for opencast coalmining had been in places where previously there was underground mining (e.g. Scotland, Wales and North England). This meant people were aware of some of the environmental impacts and changing job situation. Deep mining provided generations of families a job for life until the 1980s whereas work on opencast mines often is lower skilled, poorer paid and short-term. These places are also far away from London (and Whitehall), and have therefore been argued to be not on the political radar of the UK government. In 2014, seven new opencast coalmine applications were not put forward and/or rejected (e.g. in Whittonstall, Northumberland, North England).

This all happened in a context in which the quantity of coal produced in the UK had fallen since 2011 by 6 million tonnes. The main production of coal moved from Scotland to England in 2014, where 56% of coal output was in England and only 22% in both Scotland and Wales (Coal Action Network 2015). Part of the reason was that two coal companies went into liquidation in Scotland (i.e. Scottish Coal and ATH Resources) and closed their mines. But also, in England, UK Coal went through a financial restructuring, demonstrating an increasing decline of the industry. The liquidation of some coal companies left a few coalmines without resources for restoration work on the sites. Several unrestored sites were abandoned by the industry.

(Photo derived from Coal Action Network website: www.coalaction.org.uk)

Power and power relations (power to)

The concept of 'power to' relates to actors having different kinds/levels of power/capacity to mobilise social innovation in energy (SIE) resources-related resources and/or to achieve SIE-related goals. 'Power to' can therefore be summed up as people's capacity and resources to take action to be able to change the existing energy system (and its social relation within it). Resources for anti-fossil fuel activities are scarce in comparison to the fossil fuel industry. Local groups, grassroots networks and NGOs alike heavily rely on fundraising activities to pay for their activities. In particular, taking some of the legal actions involve extremely high costs.

'It cost us tens of thousands of pounds to fight it over the five years. And it took in my nearest three figures, maybe a hundred grand to do the fighting because we had to employ experts to look in for things like the visual impacts, looking at things like noise. We had experts to consult on noise. We had a health expert, you know, we had to engage people' (Interviewee 7).

Capacity building seems to be one of the core activities in the groups, often being described as a steep learning curve that they had to go through. A lot of the local capacity building on the ground is supported by regional and national organisation (e.g. Friends of the Earth and People and Planet). Sometimes, this happens through regional contact points, other times campaign manuals have been created that can easily be followed.

The idea of 'power to' can therefore point to different experiences related to anti-fossil fuel activities. Nonetheless, whilst conducting the fieldwork, one theme emerged several times: These are the personal journeys that most of the campaigners and/ or groups have gone through when starting to engage in framings against fossil fuel. These personal journeys provide a good understanding of how people got empowered by taking part and organising activities. But what they also highlighted is the amount of stamina that is needed over long periods of time to fight the industry. Here is a short summary of one of these personal stories,

'From a personal point, it has been an eye opener. It's been an awakening, if you will, because I was always in the past a typical conservative... My husband and I were semi-retired when we moved to the village... I didn't really think much about politics and since this has happened it has sort of turned my views on politicians around completely. I became more of an environmentalist... it woke me up, you know, to what we were doing to the environment, climate change issues... It took five years out of my life and I was absolutely, I didn't realise at the time it was all about fighting and moving forward. And when it all went away. When the threat went away, it's almost like there's been sort of a backlash. I'm absolutely drained' (Interviewee 7).

'I've spent a lot of the last 7 years talking to people, who have protested, who have basically changed their lives. And certainly, in the early days, a lot of those people were women. A lot of them were in their 40s and upwards. Some of them had taken early retirement and were basically spending what they had planned to be their early retirement campaigning against an industry that they disapproved of... I think it's quite fair to say that communities of interest have formed around this and huge friendships have been made' (Interviewee 1)

Time, social connectedness and emotional stamina seemed to be key. Quite a few people, who got involved were retired, students or employed by an organisation. This was not the case for everyone; others gave up parts of their work and started to work part-time. At the beginning, they did not probably think that it would come to this. But some interviewees talked about how the more they uncovered about the industry and their practices and the UK government's reactions to it, the more they wanted to stop it and spent more and more time and energy to do so. Moreover, they got contacted by other groups to talk about their experience and other activities emerged that needed to be done. Some people have spent most of their lives trying to stop the industry, going from one local campaign to the next,

'A lot of the people, climate, environmental campaigning, there are people who dedicate their lives to environmental campaigning, and they go around... move from one cause to another' (Interviewee 10).

Most interviewees also talked about the steep learning curve that they (and the group) had to go through to build the capacity to take diverse sets of actions against the industry. Some of the interviewees talked about how they used to

consider themselves to be shy because they never had spoken even at a dinner party, but now found themselves talking to large groups of people, giving media interviews and providing evidence at government select committees,

‘I think the key thing to remember is that we were a group of just normal residents that had no experience in fracking. We had no experience in the planning process. But we basically researched, we became aware that we were very concerned about fracking and we had to learn. It was huge learning curve, both the planning, how we could challenge the process and also understanding what fracking was, enough to be able to talk sensibly to the regulators, to whomever about it’ (Interviewee 6).

What also became apparent, in particular when talking to people involved in anti-fracking was that ‘probably something like 75% were generally women, 25% men’ (Interviewee 7). Most of the interviewees could not really provide an answer why this was necessarily the case. At the Preston New Road, Lancashire fracking site, a group called ‘Women in White’ carried out weekly peaceful protest activities that became well known. Some initial research has gone into the role of gender in anti-fracking protest. For example, Monk et al. (2019:64,75) have said that ‘women have long been at the forefront of various social movements and forms of emancipatory politics (Rosen 1974; Rowbotham 1992; Griffin 1995). Globally, there has been a resurgence in feminist activism and thought, with women becoming increasingly engaged in, and reconnected with, contemporary protest and acts of resistance (Mackay 2015; Cruz and Brown 2016; Moss and Maddrell 2017) ... Their presence has, in some instances, significantly shaped the nature and success of protest. It has, therefore, also shaped the response to protest. Women’s experience of violence during protest at the hands of the state—through state-sanctioned policies, military violence and police violence—though documented (Young 1990; Roseneil 1995; Al-Ali 2012; Human Rights Watch 2013; Tadros 2013, 2016) remains under-researched... Some women remained on the frontline of direct action for the duration of the protest and refused to be scared out of exercising their legal right to demonstrate peaceful opposition to fracking. They continued to represent the disorder that must be eradicated’.

Short summary

Looking at the second phase, some of the similarities between anti-fossil fuel activities become apparent. All of them seem to have a strong local and community base i.e. student and/ or resident groups that gain support from regional and national organisations, transferring knowledge and campaign tactics between groups. At the time, mobilisation surrounding anti-fracking and anti-coal is also based on an increasing industrialisation of the countryside with lasting environmental and health impacts for local residents. Some of the differences have also become visible. Around 2013, anti-fracking became not only a local issue but also a national one. In particular, protests in Balcombe made it more and more into the national press. This was not the case for anti-coal (and at the time, divestment), as outlined by Interviewee 2,

‘And anti-fracking resistance is really big in the media whereas anti coal really is not... At the same time, of course, I mean, there’s also coal happening in the UK which is something hardly anyone talks about. In the overall energy mix coal is so small now, but at the same time, they’re still pushing to open up new opencast coalmines.’

The coal industry was in decline. In addition, in comparison to, for instance, Germany, coalmines were ‘cute, they are tiny’ (Interviewee 2) in the UK. Still, there is a long legacy of coalmining in some areas of the UK (e.g. Yorkshire, Cumbria, Lancashire, Wales and the Scottish Central Belt), tying communities socially and culturally together. Studies show that the rapid closure of mines in the 1970s and 80s has had lasting impacts with former coal communities facing structural problems around higher levels of unemployment, incapacity benefit claims, and fewer available job positions that are still felt today (Foden et al. 2014). As Elliot (2016) notes, spending power was removed from these deindustrialising regions, and they have never recovered with high skill and high wage industrial jobs replaced by fewer low paid jobs and insecure work in the service sector. This long history has also shaped anti-coal activities where any kind of campaign needs to be closely aligned with the local community (Interviewee 11). As highlighted by Interviewee 2, ‘it’s obviously not the thing with fracking, it is new, dangerous and crazy. It’s easy for people to understand why it is a silly idea to pump stuff into the ground and hope that nothing happens’.

Occurring rather under the radar of national attention and press has also meant that anti-coal activities have been a ‘testing ground’ for several legal strategies, trying to ‘control’ the activities of protestors through law and police enforcements, as argued by Interviewee 2.

‘So, they get away with kind of testing thinking so trying out things in world of anti-coal resistance that they would otherwise not get away with in the world of anti-fracking resistance because it has become quite a high profile... I give you an example, there was a big court case against a few people who were evicted from an occupation of a coalmine and they were found not guilty and... still bailed away from the site and that was the first time that this happened in the UK’ (Interviewee 2).

Some of the interviewees pointed out how the extraction of fossil fuel is a highly political issue. Anti-fracking was happening in some rural areas where the Conservative Party had some of their core base of voters. Although, it might have taken quite a while for the Conservative Party to react, as public acceptance towards fracking decreased over time and local Conservative MPs realised the increasing mobilisation against the industry, the more the party had to realise that this is a controversial technology that might make them lose some of the core base. This was less the case for anti-coal.

Diversity, contestations and relations between actors

Contestations between different actors seem to be very clear in the case of anti-fossil fuel and fossil fuel. On the one side, there are campaigners who oppose fossil fuel through lobbying, direct action, education, etc. and on the other side, there

is the fossil fuel industry and their supports in, who put a lot of effort into creating a favourable social, policy and regulatory environment so that they can conduct lucrative extractions, etc. Organisations that get involved in anti-fossil fuel are diverse in relation to their aims, level of formality, actions and tactics that are decided on, geographical focus and politics of change. Rather than listing all possible relations and focus on contestations between campaigners and the industry, one re-occurring theme during the fieldwork is the topic of this box: Challenging, who is an activist and campaigner.

Looking at the experiences in Balcombe, West Sussex (see box page 21), it might be possible to draw boundaries between local residents (the ones who welcomed activists and the ones who did not), incoming activists and national campaign organisations. Whilst conducting the fieldwork, however, it became quickly apparent that these boundaries are often used by the national media, policymakers and industry to create divisions between anti-fossil fuel campaigners. For example, a common misconception has been that protests have mainly been organised by incoming campaigners rather than local residents.

‘And I mean, I think in a way it's problematic distinction anyway, because it seems that's one of the things newspapers do, it is used to kind of stigmatise and create divisions between local and not local’ (Interviewee 2).

Although some neighbours might no longer talk to each other in Balcombe, clear divisions usually do not exist. Interviewees rather talked about the people's willingness and sense of appropriateness of different actions and tactics that can be taken linked to anti-fossil fuel.

‘So, I think the interesting thing is that people have different ways of campaigning. So some people will focus on, you know, objecting against or supporting planning applications. Some people will do petitions. Some people will do direct action’ (Interviewee 2).

One of the interviewees talked about how she did not get involved in direct action but rather wanted to inform her neighbours, object to planning applications, provide evidence at reviews, etc. (Interviewee 6). Still, it was more of a sense of ‘we got used to the protest’ rather than an ‘us and them’ attitude that was often taken. One of the other misconceptions that was frequently made use of by most of the national media, industry and policymakers was that only green and/ or left-wing people would get involved,

You know, they're looking at us... as green blobs. And it was a deliberate tactic to try to suppress us, if you will, and to make it sound like we didn't have a legitimate case’ (Interviewee 7).

‘There have been so many amazing, I don't want to say old but elderly women, retired women maybe. Yeah that is really cool. Challenging who is an activist’ (Interviewee 2).

Most of the interviewees, who considered themselves as campaigners, felt that a diverse set of people got involved. They often said that through getting involved in anti-fossil fuel activities they have met people (or people had come into their life), who they would not have met otherwise, which had profound influences on their life (e.g. Interviewee 7, 8). They created friendships for life that they would not otherwise have had.

Phase 3 Local mobilisations and resulting national policy changes around anti-fossil fuels 2014-2015

Around the middle of the 2010s, mobilisations around anti-fossil fuel continued in the UK. It also became a time that was shaped by national policy developments, in particular surrounding the Infrastructure Act (influencing the National Policy Planning Framework (NPPF)) and the UK government's decision to phase out use of coal. Even though the divestment movement developed partly independently from national policy during this time, it gained more national media traction through some universities responding to the pressure derived from the activities.

Fossil fuel companies need to gain planning permission before they can start any activities locally. Who can make these decisions and how they are made has changed in the UK (see for instance the work by Johnstone 2014)? The importance of this process is highlighted by Brock (2020:6),

'The most important legislative battleground contesting fracking has been the national planning framework, modified to curtail the power of councils to reject planning decisions, in addition to financial incentives for the industry' (Brock 2020:6).

An example of the decision-making process concerning opencast coalmining is shown in the diagram below. For fracking this process looks slightly different and has changed, which is outlined in the next two upcoming historical phases of this account. The diagram is still relevant because it depicts what types of actors can be involved in the decision-making process. Moreover, it shows that decisions are taken at the local level (i.e. planning officer and/ or council) but also can go to the national level (i.e. Secretary of State).

Decision-making process concerning opencast coal mining in the UK (taken from Walsh et al. 1991)

More planning applications are being made for fracking: The Infrastructure Act comes in to ease the process

The Conservatives support of onshore gas continued in 2014. For example, the Environment Secretary argued that he wanted to see fracking across the UK. He considered environmental concerns to be unfounded. Moreover, the UK (led by David Cameron at the time) took a leading role against efforts of the European Union (EU) to set legally binding environmental regulations for the shale gas industry (as reported by Hayhurst 2014).

At the same time, several onshore oil and gas companies had been applying for planning permission in several locations across the UK (e.g. Lancashire, Yorkshire and Nottinghamshire), including Cuadrilla, who applied for eight wells at two sites in the Fylde district in Lancashire (North England). Most local councils started to realise that planning applications for shale gas (including fracking) should go to planning committees i.e. should not be decided by delegated powers so that both sides could voice their concerns and a decision would be made by an elective body rather than a planning officer, 'who has no democratic remit. So, I think councils responded to increasing [public] concern' (Interviewee 1). Rather than making the process more stringent, the industry seemed to want to go back to the 'good old days',

'And I remember sitting in an all-party parliamentary group and listening to somebody from Cuadrilla and he said, you know in the good old days you just go to a field with planning officer and say 'that's where we want to drill'. And the planning officer was saying 'yeah that looks all right...' And interestingly, the industry says, 'well, actually, that's how it should be, because, you know, we didn't cause any trouble. Nobody should have been getting worked up'' (Interviewee 1).

The existing planning system was critiqued in a report (compiled by a management and engineering consultancy), warning 'that investment in shale gas could be deterred because it was unclear whether the UK regulatory authorities could deal with the significant increase in applications needed in the production phase' (as reported by Hayhurst 2014). It concluded by calling for the easing of planning and consent processes. Members of the Conservative Party started to think about how to make this happen,

'In a leaked letter to the Economic Affairs Committee, George Osborne asked cabinet ministers for "rapid progress" on a number of actions to support fracking development, including intervening in local planning processes...' (Brock 2020:6).

In January 2014, secondary legislation (i.e. law created by ministers to fill in detail of an Act (primary legislation)) came into force which meant that land/ homeowners no longer needed to be notified of planning applications to drill for oil and gas under their homes. The Conservative Party brought the legislation in but at the time Labour went along with it, seeing that the legislation went through (Interviewee 1). It showed that the House of Common was not going to be in the way of fracking projects. Discussion around planning continued in 2015, starting with parliamentary discussions as part of the development of the Infrastructure Bill. Amendments to clauses on fracking were discussed and two groups of MPs called for a moratorium

on fracking in the UK. There was a rally outside Westminster, London in support of a moratorium and the Environmental Audit Committee argued that fracking was not in line with the UK's commitments surrounding the limitations of global climate change. Although they were heavily contested, the majority of the suggested changes to clauses about fracking for the Infrastructure Bill were rejected by the MPs (for a more detailed outline see Hayhurst 2015). A vote on a moratorium on fracking was heavily defeated after Labour abstained.

The Infrastructure Act was passed in February 2015. 'It gave the Energy Secretary a statutory responsibility to maximise the economic recovery of UK petroleum. Among other conditions, it prohibited fracking from depths of less than 1,000m and defined fracking by the volume of fluid used' (Hayhurst 2015). The change of the definition was key; rather than defining it via a particular extraction process, the Conservative Government defined it as 'the injection of more than 1,000 cubic litres of fluids at each stage (or expected stage), or the injection of more than 10,000 cubic litres of fluid in total'. Under the definition the first fracking attempt that caused small earthquakes in Blackpool, North England in 2011, would not have qualified under the definition.

In July, the UK government opened up large areas for oil and gas exploration and extraction by handing out new licenses. An overall total of 93 licenses were issued. Moreover, the decision on licensing was also devolved to the Scottish Government and the Welsh Assembly. In January 2015, the Scottish Government put a moratorium on planning consent for unconventional oil and gas extraction. In an almost identical situation to that in Scotland, the Welsh Government also announced a moratorium on fracking.

At the same time, the UK government public attitudes survey showed that opposition to shale gas has overtaken support for the first time. Moreover, more and more people started to become aware of the issue, in particular, local residents, who got a letter through the door, informing them of planning applications,

Before 2014, I was completely oblivious to any of the issues related to fracking except I've heard in the background that there'd been some earthquakes in Lancashire near where I live, but I haven't taken a lot of notice. What woke me up was the fact that Cuadrilla Resources had been doing some surveys in our local area. Again, I didn't take much notice of it. I just thought they were doing some geophysical survey. And then February, I think it's February the 4th, 2014, we got a letter through our door saying that Cuadrilla were looking to apply for planning permission to frack for gas in our village, basically. So of course, it was quite pertinent to me' (Interviewee 7).

Proposed fracking site, Roseacre Wood, Lancashire – Photo by DrillOrDrop.com

After an initial learning process based on reading up about the topic, contacting scientists and their local MP, setting up and joining local meetings about the topic between residents, attending the company's local PR events and/ or joining the community liaison groups, more and more local residents started to create their own local and/ or regional groups. For example, in Lancashire two local groups: the Preston New Road Action Group and Roseacre Awareness Group and a regional umbrella organisation Frack Off Lancashire were created – to campaign about two sites in the Fylde area that are not far from each other. Once the companies submitted their local planning applications, the work shifted somewhat. Having a more formalised group structure helped this shift. The mobilisation of people to get involved in sending in objections to planning applications (in particular how to do it so that they would be considered), getting experts involved to talk at planning hearings and writing to local MPs and/ or the prime minister were key activities.

UK government announced coal phase out: Opencast coalmining applications had to still be objected to on a one by one basis

In November 2015, there was another key policy announcement that shaped anti-fossil fuel activities (in addition to the Infrastructure Act). The UK government announced it would close all coal-fired power plants by 2025. The UK became the first country in the world to officially commit to phasing out its coal operation, just before the Paris Agreement meeting took place. The UK government also handed out commercial loans for the phase out of all of its deep mines to be closed – Thoresby, Hatfield and Kellingley Colliery. This meant that UK Coal, which used to be one of the largest coal businesses, stopped acting in mining. Six out of the 20 opencast coalmines were due to stop operating by the end of 2016.

Although the coal phase out was announced, it was not legislated; this meant that opencast coalmine applications had to still be fought 'on a case by case basis' (Interviewee 11). For example, the work of the Coal Action Network, supporting local

communities with objections to opencast coalmines needed to be continued. In addition, they also had to take up new activities: government lobbying work. Through the announcement of the coal phase out, the Coal Action Network saw a chance of raising local anti-coal issues in a national context. For quite a few years, these had been more a local fight, for example, trying to object to local planning applications. The announcement of the national policy target made it a more national issue again. Although the 2025 target was welcomed by some organisations, the Coal Action Network's campaign wanted to stress that 'coal mining needed to stop now and coal needed to stop now' rather than in 2025 (Interviewee 11).

'There were people saying, you know, there were local people, who were able to raise their voices and say every day this is going on our lungs and they get more polluted, we lose a bit more land nearby and our business gets damaged' (Interviewee 11).

The UK government ran a consultation on coal consultation that was based around understanding "how to take action to regulate the closure of unabated coal to provide greater market certainty for investors in the generation capacity that is to replace coal stations as they close, such as new gas generators" (BEIS 2016:6). It focused on issues including changes to the capacity market, security of supply and possible obligations on coal producers, as well as wider impacts of these proposals. The consultation document recognised that direct job losses of 150–200 for a large coal fired power plant, supply chain jobs in shipping and freight, as well as effects on local businesses and suppliers in nearby communities were all areas of concern. However, the impact assessment of coal phase out (published at the same time) did not look into how the local communities might be affected by the decision. This lack of attention was picked up by the Coal Action Network (CAN, 2016). In their response to the consultation, they argued that social issues needed to be prioritised within the phase out of coal.

Divestment movement became increasingly recognised

The divestment movement rapidly picked up during this period in the UK (Interviewee 5) but somehow detached from any type of policy developments. The Guardian (national newspaper) regularly started to report on the developments (and even run their own divestment campaign). The newspaper published several articles on the topic for about two months and had a special edition where divestment made it to the front cover (Interviewee 5). The fairly positive media experience for the divestment movement was a strong contrast to the complex relationship between other anti-fossil fuel groups and mainstream journalists. These advances meant that the divestment movement started to move from the universities to also other institutions as well (e.g. local authorities). More and more local campaigns emerged (see box to read up more about the Fossil Free Sussex experience).

Fossil Free Sussex, University of Sussex, South England

Fossil Free Sussex (local student-led divestment group) officially started at the University of Sussex in 2014. One of the master's students heard about divestment as part of a lecture by Jeremy Legget (British social entrepreneur). He started

to conduct his own research and decided to launch a Freedom of Information request to the University of Sussex, asking about their investments and endowment funds. At the same time, a small group of master's students got in touch with the master's student once they saw he had launched the request. Once they had the information, they tried to liaise with the University's Finance and Investment Committee, who engage with the investment manager. The Finance and Investment Committee felt that the fund was too small to actively manage it themselves and 'there are no eligible funds that we can put this money in that are fossil free that meet the criteria that you are asking of us' (Interviewee 10). Most of the students involved in the group had a sustainability/ climate change background and therefore little finance expertise. They had to 'learn quite a lot of the lexicon of finance in quite a short space of time' (Interviewee 10).

As part of their activities, the group connected with the local Students' Union and People and Planet, who organised a wider national student campaign to pressure universities to remove their investment from the fossil fuel industry. People and Planet provided less information about the finance sector but became really useful for the group when 'we started to come on to the activism side of it, the actual organising process and campaigning, and learning how to run a student campaign They were able to provide resources to us then, so they came and did like campaigning workshops' (Interviewee 10). They also provided an online platform from which the group could start their petition – 'the backbone of the campaign' (Interviewee 10). The strategy was to get as many people as possible to sign the petition, including some more high profile public figures. They wanted to 'demonstrate to the university management that there was a real appetite amongst students and staff to divest their endowment funds from fossil fuel' (Interviewee 10). The group organised a large rally to hand over the petition (which 2045 people signed) to the university management. Some of the other activities included film screenings of 'Do the Math' (i.e. Bill McKibben's film about divestment), banner drops, a critical mass protest as part of the Global Divestment Day and 'Red Line Demo' at the university's square.

Eventually, the university agreed to a task and finish group (which had no student representatives) to review their investment policy and introduced a new socially responsible investment portfolio. In 2018, the group could announce that the 'finance and investment committee have actually moved their money into a fund which doesn't invest in fossil fuel at all. So, essentially, we've had a victory essentially, a complete victory' (Interviewee 10). Despite moving their money into Liontrust (Sustainable Futures Management Fund), the University of Sussex has not yet written the explicit exclusion of investments in fossil fuels into university policy. For the full history of Fossil Free Sussex see the Annex 3.

Photo from Fossil Free Sussex, taken from 2018 victory video

Most of the interviewees mentioned the empowering effects divestment had on people who took part in the movement. The targeted campaigns gave people a feeling of agency that they could actually make a difference. Similarly, feelings of an opportunity to get involved in active change processes through collective action were expressed by students involved in the 'Fossil Free Sussex' campaign at the University of Sussex. A sense of togetherness was also created through organising and travelling to events together, for instance, going to the COP 21 in Paris. Many of the students, who got involved in the divestment movement during their university years, have gone on to be active in and driving wider climate and social justice movements in their day-to-day work afterwards. Impacts of the movement have therefore been evident both in terms of personal empowerment, taking people from being bystanders to being engaged activists, and in terms of reviving the (student) environmental movement (Bergman 2018).

Short summary

The third phase of framings against fossil fuel energy pathways makes visible the co-shaping of anti-fossil fuel and local and national policy developments. Policies have been developed to ease fossil fuel activities and phase them out, whilst at the same time, increasing mobilisation developed to either stop fossil fuel activities i.e. its emergence: fracking and its slow phase out: coal extraction. But not all anti-fossil fuel activities needed to engage with the national policy developments. As argued by one of the interviewees from the divestment movement,

'So, it's not to say that there hasn't been policy at the same time. I think in terms of the actual divestment campaign, I think what is often said is 'don't really worry about that stuff'. Like we're focusing on bringing down the fossil fuel industry and through doing that creating the space for all of that to happen' (Interviewee 5).

The interviewee went on to explain that most of the people in the divestment movement believed that first, the fossil fuel industry needed to be marginalised so that second, a low carbon energy transformation could happen. In order to marginalise the industry, the campaign involved targeting institutions that invested in the fossil fuel industry where no direct interactions with UK policymaking were needed.

Policies and policy making

The SONNET team is interested in building an understanding of how policies - policy strategies and instruments – enable and/or impede social innovation in energy to develop over time such as framings against fossil fuel energy pathways. In addition, the relative role of the urban, regional and national governance level is examined. This interest is led by the following question: How are people engaged in social innovation in energy and their interests being considered in policy-making processes, as well as how these are potentially empowering (or not) actors. Two policy changes are discussed in the box: first, changes to the planning framework and second, the Climate Change Act.

The historical account up to this point has already shown the key role of planning in anti-fossil fuel activities. Changes to the UK planning framework started around 2007. A series of white papers written under New Labour called for improvements to the planning framework to meet the challenges of the 21st century. These changes culminated in the unveiling of the Planning Act 2008. The aim was to streamline the planning process for infrastructure projects including ones related to energy (e.g. nuclear power stations). This aim continued under the Conservative–Liberal Democrat Coalition Government with the Localism Act 2011 and Conservative Government with the Infrastructure Act 2015 (Cotton 2016). The Town and Country Planning Act 1990 was altered with the intention of accelerating development by ending excessive delays on projects that already have planning permission. Planning powers were rescaled to the level of state control over site-specific planning development for infrastructure plans deemed to be of national significance (Marshall 2013). In practice, critics have suggested such systems have served to reinforce hierarchically organised political-administrative structures to create a top-down planning system (Johnston 2014). The consequences of these changes for anti-coal and anti-fracking activities are outlined in phase 4 of the historical account.

The UK has strict targets to reduce carbon emissions under the Paris Agreement, but also by its own legally binding Climate Change Act. The legislation commits the UK to reducing carbon emissions to below 80% of 1990 levels by 2050. The UK seems to have a clear policy on coal for electricity generation. It has pledged to phase out unabated coal-fired power generation by 2025, and it is a founding member of the international Powering Past Coal alliance. It still somehow feels unclear whether these policies and targets have led to the phase out of coal. First, the phase out is not legally binding and second, it did not prevent the opening of new opencast coalmines (or extension projects). One of the interviewees argued that local resistance often is not acknowledged enough when talking about the reasons for the decision to phase out coal but based on a more 'cynical' perspective the interviewee felt like the Conservatives could make the decision because they

were not upsetting their core voting base with it (Interviewee 11). Moreover, it has become a policy that the Conservative Party 'rolls out every time, they get queried on their environmental credentials' (Interviewee 11).

Phase 4 Increasing local protests and national actions surrounding anti-fossil fuel around 2015 – 2018

Local protests intensified across the UK in the period of 2015-2018. Strategies against fossil fuels involved more and more engagements with national level, for instance, including responses against the government's steps to ease the planning process for fracking applications and develop non-binary decisions for the phase out of coal. The divestment movement gained more and more national traction, including quite a few university decisions to divest. All these activities were supported by an increasing public awareness around climate change towards the end of this phase. Fridays for Future (global climate strike movement) arrived in the UK and Extinction Rebellion (an environmental movement with the stated aim of using nonviolent civil disobedience to compel government action to avoid tipping points in the climate system) was established in May 2018.

Let communities decide: Proposed changes to the National Planning Policy Framework to ease fracking

During 2015, oil and gas industry representatives had repeatedly complained about long planning delays to shale gas applications, so the UK government took various steps to speed them up. In August 2015, the UK government changed planning rules to allow the Secretary of State to make the final decisions on planning appeals on shale gas exploration and extraction (making it a national issue). This also meant being able to overturn initial local authority decisions. The decision became relevant for lots of planning applications, including the two taken by Lancashire County Council one for each site in the Fylde area in 2015.

'When the Preston New Road and Roseacre Wood fracking applications came before Lancashire County Council that was an extraordinary event. More than 90,000 people signed a petition against the proposals... It was a very powerful expression of how people felt about fracking in their area. And it was also very powerful expression of why the industry thought it should happen' (Interviewee 1).

Lancashire County Council rejected the planning application for both sites. Cuadrilla handed in its first appeal against the refusal of planning permission for shale gas exploration in August 2015. In October, it was confirmed that there would be a public inquiry (these are major investigations into public concerns, scrutinising past decisions and events and convened by a government minister) into Cuadrilla's appeal, which took place from February to March 2016. The recommendation from the planning inspector was sent to the Secretary of State in July 2016. It took until October 2016 for the Secretary of State to announce that he would rule against the refusal of planning permission to frack at the Roseacre Wood site if the traffic

problems could be resolved (i.e. reopening a public inquiry). In the case of Preston New Road site, the Secretary of State overturned Lancashire County Councils decisions on fracking. The decision was taken a day after the Paris Agreement on Climate Change was reached. At the time, the Preston New Road Action Group published the following press release,

‘Preston New Road Action Group are devastated to learn that Sajid Javid, the Secretary of State for Local Government and Communities has upheld the appeals in favour of Cuadrilla, and overruled local democracy... Effectively, an external corporate industry is controlling local democratic planning decisions’ (PNRAG 2016 – on their website).

Lancashire City Council meeting - Photo DrillOrDrop.com

Two challenges were made against the Secretary of State in the High Court about his decision to grant planning permission to Cuadrilla to drill and frack Preston New Road. The challenges were based on the minister’s decision failing to take into account climate change and regulation to protect public health. But in April 2017, the community groups and an anti-fracking campaigner lost their legal challenge against the Secretary of State. In August 2017, Cuadrilla began drilling at Preston New Road, setting in motion several local actions (see green box ‘Roseacre Awareness Group and Preston New Road Action Group’ for more details on the developments of fracking in the Fylde area).

Roseacre Awareness Group & Preston New Road Action Group, Lancashire

‘The planning inquiry into Cuadrilla’s appeal on fracking at Preston New Road and Roseacre Wood was highly significant. It was like a primer on fracking’ (Interviewee 1). These are the two pathways of the two sites from the moment the Secretary of State made his decision in 2016.

Roseacre Wood's pathway

It took until October 2016 for the Secretary of State to announce that he would allow against the refusal of planning permission to frack Roseacre Wood if the traffic problems could be resolved. He reopened the public inquiry so that Cuadrilla was able to provide additional evidence on highway safety. The inquiry opened in April 2018, after a failed attempt for a statutory challenge against the decision to reopen the inquiry. The inspector of the re-opened inquiry submitted his report in September 2018. Five months later, the Secretary of State refused Cuadrilla's appeal.

'Our case was always a silly one to do with traffic. It wasn't much to do with climate change or pollution, although those were all factors. But the big factor at Roseacre were those huge HGVs trundling up and down country lanes. And the fact that it was a totally unsuitable industry in the middle of a very agricultural rural area, which was known for rural tourism' (Interviewee 7).

Preston New Road's pathway

Rather than reopening the public inquiry as in the case of Roseacre Wood, the Secretary of State announced that he would overturn Lancashire County Councils decisions on fracking at Preston New Road. At the time, the Preston New Road Action Group (PNRAG) wrote a press release as a response to the decision,

'Preston New Road Action Group are devastated to learn that Sajid Javid, the Secretary of State for Local Government and Communities has upheld the appeals in favour of Cuadrilla, and overruled local democracy... Over 100,000 people objected to fracking here: unprecedented numbers of the community said no. Due democratic process has been followed but our local community will feel ignored and overruled by this decision. Effectively, an external corporate industry is controlling local democratic planning decisions' (PNRAG 2016 on their website).

In November 2016, PNRAG (represented by a law firm) issued formal legal proceedings at the High Court against the government's decision to grant permission to frack at the Preston New Road site. The group had written to the Secretary of State, asking him to reconsider his decision but he refused. They argued that the 'government's decision to overrule Lancashire County Council's refusal of planning permission for fracking in Flyde, Lancashire is unlawful because the decision is fundamentally flawed as it failed to properly apply relevant planning laws and policy' (PNRAG 2016 on their website).

In January 2017, Cuadrilla started construction work at the site. Some people involved in anti-fracking increased their lobbying work and took part in preparing the formal legal and regulatory proceedings (which included e.g. engaging with experts, reviewing documents and liaising with regulators and legal teams (such as the Environment Agency)). Other people also got involved in direct action that had been at the site from the beginning, but which now intensified. It consisted of 'slow-walking (in front of delivery lorries), blockading sites (e.g. with lock-on devices, or 'lorrysurfing'), demonstrations, and marches' (Brock 2020:3).

'Our position [PNRAG] was that we were challenging through the official channels. So, we did our challenging through the planning process, through the regulators, through that route. And as a group, we didn't tend to get involved in the direct action although some members of the group obviously did take part. But as far as a whole, the group the challenge was more around the court cases and the liaising with the regulators and that side of things' (Interviewee 6). In addition, the group installed their own monitoring equipment to be able to check the water and air quality and noise levels.

In February 2017, two rallies against fracking were organised, attracting hundreds of people from across the country whilst in May, people arrived from across Europe to support the protests. Local councillors, celebrities, and politicians joined in. In the summer of 2017, the Camp of New Hope held a large energy symposium organised by Biofuelwatch, Coal Action Network and Reclaim the Power. During July, Reclaim the Power held a month of 'rolling resistance' (as reported by Hayhurst 2017).

'I was always particularly impressed by Preston New Road because it was there for five years and people were there for five years day and night. And there were always people at the gates for years... Because it's quite easy to do an action somewhere and maybe people are arrested and have a trial and that's over. But to really stick on and stay with it for so many years. Every morning getting police abuse, trauma, to make yourself come to that gate, sing and knit. I think that is really quite impressive. In the snow, in the rain, in the cold...' (Interviewee 2).

One of the interviewees reflected upon how the campaign had changed for her over the years, 'originally, it was very local, very focused on specific issues... And then it got bigger. And then, we would have big events set by big locations within Lancashire, particularly in this area in the Fylde, where we're under threat, where we would literally get thousands of people. So we'd have things like where we have scientists come along to talk and people could question people who've got more experience about these things... There were really big events where thousands of people turned up. And then we concentrated on getting into London because we realised that to be effective, it's the government, the MPs that you had to effect... We liaised with the national groups as well... like Frack Free United, who are particularly focused on the lobbying of MPs. There is Talk Fracking with Vivienne Westwood... who did a lot to like the campaigning in London and celebrity engagement and things like that. The Nanas⁷ also some of them were originally part of the Occupy movement' (Interviewee 7).

In June 2017, the court upheld a right of appeal against the decision to allow fracking at the Preston New Road site. In August 2017, Cuadrilla began drilling at Preston New Road and applied to vary the planning conditions in November of the same year. The PNRAG's appeal was rejected by the Royal Courts of Justice in January 2018. In March, the group

⁷ The Lancashire Nanas have been part of the Preston New Road resistance from the beginning. 'These ladies come armed with fruitcake and fury. They sing, wave banners and get through a seemingly inordinate amount of tea. Occasionally, there's dancing. On Wednesdays, they wear white as a symbol of peaceful protest and hold a silent vigil' (Independent 2018).

decided not to progress the challenge in the Supreme Court. Please see Annex 3 for the full historical narrative of both groups.

Preston New Road fracking site picture from Independent newspaper, 2019

In October 2017, a ministerial statement came out announcing that fracking application could be ‘classed as nationally-significant infrastructure projects to be decided by a government-appointed inspector. Non-fracking shale gas proposals in England could become permitted development under the proposals, avoiding the need to go through the full planning system’ (as reported by Hayhurst 2018).

A bit later on and not connected; two consultations were opened on the government’s proposal to fast-track decisions on shale gas. In July 2018, the revised National Planning Policy Framework (NPPF) was published. It required ‘English councils to recognise what are described as the benefits of onshore hydrocarbons, including shale gas, for energy security and transition to a low carbon economy. Councils are also required to ‘put in place policies to facilitate their [onshore hydrocarbons] exploration and extraction” and ‘plan positively for them” (as reported by Hayhurst 2018). In October 2018, three petitions were handed to the UK government with a total of 300,000 signatures that opposed the plans to fast-track fracking planning decisions in England. The ‘Let Communities Decide’ campaign and associated week of local action organised mainly by Go Fossil Fuel took place.

'The slogan was 'Let Communities Decide'. And it really brought together grassroots campaigners, Friends of the Earth, CPRE, Frack Free United, which was some kind of umbrella group, and 38 degrees and 350.org. It was a very effective campaign. It was all really about local democracy because it would have removed local decision-making' (Interviewee 1).

'Let communities decide' photo by Frack Off London

In August 2018, Leigh Day (a law firm), who represented Talk Fracking (anti-shale group) asked the Secretary of State to withdraw the paragraph on fracking in the Framework. They made the argument that the revised NPPF did not take into account the greenhouse gas emissions from fracking, measuring methane releases and impacts on air quality. Moreover, the revised NPPF was not in line with the government's Clean Growth Strategy that was published in 2018. In December, Friends of the Earth and Talk Fracking (through its member Claire Stephenson) sought judicial reviews of the revised NPPF in the High Court. In March 2019, the High Court ruled on the two challenges to the NPPF, one brought by Friends of the Earth and the other by Talk Fracking. Talk Fracking's case actually won. It focused on a specific policy of the NPPF: its approach to planning for shale gas and oil extraction by mineral planning authorities.

'Ms Stephenson [member of Talk Fracking] said new scientific developments cast doubts on the government's position that onshore shale gas had a lower carbon footprint than imported liquid natural gas. The case centred on paragraph 209a in the NPPF which said local authorities should develop policies to facilitate onshore oil and gas exploration and extraction and recognise their benefits in supporting a transition to a low-carbon economy. Talk Fracking said the government should have considered new evidence submitted to a public consultation, which challenged the policy. Ministers acted unlawfully the group said, because they failed to consider the Mobbs Report... Mr Justice Dove [judge] said adopting Paragraph 209a into

the NPPF was unlawful because the government had failed to take into account the scientific developments over carbon claims' (Hayhurst 2019).

The Mobbs report was commissioned for Talk Fracking and came out in 2017. It detailed that the UK government's assessment of the climate change impacts (as outlined in the Mackay-Stone review) were unsound due to poor quality data that was used for the analysis. It disputed that shale gas is a bridging fossil fuel towards a low carbon pathway.

'The 2015 statement that fracking supports a low-carbon economy was never consulted upon, and the Judge was critical of the way the Government, during last year's consultation exercise, tried to shoehorn that statement into national policy whilst brushing off public objections to the basis for doing so' (Leigh Day, law company representing Talk Fracking as reported by Hayhurst 2019).

This decision meant that future planning applications for fracking have been able to be objected to on current scientific evidence, especially about climate change, as opposed to government policy insisting on the great need for oil and gas extractions. In March 2019, the UK government's plan for fast-track planning decisions on fracking was discussed in the House of Commons. A few months later, MPs still asked for a decision on it but nothing happened. In any case, work at the Preston New Road site came to a halt in August 2019 after Cuadrilla started fracking its second well on site after abandoning the first well following multiple shutdowns because of tremors. On 26 August 2019, the bank holiday Monday, another earthquake - the biggest fracking induced earthquake in the UK – brought a halt to fracking. In November 2019, the UK government ordered an immediate moratorium on fracking.

'Outside' institutional environment shaping the development of the SIE-field

The SIE-field (and its actors) – framings against fossil fuel energy pathways - are nested within an 'outside' institutional environment linked to an energy system that is constituted by formal and informal institutions that shape the activities of actors within the SIE-field. Although energy systems consist of a wide range of institutionalised rules, norms, and beliefs, these institutions have been subject to profound changes over the past decade. These changes are due to manifold developments and can be grounded in events and contestations, inter-field interactions, external shocks and societal trends. In the SONNET team, we are interested in the 'outside' institutional environment that 'surrounds' and 'penetrates' the SIE-field. We want to understand how dominant institutions (regulative, normative and cultural-cognitive elements) within the 'outside' institutional environment influence the emergence and development of framings against fossil fuel energy pathways.

Much could be said about 'outside' institutional environment surrounding and penetrating framings against fossil fuel energy pathways. Here, the state and industry (and their interlinkages) play a prominent role, including efforts to deal with an increasing public opposition (e.g. policing protestors and controlling discourses and knowledge (see Brock 2020)),

buy consent (e.g. corporate sponsorship and tax hand-outs (see Brock 2020)), ignore some of the issues of local residents in areas affected by fossil fuel (in particular the coal regions in North of England), lack of legislated strategies to achieve climate targets, and decrease regulatory and legislative barriers for the industry (e.g. announcement of the coal phase out (without legislation), changing the definition of fracking, and fast-track planning processes). Much research has gone into these issues that I am not able to summarise in this box (due to time constraints).

The moratorium on fracking might be a relevant moment to think a bit about the 'outside' institutional environment. Several arguments have been made when trying to explain the reasons for the moratorium on fracking (also by some of the interviewees), for example, increasing public discourse (and actions) against fracking, persisting 'shocks' in the form of earthquakes i.e. industry causing seismic tremors and decreasing support for fracking within the UK parliament. Whilst discussing some of the arguments, it is important to keep in mind that a moratorium is a 'hold' on fracking (and not a decision to stop it). Moreover, the narrowing of the definition of fracking meant that most onshore oil and gas extractions do not fall under the moratorium. It might therefore be possible to argue that narrowing the definition of fracking and putting in a moratorium (rather than a stop) have also been ways to 'manage' the public discourse and ease processes for the fossil fuel industry. During the moratorium, the industry is able to develop the fracking technology (maybe without the scrutiny of the public) whilst continuing some of the exploration and extraction work that does not fall under the definition.

'No, I really don't think it's over. I think it could all change back again very quickly. And it could carry on in the way that it is with, you know, decisions being made one way or another' (Interviewee 1).

Ditch coal now: Phase out of coal is not happening fast enough

Local protests also intensified around anti-coal in the period of 2015-2018. For example, in South Wales at the largest opencast coalmine in Ffos-y-frân and nearby coal fired power station in Aberthaw, Coal Action Network, Reclaim the Power, Bristol Rising Tide (a local group of a national network taking direct action for climate justice) and United Valley's Action Group (local anti-coal group) started a series of actions. Activities included displaying banners that read 'End Coal Now', demonstrations on the beach, stopping vehicles from accessing the sites, crowd walking and creative blockages (but also included petitions, court battles and public inquiries in previous years).

'Aberthaw power station was the dirtiest power station in terms of nitrogen oxides in the UK, with the UK government allowing it to breach European Union air quality standards. The levels of toxins were more than double those from other power stations' (Coal Action Network website).

Aberthaw power station in South Wales

The environmental lawyers, Client Earth, took the UK government to the European Court over the breaches, which ruled against them. Greenpeace and Friends of the Earth had reported on the air pollution due to high nitrogen oxides levels. Actions intensified after the ruling. In 2017, a mass trespass and blockages were organised to shut down the opencast coalmine in Ffos-y-frân.

'We climbed down towards the bottom of the vast hole that Miller Argent's operations have ripped into the earth to find their 300 tonne hydraulic excavators. These are used to extract coal from the mine – five million tonnes of coal have already been extracted from Ffos-y-frân, with another six million to go – fifteen to sixteen hours a day. Following a little exploration of the excavator, we used D-locks to attach ourselves to the machine, got books, earphones, sleeping bags and sandwiches out and prepared for a long day in the pit' (Coal Action Network website).

The campaigners were dressed as bright yellow canaries, symbolising the small yellow bird that used to be taken down coalmines and the dangers of coalmining. If dangerous gases collected in the mine, it would kill the canary before the miners, thus providing early warning signals. The campaigners were arrested and sentenced to pay a large compensation charge to the coal company.

At the same time as these local direct actions took place, the UK governments coal phase out consultation took place⁸. It was accompanied by civil society organisations and NGOs sending in responses to the consultation (outlining reasons for opposition to the government's plan and demanding an end to coal now) and organising protests at the Department of Business, Energy Industry and Industrial Strategy (BEIS) in London. For instance, the 'Ditch Coal Now!' demonstration was a collaboration between the Coal Action Network, Friends of the Earth, London Mining Network and other organisations. In addition to the call to stop coal earlier, the plan to phase out coal was considered to consist of 'loopholes' (e.g. 'no mention of the impacts of coal mining' and no recommendations of 'any legislation which will encourage power stations to close prior to 2025') as argued by the Coal Action Network and Biofuelwatch (2016:2). Moreover, coal fired power stations still received subsidies to keep on operating (e.g. capacity market payments).

'We welcome a final end date for coal usage in the UK. However, this does not mean that all the battles in relation to coal have been won, there is still huge amounts of work to be done to get companies to begin to restore the damage caused by opencast coal mining and to support those working in the coal industry into new employment' (Coal Action Network website).

Applications for opencast coalmining still had to be fought on a case-by-case basis (Interviewee 11). This also did not change during this time period. Nonetheless, how and on what grounds applications could be fought was changing. First, local campaign groups started to work more closely with each other i.e. benefitting from exchanging, learning from each other and offering each other practical support, whereas beforehand groups used to carry out their own local campaigns (based on their own local issues). Second, groups started to appeal (and could do so) to the Secretary of State to call in planning decisions made by the council (i.e. making these decisions a national issue). Moreover, this could be done on climate change grounds (rather than based on local issues, e.g. noise levels). Two planning applications submitted by the mining company Banks Group in 2018 made these changes particularly visible: Highthorn coalmine next to Druridge Bay in Northumberland and Bradley coalmine near Dipton in County Durham (see page 17 for a short introduction to the local campaign).

In 2016, Northumberland County Council granted planning permission to Banks Group. The community led 'Save Druridge' campaign continued to try and stop the developments. The Secretary of State subsequently called in the decision for review. A public inquiry into the proposal was held in 2017. Friends of the Earth and the Coal Action network provided some evidence. Although the planning inspector gave the recommendation to approve the application (because it was of 'national interest'), the Secretary of State refused the planning permission in 2018.

'We didn't use arguments about climate change very much because they weren't considered necessary at a local level to

⁸ At the same time, Prime Minister, Theresa May, confirmed the UK coal phase out during a speech held in Canada, announcing a global alliance to end coal power – 'Power Past Coal'.

stop the mine. This changed over the last years. Druridge Bay has been kind of a turning point... But I know that earlier on it was quite normal for communities to form their action groups based solely around, for instance, noise... whereas what I see now is the community talking more about climate change... and trying to stop it as an industry' (Interviewee 11).

Banks Group went to the High Court to try get the decision by the Secretary of State overruled. The applicability of parts of the National Planning Policy Framework (NPPF) was discussed in court, based on the environmental harm of the prospected coalmine and status of coal and its national importance (see Coal Action Network website). In November 2018, the High Court overruled the Secretary of State's rejection decision; the case was sent back to the Secretary of State. It took until October 2020 for the Secretary of State, Rt Hon Robert Jenrick MP, to refuse permission for the Highthorn coalmine.

At the same time as the Secretary of State was asked to call in the decision on the Highthorn coalmine in 2017, a nearby community led campaign group, Protect Pont Valley, tried to do the same for the Bradley coalmine. The results were very different, demonstrating even more that the rejection of planning applications for opencast coalmines (even at the national level and with the announcement of the coal phase out) were not clear-cut. In 2018, Banks Group acquired the mining rights won by the liquidated UK Coal. The Campaign to Protect Pont Valley teamed up with national and international activists to continue their campaign to Protect Pont Valley. At the beginning, a coalition of groups (e.g. Pont Valley Network and Coal Action Network) appealed to the Secretary of State via letter to revoke Banks' permit, followed by a signature petition and protest art installation (created by Art Rise Up). The campaigners (also with the help of, e.g. Greenpeace and 38 Degrees) kept on sending letters even without gaining a response. The Coal Action Network acted as a facilitator when the option was discussed to work with other campaigners (e.g. previously occupying the Hambacher Forrest) to take direct action against the coalmine going ahead.

'What we do is try and facilitate decisions and decide strategically if people want our advice. Just trying to give the community as many options as they can introduce them to people who can help them. So sometimes these are activists who will sit down in a road and sometimes it is lawyers' (Interviewee 11).

The Pont Valley Protection Camp was set up. It was winter in the North of England. Campaigners erected their tents in the snow, which meant regularly having to dig out the entrance of the tent in the morning. Communal spaces were created with 'lots of binding in there... chatting, singing and playing the guitar' (Interviewee 2). There was a kitchen but lots of local resident also brought food, supplies and moral support. The aim was to try to slow down Banks' preparatory work on site because the company's planning permission was due to run out in June 2018 (and they needed to complete this work to keep their permission). Activities included, for instance, continuous lock-ons and human chains.

'Usually the day started off. It's like literally getting your tent out from under the snow... Yeah, it was all about occupying the land. So, to stop them from actually starting the operations on the land... And the last 48 hours were like in a film like. There were lock-ons, lock-ons, lock-ons. The last night, it was raining and it was dark and people were locked on... And we were

just sitting... oh my god four hours left' (Interviewee 2).

Although the coal company was not able to complete the work as outlined in the planning permission, the council decided not to enforce the planning restrictions. The work at the coalmining site went ahead. Over the past two years, the campaign went on to prevent further planning permissions for the extension of the mine (for the full story of Pont Valley campaign see the Annex 3).

The height of the divestment movement: Normalisation creeping in?

Several universities, throughout 2015, including the University of Oxford, SOAS, and London School of Economics announced their divestment from fossil fuels. In 2017, the UK emerged as the leading country in university divestments, with over £80 billion divested. In 2018, three Russell Group universities, including Durham, Cardiff and Bristol fully divested, in addition to Huddersfield, Sussex, Edinburgh and Anglia Ruskin that excluded all fossil fuels in the same year. The University of Edinburgh (which had one of the largest endowment funds in Scotland) committed to divest from fossil fuel, alongside a pledge to reinvest in low carbon energy sources.

'Probably early 2015 through 16, 17, 18, 2019, which was just like a ton of wins, like the universe, like, you know, the dominoes of the universe' (Interviewee 5).

Not all universities have made pledges. For instance, the other Russell Group universities had not divested, e.g. Leeds, Liverpool, Manchester, Exeter and York, and Imperial College London. Moreover, universities made different sorts of pledges, with varying degrees of commitment to divest from fossil fuels. Some have also promised to invest in low carbon technologies.

'The level of commitment within each statement from each university differs. Some of them have said they'll consider divesting, some of them have said at some point in the future they'll divest, some of them have said they'll only divest from coal and tar sands, and then some have agreed to divest fully as soon as possible' (Interviewee 10).

In 2019, People and Planet conducted some research into some of the pledges that had been made. They found, for instance, the University of Sheffield had not made good on their promise to divest from fossil fuel. Attempts were made to start up a follow up campaign. Such follow-up campaigns have been rare. Although universities provide a good space to mobilise an active group of people i.e. due to providing a location and network of people, it is also a space that is extremely transient. Students usually stay for 3-4 years at the university and then move on. A lot of the pledges could therefore not be followed up because the core group of students, who might have led the campaign, were no longer around (Interviewee 5).

Towards the end of this period, it became harder for campaigners to get national media coverage when a university or other

institution committed to divest. One of the interviewees said that divestment became more mainstream during these times (Interviewee 5). For universities, divestment became a legitimate activity and therefore no longer really needing a campaign to push for it (Bergman 2018). During this time, a divestment forum was set between different grassroots organisations and NGOs (e.g. People and Planet, 350.org, and Friends of the Earth) to discuss the progress of the movement and what to do next.

Power and power relations (power with)

The concept of ‘power with’ relates to actors holding and exercising power together with other actors to achieve collective goals, through e.g. strategic collaboration, pooling resources, joining forces, etc. There are several ways in which anti-fossil fuel groups (including actors and organisations) seem to collaborate and support each other: creating networks and intermediary organisations, encouraging people to get engaged in several activities, creating a core base of people to work on the campaign, developing clear messages for the campaign, having diverse strategies and tactics, helping to spread each other’s messages and activities, and raising the profile of climate change to be able to influence decision-making, just to mention a few. It might be worth highlighting two aspects that have been particularly mentioned by the interviewees: role of social media & networks and increasing public discourse around climate change. The role of social media and networks is best described by Interviewee 1,

‘And social media, I think it's been hugely influential in the anti-fracking movement. This is how people have connected... It's allowed people to communicate information and ideas. There are people in the anti-fracking movement who have connections all over the country... It enabled people to talk to each other. It enables people to share information. There was a lot of live streaming video... I think that was quite influential. So, when there were protests at Preston New Road, where there were protests... it allowed people to film and live stream it in real time of what was happening... And I think that probably was hugely influential because... it illustrated that the police were preventing protests or trying to prevent protests.’

Social media has therefore allowed groups to document protests and their policing to tell their own stories of what has been happening whilst at the same time, share these stories with a network of other groups – not only nationally but also internationally. Experiences, knowledge and support can be shared more widely and quickly, making it easier to support each other. Generally, there seems to have been a shift from local groups trying to fight their own battle to supporting other groups (regionally, nationally and internationally), making anti-fossil fuel a larger issue. Greater connectivity and support for each other has also contributed to being able to fight anti-fossil activities based on climate change grounds. For example, whilst several years ago, planning applications were won on local grounds such as issues related to noise levels and road infrastructure, it seems that more and more climate change could become a determining factor (but this still is to be seen).

'And then, of course, now also even in the UK, the climate change discussions are becoming kind of bigger and more in mainstream media' (Interviewee 2).

A lot of the anti-fossil fuel activities mentioned in this report occur in spaces where people's identities are connected to a sense of place: students and their university and local residents and their village. This can ease the mobilisation of people for the campaign. Interviewee 5 explained how it was not easy to move the divestment movement to other targets than universities.

'So, we tried to get students to do actions targeting Barclay's banks themselves, which, you know, was successful to a degree. But again, you have the challenge of like if you're a student on a campus, it's quite easy to mobilise... You know, obviously, there's a long history of students campaigning, you know, whether it's anti-war or all kinds of things that aren't directly related to them as students, but it's just kind of like another barrier... It's like you have even less of an affinity to your insurance company' (Interviewee 5).

Short summary

At the end of this phase, climate change rose up on the social, cultural and political agenda in the UK. The Paris agreement has required actions to be taken to prevent global temperatures from rising by 2 degrees and pursue efforts to keep them from 1.5 degrees rise. Fridays for Future arrived in the UK and Extinction Rebellion was established in May 2018. Climate emergencies were declared by the Scottish parliament, National Assembly for Wales and Parliament of the UK (in addition to several councils). At this stage, these changes did not really change the National Planning Policy Framework (that is key for anti-coal and anti-fracking) but influenced the public support against fracking and helped anti-coal campaigners to partly make a case against opencast coalmine on climate change grounds. Although climate change is not mentioned in planning decisions, it started to frame some decision-making surrounding anti-coal,

'The National Planning Policy Framework hasn't moved on very much, for example, in a recent local hearing that we had where a coalmine was stopped, the councillors in the hearing, who were making a decision, talked a lot about climate change... The motivation on the part of the decision makers was coming from some kind of another place, which is the wider public concern around climate change, which they might also share...' (Interviewee 11).

This was not the case for anti-fracking, which was still supported by the UK government. The role of the Secretary of State had become a crucial one. In the case of anti-coal, some campaigners appealed to the Secretary of State to call in planning decisions for coalmines (i.e. making it a national concern) due to the announcement of the coal phase out. This was not the case for anti-fracking, where the supportive environment for fracking derived from the UK government, creating a situation where campaigners wanted to keep planning decisions locally under the call of letting communities decide. But although anti-coal campaigns had a more favourable policy environment, as the historical account has shown, the fight to stop

opencast coalmining was far from straightforward.

Regulative, normative and/ or cultural cognitive institutions

The SONNET team is interested in trying to build an understanding of how dominant institutions (regulative, normative and cultural-cognitive elements) within the ‘outside’ institutional environment influence the emergence and development of social innovation in energy – framings against anti-fossil fuel energy pathways. Institutions are made up of regulative, normative and cultural-cognitive elements. They are tacitly or explicitly agreed upon rules constraining or enabling activities of actors that provide stability and meaning to social life. These can be: 1) Regulative institutions: laws, rules, standards, policies, 2) Normative institutions: norms and value systems, and 3) Cultural-cognitive institutions: shared conceptions of reality, binding expectations, and common beliefs.

The **regulative pillar** of institutions relates to rules, laws, policies, standards, and sanctions that are the key elements and mechanisms of compliance in these institutions (SONNET D1.2:21). Laws, rules, and standards have played a key role in planning application processes for fossil fuel extraction sites. Anti-fossil fuel campaigners have been able to, for example, take legal proceedings in the courts, challenging decisions taken by, for instance, the UK government. Moreover, noise, water quality, etc. standards (often set by the Environment Agency) could be used to object to planning applications, making measurement tools and experts essential in the campaign work. For example, the planning application to frack at Roseacre Wood was not granted on the grounds of traffic impact. As highlighted by Interviewee 1, objections to planning applications have often been successful due to very local, site-specific reasons (and not necessarily based on public opposition). Financial resources, recruiting experts and knowledge of the legal system have been key skills and competences that groups needed to build to change existing regulative institutions. In particular some of the court cases have been key to slowly influencing the planning process. The existing regulative pillar has also been used by the industry to challenge planning decisions taken against extraction activities. In addition, ‘the country has seen a range of new police powers and criminal laws which helped redefine lawful and unlawful dissent, criminalising some forms of collective action while promoting forms of collective action that don’t threaten industrial activity’ (Brock 2020:10). One example of the criminalisation of some anti-fossil fuel activities has also been described in this historical account: the granting of injunctions. ‘At PNR [Preston New Road], for instance, the injunction outlaws direct actions including trespass, slow walking, lock-ons, obstruction of the highway, and lorry surfing’ (Brock 2020:11). Much more research can be found on this topic (e.g. Netpol).

The **normative pillar** of institutions takes the “form of rules-of-thumb” (Hoffman 1999) with regard to values, social norms, duties, and role expectations in a particular field (Scott 2001). Actors adhere to these guidelines, as their actions and beliefs are guided forms of social obligation and professionalisation (SONNET D1.2:21). Within a changing energy system, the fossil fuel industry has had to redefine their expected roles over time. Interviewee 1 explained how parts of the fossil fuel industry had to change their arguments for the need for fossil fuel (and therefore their role),

‘At the beginning, it was going to bring down gas prices. And this was the reason that we should go for it, because they were saying, well, in the United States and, you know, big quantities of shale gas produced completely cut the price of gas and oil... And then, there were issues like energy security. And that's not being used quite so much anymore. The latest defence of the onshore industry is that it would be better from a climate point of view if we produced our gas and oil locally because a carbon footprint would be lower and that we must have oil and gas to help us transition to a low carbon economy’ (Interviewee 1).

It is still to be seen how successful the fossil fuel industry will be in defining their role within a potentially increasingly low carbon energy system. The move away from coal for electricity but instead utilising coal for steel production (i.e. moving sectors) could be one possibility to keep the industry alive in the UK. Some of the anti-fossil fuel movements seem to have been strongly held together by the relatively common goal of stopping the extraction and use of fossil fuels. The clarity of the message, in particular, linked to the divestment movement really supported the movement (Interviewee 5) – organisations should no longer invest in the fossil fuel industry but rather in alternative industry. But what these alternatives might be and what to do next when organisations had divested was not as easy to agree upon (Interviewee 5).

‘And I think divestment, a really good example of that, where, you know, I think the real beauty of divestment was that it was a very clear, reproducible, like campaign aim that spoke to a whole load of people.... that proposition was kind of put forward without a kind of a much wider political analysis’ (Interviewee 5).

This is not to say that there was no political analysis but ideas and norms surrounding change have differed. The diversity can be considered as an important dimension for the participation in more democratic processes but in the case of the divestment movement it might mean the need for more active engagements between the politics of divestment and theories of change.

The **cultural-cognitive** pillar of institutions refers to the socially constructed, shared conceptions of reality, binding expectations and common beliefs with which the world is interpreted or meaning is given, such as symbols, discourses and cultural categories (SONNET D1.2:22). Changing dominant social discourses (in particular the social legitimacy of the fossil fuel industry) and raising issues around who can take part in the discussion about the direction of the energy sector developments have been considered to be one of the main influences of anti-fossil fuel activities. As argued by Bergman (2018:8),

‘One of the most important impacts of divestment has been changing public discourse. Issues of investments in fossil fuels have become more prominent on both political and financial agendas and divestment may have already had significant impact on public discourse around climate mitigation’.

At the same time, an increasingly unfavourable public attitude towards shale gas emerged in the UK. In 2016, a leaked letter from three cabinet ministers to Chancellor George Osborne showed that the UK government was becoming worried about the public's attitudes towards shale gas. The letter outlined strategies to overcome barriers to fracking operations, including attempting to create a more favourable public attitude (Brock 2020). In particular for campaigners such strategies never really quite worked, even creating the opposite effect,

'For many, living near roads and fracking sites, exposure to daily police violence, and personal experience with state forces protecting extractive interest quickly turned former 'liberal' fracking opposition into anti-capitalist and anti-state resistance' (Brock 2020:11). Some of the interviewees talked about similar experiences (e.g. Interviewee 8).

Moreover, fracking operations often occurred in rural areas in the UK where the Conservative Party had some of their core base of voters, as explained by one of the interviewees,

'So when I first started looking at it, David Cameron and George Osborne were very in favour of shale gas. You know, we're going to roll out the shale. There was no great sympathy for concerns by rural Tories about what this might do to their local environment. And the really interesting thing about Balcombe was that many of the people that campaigned against the site told me, you know, I'm a Telegraph-reading Tory. But at that time, they were very angry about the government's support for fracking in particular, but also for any kind of onshore oil and gas development. What I've seen in the work that I've done is that the government's support for fracking has changed. I mean, particularly recently' (Interviewee 1).

For some of the interviewees, it was no surprise that the moratorium on fracking came in just before the general election in the UK, considering that voters could have been lost to the other parties (which started to more clearly take a stance against fracking).

Public attitudes towards shale gas have been collected by the Department of Energy and Climate Change (DECC) and later on by the Department of Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy (BEIS). Interviewee 1 has collected, analysed and visualised this data – as shown below – demonstrating that the public increasingly opposed shale gas.

Phase 5 Times of refocusing... the need to continue around 2015 to now

During this time period, most anti-fossil fuel activities have gone through a refocus of activities and framings. The phase starts in 2015 because most of this refocusing already emerged earlier on than 2019. For example, in 2015, most of the campaign posters that called for an end to fracking started to become irrelevant in parts of the country because some drilling projects no longer required fracking (according to the government’s definition introduced in the Infrastructure Act). In the case of anti-coal, the announcement of coal phase out meant that campaigns started to focus on ending coal now and prepare for anti-coal for steel production campaigns. In addition, the divestment movement had to diversify their targets and message. Wins with the university campaigns meant that new targets needed to be found, e.g. banks and insurances companies. With the new targets, the campaigns also needed to change. Over the next few pages, changes to the different campaigns are outlined in more depth, starting with anti-fracking.

Moratorium on fracking but what about other onshore oil and gas developments

The impact of the Infrastructure Act (2015) on existing onshore oil and gas developments can be exemplified by what

happened after the Act was passed in the Weald area, South East England. In the Act, fracking in the UK got redefined in the new law as “the injection of more than 1,000 cubic litres of fluid at each stage (or expected stage), or the injection of more than 10,000 cubic litres of fluid in total” (Infrastructure Act 2015). In the Weald area (including the Isle of Wight) the new definition of fracking meant that from the moment it was passed, some onshore oil and gas developments no longer fell under fracking regulations. Although the change of the definition already had a huge influence on some of the campaigns in the UK from 2016 onwards, the moratorium on fracking made the impact of the UK government changing the definition even more visible, as outlined over the next few paragraphs.

In March 2019, the UK government’s plan to fast-track planning decisions on fracking was discussed in the House of Commons. A few months later, MPs still waited for a decision on it but nothing happened. Before a decision was made, developments at a fracking site in Lancashire - Preston New Road - brought activities to a hold. In August 2019, Cuadrilla started fracking its second well on site (after abandoning the first well following multiple shutdowns because of tremors). Work on the second well caused the biggest fracking induced earthquake in the UK on the August bank holiday Monday. At the beginning of November 2019, the UK government ordered an immediate moratorium on fracking in England. At the same time, the UK government scrapped the changes to the National Planning Policy Framework. Hayhurst (2019) reported some of the responses,

‘This moratorium is a tremendous victory for communities and the climate. For nearly a decade local people across the country have fought a David and Goliath battle against this powerful industry’ (Friends of the Earth as reported by Hayhurst 2019).

Soon after the moratorium was announced, several organisations pointed out that it did not apply to all forms of oil and gas exploration and extractions.

‘It is also not that difficult to promise such a moratorium if half of your fracking projects don't fall within your definition of fracking right. In a way, it was able to almost take the steam out of some of this campaigning because people thought it is now over, but actually, no’ (Interviewee 2).

All of the poster, information leaflets, etc. that mentioned the word ‘fracking’ had to be sent to areas where onshore oil and gas explorations still fell under the new fracking definition. The new campaign became about acidisation, a process that is explained on the Weald Action Network website,

‘Acidisation is a stimulation technique, used to release oil and gas from unyielding rock such as sandstone and limestone. It involves injecting solutions of acids and other chemicals into the ground, either to clean the well, or to create passageways through the rock along which oil or gas can flow... Acidisation and fracking – short for high-volume hydraulic fracturing – are both stimulation techniques designed to release oil or gas tightly trapped inside the pores of rocks. While fracking is used to

crack open shale, acidising is used to dissolve passageways through limestone or sandstone... Wells have been acidised in the Weald in decades gone by, barely regulated or monitored. What is proposed now is on a different scale. There are many reasons to be concerned about acidisation' (Weald Action Network website).

Acid stimulation, illustration derived from Weald Action Group leaflet (only showing parts of leaflet)⁹

⁹ Professor Styles (2019) (as reported by Hayhurst 2019) explained the importance of understanding how fracking is defined in the UK, 'it is perhaps important before even considering the issue of "fracking" and its different manifestations to understand the difference between conventional hydrocarbon reservoirs and unconventional ones. Simplistically, oil and gas are formed by the effect of pressure and temperature on biological materials deposited within sediments hundreds of millions of years ago. Much of that escapes or migrates (i.e. moves out of the source) and is gone and we never see it again. Some is retained within the rocks where it was formed. And some migrates and is trapped in a different rock formation, which has a cap rock sealing it in and geometry, which prevents it moving further or at least slows it down. This requires rocks to have porosity (spaces where oil and gas can be stored) and permeability, the requirement for pores to be connected so that oil and gas (and water) can flow, albeit slowly. Strangely, it is this third scenario, which we call conventional oil and gas and a great deal of technology, seismic, drilling and other, has developed in order to identify, characterise and exploit this kind of hydrocarbon reservoir all over the world. The second case, where the hydrocarbons stay where they are formed, usually because there is little or no permeability to permit flow, is what we call unconventional oil and gas despite this being probably the largest part by far of the world's hydrocarbon reserves. If we can increase the permeability by some method, we can get this oil and gas out and how we do that depends on the nature of the rock. If, as is common, the rocks are shales, fine grained sediments, then this is usually done by hydraulic stimulation or fracking. This is done by injecting high-pressure water with a limited number of chemicals so that new fractures and pathways form and these are kept open by injecting a proppant, either sand or a synthetic material... If the rock is strongly cemented, so that the pores are blocked by calcite (calcium carbonate) or silica, or is itself a limestone, then the permeability can be increased somewhat by dissolving these cements or matrices with acids (hydrochloric for calcite, or hydrofluoric for silica). This is

As argued by Brock (2020:1) 'the term 'fracking' is politically contested and defined differently across political contexts'. The definition of fracking and its interpretation has particularly been relevant for the South East of England (Weald area and Isle of Wight) and Lincolnshire (see box Don't Drill the Wight for more detail on how the fracking definition and moratorium had an influence on developments on the Isle of Wight). Campaigns had already changed from anti-fracking to anti-acidisation in some areas of England from 2015. Still, the moratorium highlighted once more that most of the onshore oil and gas explorations and extractions were not included in it, leaving on-going oil and gas activities as potentially being 'fracking under the radar'.

Frack Free Isle of Wight renamed to Don't Drill The Wight

Frack Free Isle of Wight (South England) was created when some of the islanders heard about possible onshore oil and gas developments when the 14th round of licences were issued in 2014. At the time, they did not know whether the licence was for oil and/ or gas and whether fracking was needed to extract it. In 2016, UKOG (oil and gas company) purchased the licences. This is when the group realised that they wanted to extract oil. Nothing happened over the next four years and some people started to lose interest in the topic.

In December 2019, UKOG announced that it would hold a public meeting (in the format of a drop in session) and submit a planning application. A few months later, notices went up on the field, the group only noticed because its members saw it happening. There also was a note in the local newspaper and soon after, the council published the planning application on its website. There was some back and forward about when the consultation should start to happen because of the national lockdown. In June 2020, the council announced that the consultation had started. The group decided that 'despite the lockdown, we were going to go into action' (Interviewee 3). Interviewee 3 explained how they needed to re-frame their campaign because the company was arguing that it would not frack,

'So, we decided that we would start a new campaign, which would say 'don't drill the Wight' to move it away from the concept of fracking. Even though we seriously do believe that if this all goes ahead, they would probably want to apply to do acid fracking in the future. For the moment, we're focusing on that we just don't want drilling here whatever the format' (Interviewee 3).

known as acidising or acid stimulation. It is also possible to combine these two stimulation techniques by injecting the acidic solution at a high enough pressure to fracture the rock as well. This is known as acid fracking... the jury is out as to whether acid fracking, (the more aggressive combined acid and hydraulic stimulation process) is also actually banned under the recently-announced moratorium, as it generally uses lower volumes than the 1,000/10,000 limits.'

The website needed to be changed, banners, postcards, leaflets and videos were made, a socially distant meeting was conducted, and the social media work was set in place (including articles in the local newspaper). The group is currently busy analysing the objections, keeping in touch with the planning officer and preparing their statement for the planning commission. 'We're just holding our breath now. We just want it to be over' (Interviewee 3). Please see Annex for the full historical narrative.

'Don't Drill The Wight' campaign, photo from Weald Action Group website

In January 2020, the energy minister confirmed that oil and gas explorations and extractions outside the 2015 fracking definition were not included in the moratorium, leading to campaigners calling out for an extension to the moratorium. Although in June 2019, the UK government passed a new zero emissions law that requires the UK to bring all greenhouse gas emissions to net zero by 2050, the call for an extension of the definition was dismissed in May 2020. In the meantime, two oil and gas companies announced they would temporarily shut down their sites because of falling oil and gas prices. Other companies removed some of their drilling equipment when the moratorium came into effect.

Legal actions against the fossil fuel industry did not decrease during this time. For example, Sarah Finch (supported by the Weald Action Group and represented by Leigh Day) won the right to challenge a decision by Surrey County Council to grant planning permission for the 20 years of oil production at Hose Hill, South England. The case is significant for the whole of the UK because the hearing (that will take place in November 2020 at the Court of Appeal¹⁰) will determine how existing national planning rules fit with the UK's net zero targets¹¹. Sarah Finch's request for a judicial review was turned down twice but an appeal court ruled that the case could get a public hearing.

¹⁰ In Dec 2020, this has taken place – ruling reserved with no specific date but expected to be before Christmas.

¹¹ Another previous court case was relevant for the consideration of climate change issues in planning applications. In March 2019, the High Court ruled on the challenge to the National Planning Policy (NPPF) Framework made by Talk Fracking. The case was won and focused on a specific policy in the NPPF: its approach to planning for shale gas and oil extraction by mineral planning authorities. Winning this case meant that future planning applications for onshore oil and gas have been able to be objected to current scientific evidence, especially surrounding climate change, and not constricted as before by government policy insisting 'great weight' should be placed on oil and gas extraction (Stephenson as reported by Hayhurst 2019).

‘Our client maintains that Surrey Council has failed in its obligations to assess the indirect greenhouse gas impact of the use of oil produced from this development, as well as to properly consider the environmental objectives of the government’s Net Zero target before granting planning consent’ (Leigh Day 2020 on Weald Action Group website).

The Weald Action Group also published a report on ‘Why we don’t need more onshore oil in the UK’, showing how campaigns against fracking might have temporarily stopped but campaigns against acidisation and other forms of oil and gas explorations and extractions continue in the UK.

Coal for electricity is phasing out but how and what about coal for steel production

Whereas with anti-fracking the refocus of some of the campaigns was based on the UK government’s decision to come up with a rather narrow definition of fracking, for anti-coal the refocus was grounded in having successfully objected to several opencast coalmine planning applications, leaving more resources to broadening campaigns. In 2020, only four opencast coalmines have been operating in the UK: none in Scotland, one in England and three in Wales.

‘And we made a point now where there is only one application left in the system for an opencast coalmine. There are only a handful of coalmines operating in the UK’ (Interviewee 11).

The majority of coal-fired power stations have dates when they will be closed (or are being converted to gas). For example, Drax power station will stop burning coal by 2021 and Aberthaw power station closed on the 31st March 2020. This all happened in a context where the UK recorded two weeks of coal free electricity generation in 2019 (Guardian 2019) and the electricity grid was supplied with 5.5 Terawatt hours of coal (amounting to 2.1% of electricity produced) in 2018.

These developments have allowed for several other issues to be picked up by anti-coal campaigners over the past years: stronger calls for a ‘Just Transition’, supporting communities in countries from which coal has been imported, and engaging in a more recent shift from coal for electricity to coal for steel production. In particular the trades union movement has campaigned for a ‘just transition’ which would tackle environmental problems, provide representation and employee involvement and include stable employment and long-term planning. A just transition would aim firstly to take appropriate measures to protect jobs in vulnerable industries. Ideas of a ‘just transition’ have increasingly been discussed for example by the European Trade Union Confederation (ETUC) where this notion entails paying “greater attention to the adverse consequences of decarbonisation and address them through concrete and effective policies specifically targeting workers from sectors and regions which could be negatively impacted by the transition to a low-carbon economy” (ETUC 2016:46), while “ensuring a broad participation of local social partners is essential to the success of low-carbon industrial strategies at local level” (ETUC 2016:5). With the absence of attention towards community impact in the UK coal phase out thus far, it is not clear that the policy discussions around coal phase out in the UK were paying enough attention to the broader sets of

concerns that workers and communities in regions such as Yorkshire were considering when the phase out was discussed.

Although the collaborations were not new, anti-coal campaigners increasingly have been able to not only forge connections with local communities impacted by coal in the UK but also create solidarities with communities further afield from which coal was imported into the UK (for example Russia and Columbia) – based on increasing issues linked to climate justice. Already in 2014, the Coal Action Network made a visit to Colombia to talk to some of the communities impacted by coal mining. Supported by the London Mining Network, exchanges were taking place, with for instance, Colombian community leaders and union leaders visiting the communities affected by coalmining in the North East of the UK in October 2018 (Coal Action Network website). Crowdfunding activities have been organised to support each other's efforts. Moreover, increasingly networks and connections have been forged,

'There's also now a relatively new network, that I am part of... It is called Still Burning Network Against Coal and Colonialism that is bringing together people across European countries that import coal and the countries where the coal is actually mined and that's mainly Russia and Columbia and the US, a couple of other countries' (Interviewee 2).

It is a European network that opposes 'imports of coal to Europe through direct action and education, with a focus on neocolonialism in European coal and consumption' (Still Burning website). Other networks have also been created, demonstrating that efforts have gone across borders, for example, the Europe Beyond Coal campaign has been established to ensure coal is being phased out throughout Europe by 2030 at the latest (Coal Action Network website).

'The End Coal Europe coalition that is a group of organisations, people from the different NGOs and grassroots groups across Europe, who work on coal, and that's where we strategise about coal and there is quite a focus on coal for steel production' (Interviewee 11).

Talks about coal for steel production have been the third refocusing of anti-coal over the last year. The need to learn about coal for steel became increasingly apparent in the UK when Cumbria County Council unanimously approved the application by West Cumbria Mining to extract coking coal from the seabed off St Bees in March 2019. A significant proportion of this coal is expected to be used for steel making (which is not included in the UK coal phase out). Cumbria County Council is considering the application again following new evidence submitted by the applicants, likely in response to a legal challenge launched by campaigners Keep Cumbrian Coal in the Hole. More than 1,000 people objected and important new evidence has been submitted against the proposal.

'All of the campaign groups are turning their attention to steel, including us, learning as they go about steel making processes and the links to coal... it is not something that people have paid attention to. It requires a different level of technical knowledge from coal for power stations and, you know, understanding what the markets are like. And it's a whole other industry basically, and where everybody feels quite stretched by it because they are trying to actually campaign, so put things

out in the world, and intervene in the processes and decisions, but also learning and formulating decisions and it's very difficult to do both. It needs a stronger knowledge base' (Interviewee 11).

Interviewee 11 continued to explain that the campaign around coal for steel needs to be framed quite differently to coal for electricity – 'the focus needs to become on jobs'. People have existing jobs in the steel industry and new jobs would be created through underground coal mining. In the case of the proposed coalmine in Cumbria, Interviewee 11 argued that local people had already been sold on the prospect of jobs for the local area; no 'alternative local visions' were created. This would need to change in the future.

'The mining company has got the money and people power to present a fully finished project that can just be ready to go whereas communities generally cannot do that without a lot of financial backing. And so, there was nobody offering anything else to this area where there were no jobs' (Interviewee 11).

Coal for steel developments need to be fought on a national level (and international), asking the Secretary of State to call in planning applications and based on the UK net-zero target and Paris agreement reject them, but at the same time, local people need to be taken along by formulating an alternative vision to coal for the local area.

'We've got to change our coal for steel campaigning... around jobs, around transitions... and clean energy in a way that brings people with it like with on that journey rather than they feel left behind or make people feel in conflict with that' (Interviewee 11).

The future of coal for electricity seems to be over in the UK but the future for coal for steel production might just be on the rise. Still, imports of coal to the UK continue: The UK consumed 7.9 million tonnes of coal in 2019, including 3.0 million tonnes in the steel industry, 2.9 million tonnes in power stations and 1.5 million tonnes in other industries. Coal imports to the UK were 6.8 million tonnes.

Going beyond universities – Divestment movement winding down and/ or establishing different targets?

In 2020, over half of UK universities have made a commitment to divest from fossil fuel in some way. Of the 78 divested institutions, a majority of their commitments cover all fossil fuels and completed the process of moving their money out of the industry entirely. See full list of universities and colleges that have committed to pursuing fossil fuel divestment and date of announcement here: <https://peopleandplanet.org/fossil-free-victories>.

Having studied the impacts of the divestment movement, Bergman (2018) has argued that direct impacts of divestment have been rather small. But one might be able to argue that financially bankrupting the industry was never the focus of the movement. Bergman (2018:1) has gone on to argue that 'the indirect impacts, in terms of public discourse shift, are

significant'. The divestment movement has raised the climate change agenda in the UK and with it 'played a part in changing the discourse around the legitimacy, reputation and viability of the fossil fuel industry... to changes in the finance industry through new demands by shareholders and investors and to changes in political discourse'. Several interviewees also mentioned the significant impacts on students who have taken part in the movement. For lots of them, it was a springboard into climate justice campaigning and direct action (Interview 5,9). 'Divestment had significant impact on its participants in terms of empowerment' (Bergman 2018:1).

One of the interviewees explained how this was also a time where the movement started to 'wind down' (Interviewee 5). Universities were no longer 'putting up a fight'. They also realised that 'it's not going to be a massive drain on them' (Interviewee 5). For instance, in May 2020, the University of Manchester committed to a full divestment. It was one of the longest running divestment campaigns. If they had made the decision a few years earlier, this would have been 'amazing' but in 2020, it did not gain much attention. Moreover, the 'campaigning energy' was disappearing due to fatigue (having been involved in the movement for several years) and people moving on to other climate justice activities. Interviewee 5 continued to explain how the divestment movement was really successful in unifying the climate change movement around their particular 'clear' campaign. But this 'unity was temporary'. For quite a few people in the movement, the divestment campaign was always meant to be a starting point for larger changes. The campaign was meant to call into question the social legitimacy of the fossil fuel industry to then create a favourable political climate for 'more radical political interpretations of climate justice' (Interviewee 5). For Interviewee 5, this would have entailed partly 'resolving' people's political differences (e.g. how change comes about and should be governed) and 'cohere around a deeper politics'. The Interviewee felt that the movement did not really use the time to engage with these issues. Part of the reason why this could occur was that the divestment movement (different to anti-fracking and anti-coal) could frame and plan their campaign outside the existing regulatory and policy context.

Another change in the movement occurred around 2015, when the targets of the campaigns were diversified, including the divestment of pensions and other fund-holders (e.g. including council and parliamentary pension funds) and banks and insurance companies. Three UK banks in particular, HSBC, Barclays, and RBS, are among the banks, which have invested in and/ or loaned money, for instance, for the building of oil and tar sand pipelines.

'I think there is definitely scope to be expanding into, which is what People & Planet have done, into the financing of fossil fuel projects. They've moved on to talking about Divest Barclay, about getting that money moved out of financing of specific fossil fuel projects opposed to BP and Shell as a company in themselves' (Interviewee 9).

In May 2018, People & Planet, for instance, disrupted Barclays' Annual General Meeting. The first action of its kind in a while, they could express demands directly to Barclays' directors by attending the AGM. In 2019, the activists of the campaign led by People and Planet joined up with the grassroots Labour group and Momentum organised peaceful protest at 40 Barclays branches in the UK.

'A key early backer of fracking in the UK, Barclays continues to finance coal companies, tar sands companies, and fossil fuel projects across the globe. They even underwrote a public offering for the company responsible for the Trans Mountain tar sands pipeline' (People and Planet website).

These protests spread to Germany, the US and Canada a few months later. For the Momentum group these activities were all part of a larger agenda to back the call for the UK parliament to declare a climate emergency and gain support for Labour's Green New Deal. During the protest the campaigners aims were to creatively disrupt the running of Barclays branches, e.g. turning them into pop-up discos and children's play areas. Other activities included building coalitions, brandalism, making use of social media, education work, lobbying and negotiating with the media. Extinction Rebellion, Green Party, Rising UPI, Friends of the Earth, etc. supported some of the activities.

Although People and Planet also created an action guide (People and Planet 2019) for the divest Barclays campaign, the campaign was not easily transferred from the universities to banks. One of the interviewees argued that 'your campaigning at the university is in some ways it's really very easy' (Interviewee 5). Universities might be a transient place where students come and go but they create a 'defined base' for several years for a local movement to grow. Moreover, universities have potentially been easier targets. Universities have a greater accountability to their student group than banks to their customers. How best to create a similar 'base' is still something that people and organisations that are part of the movement try to determine (Interviewee 5) – also how framings and actions need to change.

Institutional work conducted by SIE-field actors and other field-actors

Institutional work refers to the activities of actors that aim to create, maintain and disrupt institutions. Examples: 1) Attempts to influence policy makers and the general public through direct lobbying, research reports, positioning papers, advertising, and the setting of technical standards and 2) Attempts to influence informal institutions, such as values, norms, binding expectations, common beliefs, habits, and routines, among the wider public (Arenas 2017).

Diverse actors conduct institutional work, e.g., policymakers, campaigners, NGOs, energy industry. In SONNET, we examine why, how, when and where actors (in particular actors, who are engaged in collective activities to develop social innovation in energy) work at creating, maintaining and disrupting institutions, drawing particular attention to the practices rather than purely accomplishments of institutional work. This can include different practices of institutional work: issue bracketing, road mapping, etc. In addition to institutional work, actors can also get engaged in discursive work, meaning work, boundary work, interaction work, just to mention a few (for a full list see Phillips and Lawrence 2012).

Hopefully, the historical account has given a good overview of the diverse framings (i.e. actions and discourses) created by anti-fossil fuel campaigners. These have involved learning process, awareness raising activities, engaging with

policymakers, lobbying and legal work, mobilising work, just to mention a few. Most of the interviewees talked about diversity of activities that they had to engage in and how these had transformed their lives, for example, having to regularly communicate to an often hostile press. It is not easy to single out different actions taken and demonstrate how they can be considered to be 'institutional work' i.e. creating and disrupting institutions. Some of the work that has happened in courtrooms could be singled out, as it seemed to start to pave the way for climate change issues to be considered in planning applications (although the outcomes are still uncertain). Currently, most of the objections to planning applications are still won based on local issues (i.e. noise, etc.) and technicalities. Although this legal work seems to be key when thinking about institutional work, singling out one activity over another might detract from the overall picture, where a multiplicity and diversity of actions and discourses have allowed for existing institutions to be disrupted by campaigners. In a way, it might be possible to argue that the fossil fuel industry had to lobby for the creation of institutions to 'control' the anti-fossil fuel activities (i.e. fast-tracking the planning process). Institutional work was therefore conducted on both sides. It might therefore be less of a question of who creates, maintains and disrupts institutions in the SIE-field but rather which institutions are considered to be in need of disrupting and maintaining (or the need to create new ones).

To put it simply, campaigners have been active in maintaining and creating institutions that support climate targets set by the UK government (and even press for more stringent targets) and disrupting institutions that can be argued to move away from these targets and/ or sustain 'business as usual' in the energy sector. The work involved included changing regulative, normative and cultural institutions, from example, fighting existing regulation in courts and changing the public discourse. The work of anti-fracking and anti-coal show more similarities but it might be possible to suggest that the combined anti-fossil framings have helped to shape the public discourse on anti-fossil fuel.

Short summary

In 2020, it seems that campaigners engaged in anti-fossil fuel are to some extent at the crossroads. Although there have been several achievements: moratorium on fracking, coal phase out, net-zero carbon target, etc., the historical account has shown that the work for campaigners is far from over. Campaigns needed to be refocused rather than stopped. The decision-making process, type of energy mix, technology deployed, etc. that will bring the UK to its net zero target by 2050 are already in discussion but there are still several questions left unanswered and it is to be seen whether the targets will be met.

Key changes in the SIE-field over time

Changes to SIE-fields i.e. framing against fossil fuel energy pathways have been explained based on manifold developments and can be grounded in field events and contestations, inter-field interactions, external shocks and societal trends. I would like to use this box to summarise some of the key changes in framings linked to anti-fracking, anti-coal and divestment over time.

Framings surrounding 'shale gas', 'fracking', etc. in the UK have been well studied by the academic community (e.g. Bomberg 2015; Cotton et al. 2014; Nyberg et al. 2018). One of the most recent studies has been conducted by Williams and Sovacool (2019). They identified nine key frames between 2010-2018. The five anti-shale ones consist of 1) industrialisation of the countryside; 2) bad governance (i.e. fractured democracy); 3) dirty fossil fuel; 4) elusive threats (i.e. bad regulation); and 5) no repeat revolution. They have found that from 2011 onwards most of the frames started to be used. The 'bad governance frame' was dominant between 2014 and 2015. This is when the Infrastructure Bill was debated and the Act was received Royal Assent, leading up to the 'Let Communities Decide Campaign'. For some of the local groups, framings also moved from mainly outlining local issues to increasingly including topics concerned with climate change, as explained by one of the interviewees,

'They've [campaigns] become more climate aware, as opposed to being anti-fracking at a local level. So, the focus has changed because as people become more aware of what fracking entails, then you see how it fits into the bigger picture. You talked about energy solutions and you know, people wanting green energy solutions and different ways. That's how the campaigns are sort of changed, I would say' (Interviewee 7).

The historical account has also shown how campaigns had to change after the UK governments new definition of fracking came into effect. In some places in the UK, anti-fracking became anti-acidisation and/ or anti onshore oil and gas. It shows how the term 'fracking' has been highly politically contested. On the ground, this has meant new learning, re-framing of campaigns (maybe with less clear messages) and making up new posters (whilst old ones with the word fracking were no longer any use). To sum up, campaigners had to be pretty inventive, flexible and resilient over time, considering efforts by the fossil fuel industry and UK government trying to control the discourse and resistance against onshore oil and gas in the UK.

In comparison to anti-fracking, campaigners mainly involved in anti-coal for power could develop their campaign in a slightly more favourable policy context from 2015 onwards. The announcement of the coal phase out meant that campaigns needed to be reframed to say that coal needed to be stopped earlier than 2025. A lot of local opencast coalmining planning application had to be still fought on a one-by-one basis and based on local issues. Nevertheless, the context in which planning applications have been decided has changed, considering, for example, the declaration of 'climate emergencies' by several councils. Although the planning framework has not changed, changes to the local social and political environment meant that framings against anti-coal could involve clearer climate change messages. However, considering the long history of coal extraction in the UK and its interlinkages to local economies (i.e. job market) and socio-cultural dimensions of people's daily life, framings against fossil fuel have always had to be sensitive to broader social issues. This is why in some parts of the UK, calls for a 'Just Transition' have been part of anti-coal framings. Moreover, coal for power clearly is in decline in the UK, coal for steel production and imported coal might even become a stronger focal point of anti-coal campaigners.

In comparison to anti-fracking and anti-coal, framings produced by the divestment movement could partly develop more 'freely' from regulatory and policy changes (Interviewee 5). A few organisations could see how fruitful this clear message of divesting from fossil fuel companies had been in the US and how well it worked within a university context i.e. students asking universities to divest. Although the clear message persisted over time, framings and their aims have been debated within the movement. Is the aim to bankrupt the industry? Or is it more about ruining their social legitimacy? Is it possible to work with the industry to make it low carbon or is this a movement against the all types of activities derived from the industry? One of the interviewees argued that although the campaign was so successful and was able to unite the environmental movement for a while, it did not use the time to conduct a political analysis of what was going on and what should be achieved in the future (Interviewee 5). Over the past five years, new targets (e.g. banks and insurance companies) have been found where campaigns had to be adapted to see which messages and activities can work and how to create a core base of campaigners.

6 Summary, synthesis and conclusions

6.1 How do SIEs and SIE-fields emerge, develop and institutionalise over time?

In SONNET, we are interested in studying diverse social innovation in energy (SIE). We define SIE as ‘a combination of ideas, objects and/ or actions that change social relations and involve new ways of doing, thinking and/ or organising energy’. As part of this work, we have identified seven different types of SIE, including one called ‘framings against specific energy pathways’. Here, social interactions (and changes to social relations) that aim to bring about changes in the energy system are often based on ‘conflicts’ (rather than cooperation, exchange and competition) and make use of novel ways of ideas and thinking about energy issues (whilst making use of objects and actions) to stop particular energy pathways. The SIE therefore is based on different framings (but also includes protesting and lobbying work) derived from different groups and organisations that aim to stop the extraction of fossil fuels. This includes framings derived from anti-coal, anti-onshore oil and gas (fracking) movements and the divestment movement. We are particularly interested in the content, construction and performativity of these framings and their emergence and development over time.

The SIE-field is an arena that includes a specific SIE (e.g. framings against fossil fuel energy pathways) as well as SIE-field-actors (e.g. Coal Action Network, Friends of the Earth and Fossil Free Sussex) working on it and other field-actors enabling and/or impeding it (e.g. UK government, local authorities, Secretary of State, and fossil fuel industry). In this space these actors take one another and their actions into account and have a shared (but not necessarily consensual) understanding of a SIE and of their relationship to other actors. They recognise (but do not necessarily follow) shared norms, beliefs and rules. SIE-fields are often not homogenous but are composed of actors with diverse and contradictory aims and interests. Within this SIE-field, relations between SIE-field-actors have been partly built on some longstanding organisations - environmental organisations (e.g. Greenpeace and Friends of the Earth) and existing national grassroots direct action groups (e.g. Frack Off and Reclaim the Power) – who have organised and supported national, regional and local anti-fossil fuel campaigns over the last decades. They therefore hold some of the anti-fracking, anti-coal and divestment activities together, in particular, by supporting local groups to set up their own campaigns, providing information about anti-fossil fuel, taking on court cases against certain policy decisions and organising direct action (i.e. not all organisations get involved in similar ways).

Moreover, a campaigner that might formally work for divestment organisations can also informally get involved in organising anti-fracking events (Interviewee 5). Most of the interviewees had affiliations to several groups and organisations. Because of this, ways to organise, mobilise, lobby, take direct action, etc. are transferred between people, organisations, and locations (even across borders). Although there are some clear differences between the framings (anti-fracking, anti-coal and divestment), the SIE-field is held together by some of the people who get involved in several anti-fossil fuel activities. Interactions between anti-fracking, anti-coal and divestment activities have also frequently occurred on an ‘ad hoc’ (Interviewee 11) basis. For instance, in 2017, an energy symposium was carried out at an anti-fracking camp, inviting anti-

coal and divestment campaigners. Sometimes, there have also been exchanges between anti-fracking and anti-coal camps. ‘And in fact, while we were during the camp at Bradley [anti-coal camp] there was the camp at Preston New Road [anti-fracking camp] at the same time. It was a lot more established and well known so groups of people came down for the weekend to have a bit of a holiday from Preston New Road and came to a different camp’ (Interviewee 11). More frequently, upcoming news is shared in between people (and organisations) across their social media accounts to increase the visibility of each other’s activities.

Campaigners involved in ‘framings against energy pathways centred on fossil fuels’ have had to be inventive, resilient and persistent over the past years because of powerful state and energy companies’ efforts ‘to facilitate the suppression of protest’ and other activities (see Brock 2020:1). For example, existing laws and regulations have also been used by the fossil fuel industry to challenge planning decisions taken against extraction activities. In addition, ‘the country has seen a range of new police powers and criminal laws which helped redefine lawful and unlawful dissent, criminalising some forms of collective action while promoting forms of collective action that don’t threaten industrial activity’ (Brock 2020:10). One example of the criminalisation of some anti-fossil fuel activities has also been described in this historical account: the granting of injunctions. ‘At PNR [Preston New Road], for instance, the injunction outlaws direct actions including trespass, slow walking, lock-ons, obstruction of the highway, and lorry surfing’ (Brock 2020:11).

Below is a short summary of the historical account of anti-fracking, anti-coal and anti-investment into fossil fuel, summarising developments over time:

During World War I and World War II, legislations were introduced to enable oil and gas companies to further explore onshore oil and gas (hydrocarbons) due to the UKs need to produce its own oil to help war efforts. Onshore oil and gas activities started to accelerate again after the 1979 oil crises, as domestic production became more important for the UK government. Over the last decade, the extraction of onshore oil and gas — particularly through hydraulic fracturing — has been contentious and controversial, not least in the UK. UK proponents emphasise the potential economic, security and environmental benefits of onshore oil and gas, while opponents stress the incumbent environmental, health and climate risks associated with these extractions and operations. Opponents can be local groups (e.g. Preston New Road Action Group and Frack Free Isle of Wight), regional network organisations (e.g. Weald Action Group and Frack Free Lancashire) and national organisations (e.g. Reclaim the Power, Friends of the Earth UK and Green Party). The UK government has promoted the extraction of onshore oil and gas over the past years. A licence is required by the Oil and Gas Authority, which grants rights to explore and extract onshore oil and gas. The rights granted do not include any rights of access, and the licensees must also obtain any consent under current legislation, including planning permissions. Despite promising geological estimates and strong support from the highest levels of UK government, public support for shale gas has declined over the recent years (see Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy (BEIS) Public Attitude Tracker). Growing opposition and protest have marked development since 2013 (e.g. Cotton et al. 2014). In November 2019, the UK government halted fracking in England with immediate effect. The decision was taken after a scientific study warned it was not possible to rule

out “unacceptable” consequences for people living near fracking sites. The report, undertaken by the Oil and Gas Authority (OGA), also warned it was not possible to predict the magnitude of earthquakes fracking might trigger. The UK government said it would not agree to any future fracking “until compelling new evidence is provided” (...) that proves fracking could be safe. This moratorium has not stopped all onshore oil and gas activities in the UK.

The decline of the coal industry started due to increasing social, political and economic pressures in the late 1950s in the UK (Turnheim and Geels 2013). It was signified by pit closures and triggered the 1984-85 miners strikes. Some of the areas are still economically marked by the decline today. Coal has been entwined with places where communities spanning generations have been formed and held together through coal (Kirby 2015). Following the privatisation of the coal industry in 1994, the ownership of all coal resides with the Coal Authority which grants licences for coal exploration and extraction. In 1999, the Coalfields Regeneration Trust was created as a charity organisation in order to support the local population and subsidise projects for coalfields communities. In 2016, the Camp for Climate Action was set up as a week-long protest based just miles from the coal-fired power station Drax, in Yorkshire. More recently, specific policy announcements have been made to phase out coal by 2025 (DECC 2015). Calls for a ‘Just Transition’ have emerged to learn from 1950s. This notion is particularly strong in Scotland where the local government has set up a ‘Just Transition Commission’. Considering the UK’s dropping reliance on coal for electricity from 70% in 1990 to less than 3% today (BEIS 2020), the prime minister announced in February 2020 the decision to bring forward the phase out of coal to October 2024. The last deep coal mine, North Yorkshire’s Kellingley Colliery, closed on the 18th of December 2015. However, open cast mining has continued in some parts of the UK and plans for expansion have proven contentious, including several campaigns, local groups (e.g. United Valleys Action Group and Keep Cumbrian Coal in the Hole) and actions opposing coal developments in the UK (Greenpeace 2013). Some of the local groups are held together by a grassroots network organisation the ‘Coal Action Network’. Some of the other organisations are Greenpeace UK, Friends of the Earth UK and Reclaim the Power (i.e. a direct action network). Another example of a local group is the ‘Protect Pont Valley’ group (located in County Durham, North England) which has been fighting planning application for the coal site for the past 30 years. The most recent planning application was rejected in 2011 but the coal company appealed in 2011 and 2013. Bank’s Group gained planning permission and developed the Bradley mine. They stopped extracting coal in 2020. Although the extraction of coal went ahead, a more recent attempt for an extension of the opencast coalmine could be prevented by the campaign.

The divestment movement started in the summer of 2011 in the United States (US). Fossil fuel divestment campaigns emerged on six campuses with students urging the university administrations to turn endowment investments in the fossil fuel industry into investments in clean energy. By spring 2012, 50 US universities had divestment movements and continued to grow globally. The grassroots climate campaign 350.org that was co-founded by Bill McKibben launched its divestment campaign, supporting and joining forces with students organising the divestment movement. Their ‘Go Fossil Free: Divest from Fossil Fuel!’ campaign aimed to ‘revoke the social licence of the fossil fuel industry’ (350.org). Between 2012-2018, the movement grew considerably and there were fossil fuel divestment campaigns in hundreds of universities worldwide, including dozens in the UK, as well as local authorities and other institutions. The divestment movement has been

coordinated mainly by two organisations in the UK: 1) People & Planet, who coordinate the student movement and work closely with the National Union of Students and 2) 350.org, who work with local councils and pension funds. Many of the groups involved are student organisations, although religious organisations, local and regional governments and other public bodies have also divested, or have been targeted by divestment campaigners. Over the past few years, the student divestment movement has become smaller, after seventy-eight of the UK's 154 public universities signed up to divest from fossil fuel in 2020 (see Bergman's (2018) study on the divestment movement in the UK).

6.2 How do SIE-field-actors and other field-actors interact with the 'outside' institutional environment and thereby co-shape the SIE-field over time?

The SIE-field (and its actors) – framings against fossil fuel energy pathways - are nested within an 'outside' institutional environment linked to an energy system that is constituted by formal and informal institutions that shape the activities of actors within the SIE-field. Although energy systems consist of a wide range of institutionalised rules, norms, and beliefs, these institutions have been subject to profound changes over the past decade. These changes are due to manifold developments and can be grounded in events and contestations, inter-field interactions, external shocks and societal trends. In the SONNET team, we are interested in the 'outside' institutional environment that 'surrounds' and 'penetrates' the SIE-field. We want to understand how dominant institutions (regulative, normative and cultural-cognitive elements) within the 'outside' institutional environment influence the emergence and development of framings against fossil fuel energy pathways.

Much could be said about 'outside' institutional environment surrounding and penetrating framings against fossil fuel energy pathways. Here, the state and industry (and their interlinkages) play a prominent role, including efforts to deal with an increasing public opposition (e.g. policing protestors and controlling discourses and knowledge (see Brock 2020)), buy consent (e.g. corporate sponsorship and tax hand-outs (see Brock 2020)), ignore some of the issues of local residents in areas affected by fossil fuel (in particular the coal regions in North of England), lack of legislated strategies to achieve climate targets, and decrease regulatory and legislative barriers for the industry (e.g. announcement of the coal phase out (without legislation), changing the definition of fracking, and fast-track planning processes).

Changing dominant social discourses (in particular the social legitimacy of the fossil fuel industry) and raising issues around who can take part in the discussion about the direction of the energy sector developments have been considered to be one of the main influences of anti-fossil fuel activities. One of the most important impacts of divestment has been changing public discourse. Issues of investments in fossil fuels have become more prominent on both political and financial agendas and divestment may have already had significant impact on public discourse around climate mitigation (Bergman 2018). At the same time, an increasing unfavourable public attitude towards shale gas emerged in the UK. In 2016, a leaked letter from three cabinet ministers to Chancellor George Osborne showed that the UK government was becoming worried about the public's attitudes towards shale gas. The letter outlined strategies to overcome barriers to fracking operations, including

attempting to create a more favourable public attitude (Brock 2020). In 2019, following a 22-months Freedom of Information campaign, the government released a confidential report demonstrating that '[p]ublic opposition [is the] root cause of slow progress of UK fracking' (Brock 2020).

6.3 What are the enabling and impeding factors for SIE-field-actors and other field-actors to conduct institutional work and change the 'outside' institutional environment?

Hopefully, the historical account has given a good overview of the diverse framings (i.e. actions and discourses) created by anti-fossil fuel campaigners. These have involved learning process, awareness raising activities, engaging with policymakers, lobbying and legal work, mobilising work, just to mention a few. Most of the interviewees talked about diversity of activities that they had to engage in and how these had transformed their lives, for example, having to regularly respond to an often hostile press. It is not easy to single out different actions taken and demonstrate how they can be considered to be 'institutional work' i.e. creating and disrupting institutions. Some of the work that has happened in courtrooms could be singled out, as it seemed to start to pave the way for climate change issues to be considered in planning applications (although the outcomes still are uncertain). Still, most of the objections to planning applications are still won based on local issues (i.e. noise, etc.) and technicalities. Although this legal work seems to be key when thinking about institutional work, singling out one activity over another might deter from the overall picture, where a multiplicity and diversity of actions and discourses have allowed for existing institutions to be disrupted by campaigners.

The historical account has shown that institutional work was not only conducted by campaigners but also by the fossil fuel industry, lobbying for the creation and maintenance of institutions to 'control' the anti-fossil fuel activities and creating more favourable conditions for their operations (i.e. fast-tracking the planning process). Institutional work was therefore conducted on both sides. It might therefore be less of a question of who creates, maintains and disrupts institutions in the SIE-field but rather which institutions are considered to be in need of disrupting and maintaining (or the need to create new ones) and who conducts the institutional work in what kind of way.

To put it maybe a bit too simply, campaigners have been active in maintaining and creating institutions that support climate targets set by the UK government (and even press for more stringent targets) and disrupting institutions that can be argued to move away from these targets and/ or sustain 'business as usual' in the energy sector. The work involved included changing regulative, normative and cultural institutions, for example, fighting existing regulation in courts and changing the public discourse. The work of anti-fracking and anti-coal activities shows some similarities in this regard. Overall, anti-fossil fuel campaigners seem to have played a key role in shaping the public discourse on the legitimacy of the fossil fuel industry and need to develop policies and frameworks that support the achievement of set/ announced climate change targets. Nonetheless, energy planning policies seem to still favour, for instance, major fossil fuel power plants, open cast mines or fracking, although the UK government has made promises to tackle carbon emissions, including in the Paris agreement and in its own net zero legislation. Existing energy planning policies were put in place by government officials almost a decade

ago to help avert the risk of blackouts and are still being used to justify fossil fuel projects. It might be possible to argue that climate targets need to be more closely aligned with energy planning policies. Campaigners have been busy creating new institutions to allow for these changes to occur but it has been a long journey and the outcomes are still uncertain.

7 Recommendations for our city partners, national and EU policy makers and SIE practitioners

SONNET city partners

- It is important to recognise that a lot of campaigners give up their spare time (and even reduce their work hours) to organise and get involved in anti-fossil fuel activities. This entails an endless amount of emotional work, in addition to, gathering knowledge and skills about how to stop the industry. Most people do not only get involved for a few months but years and years. This can take a real toll on people's lives.
- The historical account demonstrates the large amount and diverse knowledge, skills, capacity to mobilise, etc. that exists within different communities and groups. It also shows a readiness and willingness to engage with complex energy issues. Local authorities should therefore support citizen-led initiatives that already exist and help their visibility and recognition.
- Planning applications need to be submitted for a variety of operations (e.g. building and engineering). Several interviewees felt that the local planning process could be improved. For example, when fracking started in the UK, interviewees felt that it would have been good to provide training on the technology and extraction process for planning officers. This might still be the case now.

EU policy makers

- The UK experience might be of interest to other EU countries and policymakers because it makes apparent the importance of including citizens in the debates surrounding pathways towards low carbon energy transitions. Transparency and democracy therefore are key notions that need to be part of energy transitions. Democratic processes need to be kept alive, including local decision-making.
- Moreover, the UK experience demonstrates that citizens are already getting engaged and participate in energy transitions. Energy pathways that are being pursued can be extremely diverse. The question might therefore not be how to engage people but rather how to include citizens into decision-making processes, in particular voices that are not being heard at the moment.
- Another lesson from the UK case study on framings against fossil fuel pathways is that determining who becomes a campaigner and who gets involved in anti-fossil fuel activities is not a straightforward question to answer. People seem to have diverse motivations leading them to get involved and ideas about what are appropriate and relevant activities to pursue. In the case of the UK, campaigners have been framed as extremist, lefties and environmentalists (partly in order to create divisions). The empirical evidence has shown these categorisations are highly problematic and do not help when trying to think about how to engage citizens in energy transitions.

SIE-field-actors

- Having conducted research into civil society activities for several years, I have been blown away by the amount of research, analysis and documentation that has been produced by people who get involved in anti-fossil fuel activities. This research work feels extremely useful.

- A lot of the interviewees talked about the friendships that they have forged, personal journeys that they have been on, the high percentage of women organising activities (in particular in anti-fracking), all stories that sometimes might get lost in the details of understanding the political economy of phasing out (or not) fossil fuel. I feel that these stories should not get lost.
- It seems that mobilisations increasingly happen across borders. European and international connections and networks are being forged, enabling learning and knowledge sharing across social, political and cultural contexts.

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9 Annex 1

Methodology

Considering that much has happened within this SIE-field over the past ten years and some might argue that anti-coal, anti-fracking and divestment deserve to be studied in-depth in their own right, there are clear limitations to this report. The focus of the historical account is based on (and partly limited by) the people that I was able to interview, number of documents and websites I could examine and the time I had to conduct the research (1.5 months).

Overall, I was able to conduct 11 in-depth interviews, review in-depth around 20 documents (several media articles were also consulted but not listed in the report), and study around 13 websites. Due to COVID, it was not possible to conduct face-to-face participant observations. Instead, I joined two online events. See tables below in this section for more details.

Although I have previously examined community energy projects in the UK, my former research work had not focused on framings against fossil fuel energy pathways. I gained an overview of key organisations through preliminary internet searches and talking to colleagues at the Sussex Energy Group, who have engaged with the movements. These colleagues supported the search to gain interviewees for this work i.e. they worked as gatekeepers. Being introduced to an interviewee through a trusted person seemed key for people to agree to be interviewed. The sampling strategy was therefore based on convenience and snowball sampling. I have spoken to more people who have been involved in anti-onshore oil and gas than anti-coal and divestment (see table below). My interviews around anti-onshore oil and gas have mainly been with people involved in local and regional activities (in particular in Sussex (including the Isle of Wight) and Lancashire). My interviews around anti-coal and divestment included two local groups and national organisations. The interviews with the participants provided a good overview of their emergence and development over time and the influence of wider regulatory, social and policy changes.

I have also gained a good overview of national developments through reviewing the recent academic social science energy literature (where a vast amount of literature has been written about 'fracking' but less so on coal and divestment) and examining several websites (e.g. Coal Action Network and DrillOrDrop.com) (see table below). It is possible to argue that some of these activities are extremely well documented by people, who are dedicated to researching and documenting framings against fossil fuel energy pathways in the UK (often in their spare time). Some of these websites provide a far more detailed historical account about particular movements and activities than I am able to do in this report (for onshore oil and gas, for example, see DrillOrDrop.com). The sampling of the documents and websites was based on a search of journal articles in ScienceDirect (for more details see document review sub-section) and preliminary internet search of key groups and organisation involved (i.e. their websites and reports). The search was expanded based on the additional groups and organisations mentioned by the interviewees.

The initiatives that mainly feature in this report are: 1) The Weald Action Group is ‘an umbrella for local groups campaigning against all forms of extreme extraction of oil & gas across the Weald and the Isle of Wight in the South East of England’ (see Weald Action Group website). The aims are to support other community groups through providing training, facilitating networking, getting involved in lobbying and campaigns. I have spoken to members from Isle of Wight and **Balcombe groups**, who are part of the Weald Action group. 2) Two local groups based in Lancashire (North England): **Preston New Road Action Group** is a ‘residents’ organisation trying to help save our community and the planet from fossil fuel extraction by fracking’ (see Preston New Road Action Group website) and **Roseacre Awareness Group** is a community organisation which aims to engage in planning applications, public inquiries and any other statutory processes to protect the local and surrounding area from any exploration of oil and gas and at the same time to work bring together residents and work in partnership with like-minded organisations (see Roseacre Awareness Group). 3) **Fossil Free Sussex** is ‘part of a wider national Fossil Free campaign led by People and Planet, which aims to pressure universities to remove their investments from fossil fuel industry (known as divestment)’. They are a local group at the University of Sussex. (See Students’ Union website, University of Sussex). 4) **Coal Action Network** (and the **Campaign to Protect Pont Valley** – led by local campaigners and residents and works with the Coal Action Network) ‘works for an end to coal-fired power generation, coal extraction and coal imports in the UK, and justice for communities affected by the UK’s current and historical coal consumption and mining’ (see Coal Action Network website).

Documents and websites reviewed

For the document review, I conducted a search in ScienceDirect with several search terms (e.g. fracking in the UK) to gain a selection of journal articles that outline different UK framings against fossil fuel topics derived from the social science energy literature. A wide variety of journal articles emerged about anti-fracking (in particular looking at framings), fewer articles have come up about coal and divestment. I have not listed all of the articles in the below table but only the ones that I have drawn on the most for the analysis. As part of the case study work, I also looked at several actors, groups and organisations’ websites. Some of them have produced their own reports, statements, newspaper articles, etc. This also included policy documents (e.g. derived from DECC and BEIS). I chose to analyse the documents (i.e. reports) that helped me to deepen my understanding of key events and activities mentioned by the interviewees. I have not listed all of the documents in the below table but just a selection (to give the reader an idea of the types of material consulted for the analysis):

Author name	Document name	Document type	Year
Andrea Brock	‘Frack off’: Towards an anarchist political ecology critique of corporate and state responses to anti-fracking resistance in the UK	Journal article	2020
Atif Ansar Ben Caldecott James Tilbury	Stranded assets and the fossil fuel divestment campaign: what does divestment mean for the valuation of fossil fuel assets?	Journal article	2013
Benjamin Brown, Samuel J. Spiegel	Resisting coal: Hydrocarbon politics and assemblages of protest in the UK and Indonesia	Journal article	2017

Christina Beatty, Stephen Fothergill, Ryan Powell	Twenty years on: has the economy of the UK coalfields recovered?	Journal article	2007
Coal Action Network	Ditch coal	Report	2015
Coal Action Network	Coal Action Network's response to the UK Government's Coal Generation in Great Britain Consultation Document	Report	2016
Elizabeth Bomberg	Shale We Drill? Discourse Dynamics in UK Fracking Debates	Journal article	2017
Department of Energy and Climate Change	Developing Onshore Shale Gas and Oil – Facts about 'Fracking'	Policy document	2013
Green Alliance	The case against new coal mines in the UK	Report	2020
Greig Aitken	THE UK'S DIRTY COAL SECRET	Report	2019
House of Commons	Shale gas and fracking	Briefing paper	2020
Julie Ayling & Neil Gunningham	Non-state governance and climate policy: the fossil fuel divestment movement	Journal article	2017
Laurence Williams, Benjamin K. Sovacool	The discursive politics of 'fracking': Frames, storylines, and the anticipatory contestation of shale gas development in the United Kingdom	Journal article	2019
Lorraine Whitmarsh, Nick Nash, Paul Upham, Alyson Lloyd, James P. Verdon, J.-Michael Kendall	UK public perceptions of shale gas hydraulic fracturing: The role of audience, message and contextual factors on risk perceptions and policy support	Journal article	2015
Netpol	Protecting the Protectors - MONITORING THE POLICING OF ANTI-FRACKING PROTESTS SINCE 2014	Report	2016
Noam Bergman	Impacts of the Fossil Fuel Divestment Movement: Effects on Finance, Policy and Public Discourse	Journal article	2018
Phil Johnstone, Sabine Hielscher	Phasing out coal, sustaining coal communities? Living with technological decline in sustainability pathways	Journal article	2017
Sarah J. Darby	Coal fires, steel houses and the man in the moon: Local experiences of energy transition	Journal article	2017
The Royal Society and The Royal Academy of Engineering	Shale gas extraction in the UK: a review of hydraulic fracturing	Research report	2012

Individuals, grassroots organisations and networks and local groups have documented anti-fossil fuel campaigns in the UK with much detail on their **websites**. Much of the historical narrative has also derived from study and analysing their websites. The following websites have been studied in depth for this report: a) Drill or Drop? - <https://drillordrop.com>; b) Frack Off - <https://frack-off.org.uk>; c) Reclaim the Power - <https://reclaimthepower.org.uk>; d) People and Planet - <https://peopleandplanet.org>; e) 350.org - <https://350.org>; f) Campaign Against Climate Change - <https://www.campaignccc.org>; g) Friends of the Earth - <https://friendsoftheearth.uk>; h) Coal Action Network - <https://www.coalaction.org.uk>; i) Frack Free Balcombe Residents Association - <https://frackfreebalcombe.org.uk>; Protect Pont Valley - <https://protectpontvalley.noblogs.org/blog/>; Preston New Road Action Group - <https://pnrgroup.org.uk>;

Roseacre Awareness Group - <http://www.ragfrack.co.uk>; Frack Free Isle of Wight - <https://www.dontdrillthewight.co.uk>. Additional websites have been consulted but not studied in depth.

List of interviewees

Code interview	Empirical description of case*	Type of actor according to SONNET**	Date of interview	Duration of interview	Interviewer
Interviewee 1	Reporter	Other field-actor	29.07.2020	01:54:49	Sabine Hielscher
Interviewee 2	Academic & activist	Other field-actor/ SIE-field-actor	04.09.2020	01:08:23	Sabine Hielscher
Interviewee 3	Member of Frack Free Isle of Wight	SIE-initiative	21.09.2020	01:55:12	Sabine Hielscher
Interviewee 4	Member of Weald Action Group	SIE-field actor/ SIE-initiative	25.09.2020	01:33:10	Sabine Hielscher
Interviewee 5	Former staff member/ Campaigns Manager at People & Planet	SIE-field-actor/ SIE-initiative	25.09.2020	01:03:48	Sabine Hielscher
Interviewee 6	Member of Preston New Road Action Group	SIE-field-actor/ SIE-initiative	29.09.2020	01:08:58	Sabine Hielscher
Interviewee 7	Member of Roseacre Awareness Group	SIE-initiative/ SIE-field-actor	30.09.2020	01:21:05	Sabine Hielscher
Interviewee 8	Member of Weald Action Group	SIE-field-actor/ SIE-initiative	05.10.2020	01:32:16	Sabine Hielscher
Interviewee 9	Trustee People and Planet	SIE-field-actor/ SIE-initiative	Transcript previous SEG project (consent gained)	-	Noam Bergman
Interviewee 10	Former member Fossil Free Sussex	SIE-initiative	Transcript previous SEG project (consent gained)	-	Noam Bergman
Interviewee 11	Part-time freelancer at the Coal Action Network	SIE-field-actor	27.10.2020	01:20:34	Sabine Hielscher

*Most of the interviewees have several affiliations. I have only mentioned one so that the interviewee cannot be identified.

**I mentioned more than one actor type to indicate that the interviewee has several affiliations that fall into different actor types according to SONNET.

List of meetings and events attended

Code event	Event name	Event organiser (name or description)	Type of event	Date of event	Who attended
Event 1	Ende Gelaende: Media Training	Ende Gelaende	Online webinar	05.05.2020	Sabine Hielscher
Event 2	Horse Hill Oil Legal Challenge	Weald Action Group	Free live online webinar	24.09.2020	Sabine Hielscher

10 Annex 2

SIE-field timeline

The SIE-field timeline does not show all of the events that occurred during the last ten year of framings against fossil fuel energy pathways in the UK. All of the key national policy events should be included. The activities surrounding framings against fossil fuel energy pathways and steps taken by the fossil fuel industry have been so manifold that the table cannot present a complete picture of everything that has happened during this period. I have therefore tried to concentrate on the events and activities linked to key initiatives mentioned throughout the report. The initiatives mentioned in the report and associated events listed in the table are meant to exemplify the diversity of activities and events that occurred from 2010 onwards in the UK. Some of the events listed in the report might not be listed in the table. The table therefore shows national policy developments over time whilst exemplifying activities surrounding opposition to fossil fuel in some parts of the country (see introduction for a list of initiatives that have been studied in more depth for this report).

DATE	TYPE OF EVENT	DESCRIPTION OF EVENT	SOURCE
	External trend	Coal industries and the trade related to them were considered to be crucial for the rise of the Industrial Revolution.	
1984-1985	SIE-field events	Miners' strike.	
1970s	SIE-field events	The closure of coal collieries from the 1970s onwards meant the industry collapsed. The number of people employed in mining fell from one million in 1920 to 2,000 in 2015.	
1994	Policy 'event'	Privatisation of the sector with the introduction Coal Industry Act.	
2007	SIE-field events	Cuadrilla secured planning permissions for several shale gas exploration sites including Preese Hall, Becconsall/Banks, Grange Road/Singleton and Anna's Roads.	Interviewee 1
2008	SIE-field events	40-50 planning applications for opencast mining are submitted; Creation of Coal Action Network.	Interviewee 11
2009	Policy 'event'	Planning application was rejected by Council for Bradley mine (Pont Valley), Durham.	
PHASE 1: Some new emerging anti-fossil fuel campaigns around 2010 - 2012			
May 2011	Policy 'event'	Fracking was suspended following two seismic tremors with magnitudes 2.3 and 1.5 following drilling in Presse Hall, Lancashire, in Northwest England during fracking operations by Cuadrilla – UK moratorium on fracking.	Interviewee 1
Summer 2011	SIE-field events	The divestment movement began when student activists launched campaigns in six universities in the US to divest their endowments from coal.	

Nov/ Oct 2011	SIE-field events	UK Coal appealed the Council's decision to reject planning permission for Bradley mine, which led to a three-week public inquiry.	
Sep 2011	SIE-field events	Cuadrilla's press conference hosted for councilors of all levels in Blackpool, North England was aimed at demonstration of the benefits of 'new gas'.	Frack Off
Oct 2011	SIE-field events	Cuadrilla caused earthquakes at the site of its two test wells - British Geological Survey confirms.	Frack Off
2012	SIE-field events	The divestment movement grew considerably in 2012 due largely to the climate advocacy group 350.org, founded in 2008.	
March 2012	Policy 'event'	East Sussex County Council passed a motion highlighting concerns over Fracking, the first county in England.	Frack Off
April 2012	Policy 'event'	UK government report was published. Despite acknowledging the role of fracking in causing seismic activity in Blackpool, the report called for deployment of fracking.	
Nov 2012	SIE-field events	No Dash for Gas action group occupied West Burton, North Yorkshire gas-fired power station - Reclaim the Power formed out of it.	
Dec 2012	Policy 'event'	Chancellor George Osborne announced that he wanted a "dash for gas", and for Britain to be at the centre of the European shale gas industry.	
Dec 2012	Policy 'event'	UK government lifted restrictions on fracking exploration activities, leading to Cuadrilla and iGas's exploration activities, both of which triggered significant local protest.	
PHASE 2: Local mobilisations and continuations surrounding anti-fossil fuel around 2013-2014			
2013	SIE-field events	Main targets of Coal Action Scotland, Scottish coal and ATH Resources, collapsed.	Coal Action Network
2013	SIE-field events	People & Planet launched the Fossil Free campaign, over 68 UK universities divested.	
April 2013	SIE-field events	Establishment of the Scottish Mines Restoration Trust: Restore derelict coal sites.	
Summer 2013	SIE-field events	Large protest took place in Balcombe, West Sussex, when a wide range of the public, including farmers, environmentalists, church groups, Members of Parliament (MPs) and local residents, mobilised to protest about energy firm Cuadrilla's plan to drill an exploratory borehole.	
Summer 2013	Policy 'event'	Department of Energy and Climate Change survey showed growth in awareness around fracking was not steady over this period, rather there was a steep increase in awareness in the period coinciding with the protests at Balcombe in West Sussex. There has been a gradual decline in support and an increase in the level of opposition.	
Aug 2013	SIE-field events	Reclaim the power camp opened. No Dash for Gas held a meeting at the Reclaim the Power camp in Balcombe.	DrillOrDrop.com
Autumn 2013	SIE-field events	Protests about shale gas drilling at Barton Moss in Salford –It's important because it was a shale gas site (which Balcombe wasn't). It didn't attract much national media interest – at the time it was thought this was	

		because it was in the north west, away from London, and the protests were in winter (DrillOrDrop.com)	
2014	SIE-field events	Seven new opencast applications rejected/ not put forward in planning stage.	
2014	Policy 'event'	Decision: Aberthaw, Wales coal power station. The European Court of Justice confirmed that the power station has been in breach of EU air pollution regulation since 2008.	Coal Action Network
2014	SIE-field events	The University of Glasgow became the first University in Europe to fully divest from fossil fuel industries.	
Jan 2014	Policy 'event'	Prime Minister, David Cameron announced that the UK was "going all out for shale gas".	
April 2014	Policy 'event'	Cuadrilla received planning permission from West Sussex County Council to test its oil exploration well. Frack Free Balcombe Residents Association submitted its objection to Cuadrilla's planning.	
Aug 2014	SIE-field events	Frack Free Balcombe Residents Association won the right to challenge in court the decision by West Sussex County Council to grant planning permission to Cuadrilla to flow test and flare in the village. They lost a judicial review in Dec 2014.	
PHASE 3: Local mobilisations and resulting national policy changes around anti-fossil fuels 2014-2015			
2015	SIE-field events	2015 was said to be a year of slow progress, or in many cases no progress, for the fracking industry. Public protests against proposed shale extraction mounted; demonstrations took place outside parliament.	Frack off
2015	Policy 'event'	Opposition MPs imposed a series of constraining amendments and regional governments in Scotland and Wales imposed moratoria on shale extraction.	
Feb 2015	Policy 'event'	The 2015 Infrastructure Act came in. It departed from the 2008 Planning Act and the 2011 Localism Act that aimed to involve local communities in decisions which affected them by suggesting that more decision-making powers was to be returned to the Secretary of State.	
March 2015	SIE-field events	Time to Act demonstration, London.	
June 2015	Policy 'event'	Lancashire County Council refusing planning permission to Cuadrilla in 2015; the Communities Secretary's subsequently decided that exploration should go ahead at Preston New Road, Lancashire (2016). To drill and frack at Preston New Road and Roseacre Wood. An application for a seismic array at Roseacre Wood was approved.	
June 2015	Policy 'event'	Planning permission was granted for Bradley mine (Consett, Pont Valley), Durham. Planning permission was granted to the now liquidated UK Coal, after a second planning inquiry for this application.	
Aug 2015	Policy 'event'	Oil and Gas Authority released details of new onshore oil and gas licences issued under the 14 th round.	
Sep 2015	Policy 'event'	The government announced details of how it intended to fast-track fracking applications through the planning system. The rules were being changed to allow the government to take over decisions on shale gas	

		appeals, e.g. Cuadrilla's appeal of the rejection of its applications in Lancashire.	
Nov 2015	Policy 'event'	UK government announced that UK's coal plants to be phased out by 2025.	
Dec 2015	SIE-field events	Closure of Britain's last deep coal mine, North Yorkshire's Kellingley Colliery.	
PHASE 4: Increasing local protests and national actions surrounding anti-fossil fuel around 2015 – 2018			
2016	Policy 'event'	UK coal phase out consultation launched by UK government.	
2016	SIE-field events	The anti-fracking movement reached almost 300 anti-fracking groups across the country.	Frack Off
Feb 2016	SIE-field events	Halt to coal production by Hargreaves Services in Scotland – just keeping one opencast coal mine open.	
May 2016	SIE-field events	End Coal Now camp at the site of the UK's largest opencast coalmine, Ffos-y-Fran in South Wales	
Summer 2016	Policy 'event'	The coalmine near to Druridge Bay, Northumberland was approved by Northumberland County Council.	
Sep 2016	SIE-field events	London Borough's Waltham Forest's pension fund committee became the first UK public authority to announce its commitment to go 100% fossil fuel free	
Oct 2016	Policy 'event'	The Secretary of State approved Cuadrilla's fracking plans at Preston New Road & reopened the public inquiry on the Roseacre Wood application.	
Nov 2016	SIE-field events	Anti-fracking groups from across Lancashire gathered and continued to mobilise to oppose Cuadrilla plans for large scale tests at the Preston New Road site on the Fylde Coast in Lancashire.	Frack off
Dec 2016	SIE-field events	Actions against Aberthaw, Wales coal power station.	Coal Action Network
Jan 2017	SIE-field events	A site off the Preston New Road in Lancashire in the northwest became 'ground zero' for the shale gas conflict in England. Work began on the site at Preston New Road – near daily protests outside the site.	
Feb 2017	SIE-field events	Ditch Coal Now! Demonstration, London. The government ends its public consultation on whether to phase-out coal in 2025.	Coal Action Network
Feb 2017	SIE-field events	National day of anti-fracking action in solidarity with Lancashire with a demo at Preston New Road fracking site.	Frack off
April 2017	SIE-field events	Multiple demos against Drax on the day of their AGM - Drax the UK's biggest coal fired power station.	Coal Action Network
April 2017	SIE-field events	Attempts to shut down Ffos-y-fran (Wales), the UK's biggest opencast coal mine.	Coal Action Network
April 2017	SIE-field events	Britain went a full day without using coal power to generate electricity for the first time since the Industrial Revolution – according to the National Grid.	Coal Action Network
March 2017	SIE-field events	Public inquiry whether coal will be mined from near Druridge Bay in Northumberland. Friends of the Earth submitted documents showing how the mine was incompatible with commitments on climate change.	Coal Action Network

		Actions by supporters were also crucial – more than 20,000 people emailed Mr Javid asking him to reject the plans. 300 people turned out for a rally on the beach.	
July 2017	SIE-field events	Energy Symposium at Preston New Road, Lancashire Fracking Camp.	Coal Action Network
July 2017	SIE-field events	Trade union UNISON voted in support of divestment of local authority pension funds.	
Sep 2017	Policy 'event'	Theresa May confirms UK coal phase-out. Today (18th September 2017) Prime Minister Theresa May confirmed that the UK will stop using coal for electricity generation by 2025.	Coal Action Network
Nov 2017	Policy 'event'	UK and Canada launched the 'Powering Past Coal Alliance' (PPCA), a coalition of governments, organisations and businesses seeking to establish a phase-out of coal for electricity generation by 2050 at the latest.	
Feb 2018	SIE-field events	Intense protest at Bradley mine (Consett, Pont Valley), Durham. The site was the focus of intense protest since February, when Banks started to remove an ancient boundary hedge. Asking the Secretary of State for Communities and Local Government to revoke planning permission, pressing for police action to stop the wildlife crimes Banks Group was committing and appealing to Durham County Council.	Coal Action Network
March 2018	Policy 'event'	Secretary of State for Communities and Local Government rejected plans for an opencast coal mine at Druridge Bay, Northumberland coast.	
May 2018	Policy 'event'	The government defended its refusal of planning permission for a highly destructive opencast coal mine at Druridge Bay in Northumberland. The government was faced with a legal challenge by the Banks Group.	
July 2018	SIE-field events	Operations began at the Bradley open-cast mine by Banks at Bradley mine (Consett, Pont Valley), Durham	
Oct 2018	Policy 'event'	The government consultation on shale gas closed. Proposal was to make shale gas exploration (not fracking) permitted development, avoiding the need to go through the planning permission process. The government also proposed making major shale gas production schemes part of the Nationally-significant Infrastructure Project regime – taking decisions away from local authorities.	Interviewee 1
Oct 2018	SIE-field events	Cuadrilla started hydraulic fracturing at its flagship Preston New Road site in Lancashire.	Fossil Free Fuel UK
Nov 2018	Policy 'event'	Over 800 councillors signed an open letter opposing government proposals to allow fracking companies to undertake exploratory drilling without local planning applications.	Fossil Free Fuel UK
PHASE 5: Times of refocusing... the need to continue around 2015 to summer 2020			
2019	Policy 'event'	UK government committed to achieving net-zero emissions.	
March 2019	Policy 'event'	Plans for deep coal mine approved in Cumbria. Even though no deep coal mine has been opened since the 1980s, plans were approved by Cumbria County Council for the Woodhouse Colliery site.	
March 2019	Policy 'event'	Fracking firm Cuadrilla lost a planning appeal to start work at Roseacre Wood, Lancashire.	

March 2019	SIE-field events	MP's call for divestment of fossil fuels from pension fund. Debate in parliament when more than one third of MPs call on pension fund trustees to stop investing in fossil fuels in support of move to net zero emissions.	Fossil Free Fuel UK
Aug 2019	SIE-field events	Aberthaw's (Wales) closing: A massive victory against climate catastrophe and air pollution. RWE announced in August that its Aberthaw power station will close in March 2020. The European Court of Justice ruled against the UK government in 2016.	Coal Action Network
Aug 2019	SIE-field events	Fracking at the second Preston New Road well (PNR2) suspended by the OGA hours after the UK's most powerful fracking-induced earth tremor on 26 August 2019	Interviewee 1
Nov 2019	Policy 'event'	Government announced an immediate moratorium on fracking until "further evidence is provided that it can be carried out safely." Governments in Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland had already issued measures that amount to moratoriums on fracking.	Interviewee 1
Nov 2019	Policy 'event'	In the South East of England there was no fracking "pause". Exploration of shale gas in the North of England affected by it, but fracking for shale oil not. For instance, the moratorium doesn't cover acid fracking or proppant squeeze.	
Dec 2019	Policy 'event'	The Cabinet Office released its – still heavily redacted – secret report on the fracking industry, following a 22-month Freedom of Information battle with Uneathed. The report blamed "public opposition driven by ... concerns about local quality of life and safety, environmental protection" resulting in "several practical barriers, with the most significant for operators so far being long timelines/uncertainty in local planning".	
Jan 2020	Policy 'event'	Some fracking for oil and gas could still go ahead, despite the government's moratorium, a ministerial statement has indicated.	DrillOrDrop.com
Feb 2020	SIE-field events	Three days of mass actions at Bradley mine (Consett, Pont Valley), Durham. Extinction Rebellion joined forces with local campaigners to hold a three-day mass action, calling on Durham County Council to reject Banks Mining Group's plans for expansion ahead of the planning committee's decision in early March.	Fossil Free Fuel UK
May 2020	SIE-field events	Angus Energy withdrew a planning application for an extended well test after planners recommended refusal. The company remains the licensee and today (30/7/2020) listed the well test for quarter 4 of 2020. The planning application has not yet been resubmitted. Application was resubmitted for a one-year test but no date yet for a decision – the earliest it could be is January 2021. See entry for August 2020.	Interviewee 1
March 2020	SIE-field events	Frack Free Isle of Wight has welcomed news that the island's council has halted all planning decisions during the covid-19 outbreak.	DrillOrDrop.com
March 2020	SIE-field events	Cuadrilla has taken more equipment off its fracking site near Blackpool this week.	DrillOrDrop.com

June 2020	Policy 'event'	The UK energy minister said that fracking was over and the government had "moved on".	DrillOrDrop.com
June 2020		A public consultation into plans by UK Oil & Gas to explore for oil at Arreton on the Isle of Wight has opened.	DrillOrDrop.com
June 2020	SIE-field events	The owner of the fracking firm Cuadrilla predicted today that England's moratorium on hydraulic fracturing would be lifted – but not before 2021.	DrillOrDrop.com
July 2020	Policy 'event'	A consultation on plans to drill for oil on the Isle of Wight has closed with an estimated 1,700+ objections.	DrillOrDrop.com
Aug 2020	SIE-field events	Angus Energy's new plans to test for oil at its Balcombe site in West Sussex have been published.	DrillOrDrop.com
Sep 2020	SIE-field events	A campaigner's legal challenge against oil production in Surrey has grown into a case to bring UK planning policy into line with climate change strategy.	DrillOrDrop.com
Sep 2020	SIE-field events	UK-wide protests about climate change by Extinction Rebellion	DrillOrDrop.com

11. Annex 3

Detailed SIE-initiatives descriptions

1. Campaign to Protect Pont Valley, Durham, North England

Campaign to Protect Pont Valley, Durham, North England

The long history of anti-coal and the multiplicity of activities to stop the industry (and vice versa) can be exemplified by what has happened at the Bradley mine in the Pont Valley area (Durham, North England). The area has been recovering from the loss of jobs caused by the closure of the deep pits over the past decades, but opencast coalmining has continued. The local community has fought to stop coalmining in the area over 50 years, trying to object to several planning applications. Over the last decade, the UK Coal's application to Durham County Council for the Bradley mine was unanimously rejected in 2009. Local people had formed a community group, The Pont Valley Network, and the associated No Opencast Today or Tomorrow (NOTT) campaign to fight the application. They were supported by the Coal Action Network (i.e. grassroots campaigns to stop coal mining and for a transition to a clean, just energy system).

UK Coal appealed the Council's decision which led to a three-week public inquiry in October and November 2011. Following the inquiry, the inspector upheld the council's decision, but UK Coal refused to take no for an answer and appealed to the high court in June 2013. The high court overturned the inspector's report leading to another three-week public inquiry which took place in October 2014. Both appeals were attended by local people who spoke out against the mine. In June 2015, the company gained permission to mine the site, despite UK Coal going into administration during the application processes (Coal Action Network 2015). Nothing happened for several years.

In 2018, Banks Group acquired the mining rights won by the liquidated UK Coal. The Campaign to Protect Pont Valley teamed up with national and international activists to continue the campaign which mixed direct action with political lobbying and legal challenges, whilst setting up the Pont Valley Protection Camp (including skill sharing activities). A petition signed by over 80,000 people was sent to the Secretary of State, Sajid Javid.

Nonetheless, the 500,000 tonne Bradley coal extraction site went ahead (even though the UK government announced the intention to phase out coal in 2015). At the time, campaigners tried to slow down Banks' preparation work on site through, for instance, continuous lock-ons and human chains because the company's planning permission was due to run out in June 2018.

'It was a great camp. Usually, the day started off. It's like literally getting your tent out from under the snow... Yeah, it was all about occupying the land. So, to stop them from actually starting the operations on the land... And the last 48 hours were like in a film like. There were lock ons, lock ons, lock ons. The last night, it was raining, and it was dark, and people were locked on... And we were just sitting... oh my god four hours left. Crazy' (Interviewee 2).

Although the coal company was not able to complete the work, the council decided not to enforce the planning restrictions. Over the whole time, campaigners also tried to make a case over the protection of the habitat of the great crested newts (i.e. a protected species) that was found on site but with little success (leading to a civil court case against the coal company in October 2018). However, the work at the coal mining site went ahead.

Over the past two years, the campaign went on to prevent further planning permissions for the extension of the mine. In June 2020, Durham County Council received more than 5000 objections and councillors objected to further extension plans. The company has not appealed the decision, so the campaign has now successfully stopped the spread of opencast coal from Bradley in the Pont Valley. Campaigns continue in the area due to further planning decisions for local opencast coalmines. Although 'the Bradley campaign raised the profile of campaigns against opencast coal mining in the UK' (Coal Action Network website), it did not gain much publicity in the national press (Interviewee 2). As argued by Interviewee 2, 'there's also coal happening in the UK which is something hardly anyone talks about in the overall energy mix because coal is so small now, but they're still pushing to open up new opencast coalmines.'

2. Groups in Balcombe, West Sussex, South England

Groups in Balcombe, West Sussex, South England

'We were on the train home from London when we noticed the article: 'Oil and gas company Cuadrilla to frack in Balcombe'. Fracking? In our village? It was December 2011, and we were still innocents. Back home we searched the internet for tales from America and from the Fylde region of Lancashire, where a well had been fracked by Cuadrilla earlier that year, causing an earthquake. We gathered in TV rooms and watched Gasland' (McWhirter, 2015:85).

In April 2010, Cuadrilla Resources Ltd. (i.e. an oil and gas exploration and production company founded in 2007) was granted planning permission to drill an exploratory oil and gas borehole at Balcombe sites. West Sussex County Council (an elected administrative body governing an area known as a county in the UK) decided that no environmental impact assessment was needed. In September, Cuadrilla started the construction phase but it was not until end of 2011 that the company revealed planning permission for exploratory drilling. A director of the Brighton Energy Coop (BEC) (Brighton is the nearest city to Balcombe) 'alerted the village about it in the first place' (Interviewee 8). A meeting was organised in the Balcombe Village Hall where the BEC and Cuadrilla gave presentations in 2012. 'The whole village was there, and they were

all quite angry about it' (Interviewee 8). A poll showed that the majority of people who participated would oppose any further applications for exploration or extraction of hydrocarbons in Balcombe. During the meeting, it also became visible that some of the residents were worried about (and against) protestors from Brighton arriving at their village.

'Balcombe is almost feudal, with farms, woodlands and many houses belonging to the one family, and rented to their workers. That family had leased its field to Cuadrilla. Rifts developed between friends, even within families' (McWhirter, 2015:85). A lot of local residents started to engage with the existing literature on extraction of onshore oil and gas, planning application processes (possibilities to object them) and other ways to stop the development (e.g. writing letters to the prime minister, David Cameron from the Conservative Party, talking to our local member of parliament (MP), inviting speakers from e.g. Poland (i.e. Lech Kowalski to talk about the battle against Chevron) and Canada (i.e. Jessica Ernst to talk about her fight against fracking firm Encana) to speak to local residents, and holding public meetings and informing other residents). 'It was a time of learning' (Interviewee 8). At the same time, Cuadrilla held several public information events in the village, applied for an extension to their planning permission and different permits from the Environment Agency (e.g. radioactive substance permit) (the EA a non-departmental public body with responsibilities relating to the protection and enhancement of the environment in England). In the summer of 2013, the Department of Energy and Climate Change announced that Cuadrilla had drilling consent and activities on site started to further develop.

'On 10 June 2013, three enormous lorry loads of drilling rig arrived, from the nearby motorway junction, thundering past our primary school and homes to the drill site just south of the village, beside an ancient woodland, between the London-to-Brighton railway line and the country road with its wide green verges. Suddenly there were high fencing, guards, and the drill thrusting up and down above the trees. We organised a protest picnic along the verge. Our aim was to delay the work – because Cuadrilla had arrived just four months from the end of their three-year permit. Time was short... It was Friends of the Earth who struck the first blow, pointing out that, before drilling, Cuadrilla needed mining waste and radioactive substance permits from the Environment Agency. Drilling stopped for a one-month public consultation. Normally the Environment Agency expects a handful of objections. This time they got 900, but nevertheless agreed the permit in days' (McWhirter, 2015:86).

Camps and protest outside the site spread out along the verge. The village was split about welcoming more protestors. 'And so, we were blamed by the established people in the village for calling these people in. But we didn't call these people in. But we did get very involved with the people at the camp... we got involved with being down there all the time, taking food and providing things that people needed. People coming up here to have baths in the village and showers from the camp.' (Interviewee 8).

'School and university holiday had started, and families came, plus students, teachers, nurses, carpenters, all sort of people, some of whom, like me, had never protested before. Others were old hands. The weekend brought anti-fracking groups from Wales, Lancashire, Scotland and Kent... The drilling was so noisy that we villagers, getting no response from the

company or the authorities, finally bought our own sound-testing equipment and forced the work to stop while sound baffling was installed' (McWhirter, 2015:87).

Bank holiday August, No Dash for Gas held a meeting about the Reclaim the Power (this is a UK based direct action network fighting for social, environmental and economic justice) camp that around 200 people attended. Direct action consisted of, for instance, marches, wheelchairs blockades, erection of camps, lock-ins and celebrity visits/ participants (e.g. Vivienne Westwood and Caroline Lucas (Green Party MP). Sussex Police was very present and arrested several campaigners (including Caroline Lucas, who in addition to other campaigners was charged with obstructing the highway and a public order offence. They were acquitted of the charges in 2014.)

'I've met a neighbour on the train who is an environmental campaigner, and he was very concerned about what it might do to water quality in the area. So he was very much looking at it from a campaign point of view and I was looking at it from a journalistic point of view... during the course of the day, the atmosphere suddenly changed and there was a kind of well, it was like a march down the road of what you could only call a kind of almost like a platoon of police officers. And I'd never seen anything like this in my life. I completely accept - now that I probably had quite a sort of naive approach to protests at that point. I'd never covered public order policing, never covered demonstrations before. So this was astonishing to me. And I saw all these policemen march down the road. And at that point, a large number of campaigners, protesters went and sat on a log outside the entrance to the site and there was a kind of standoff and then the police basically moved in... And I was astonished by this. First of all, the police felt that it was appropriate to use that sort of technique (i.e. pressure point arrest technique), which I'd never seen before. And I was seeing police officers basically behaving like the paramilitaries. And why would the police do that in support of an industry? And why would people who were sitting on this log risk a criminal record to prevent this industry operating?' (Interviewee 1).

The protests made it into the national and international news. In September 2013, Cuadrilla's planning consent at Balcombe expired. The company told the House of Lords Economic Affairs Committee that they need a 'social licence' to drill and need the consent from local communities. West Sussex County Council used bailiffs to evict the camp.

Two local groups emerged - No Fracking in Balcombe (NoFIBS) and Frack Free Balcombe Resident Association (FFBRA) where membership has in parts overlapped. One of the main differences has been their stand on direct action, where FFBRA objected to it. Instead FFBRA was keen to stop the development by submitting objections to planning applications, lobbying politicians, organising polls in the village where the majority opposed Cuadrilla's plans, and taking a letter to Downing Street calling for a moratorium on shale gas (i.e. a delay or suspension of an activity or law). For instance, in 2014, Cuadrilla submitted a planning application to West Sussex County Council to carry out flow testing and FFBRA submitted an objection. Planning permission was granted in the same year and FFBRA started legal proceedings in the High Court in a judicial review (i.e. a kind of court case, in which someone challenges the lawfulness of a government decision) of the decision. Although FFBRA won the right to challenge the decision in court, they lost the judicial review at the end of the

year.

‘Fracking still fills our days: studies and articles, links with groups around Britain and beyond. We travel in support for other protest camps and to give awareness-raising talks in other communities. We got to London university lectures and debates, and parliamentary committees in Westminster. We have presented evidence to enquiries. We have learnt to lobby. Some of us have given up their jobs. Together we wield a wealth of skills, we have lost some friends but have many new and better friends, with whom we share values’ (McWhirter, 2015:89).

In addition to the legal activities, some of the residents in the village have taken up positions in the Parish Council to be able to influence local decision-making, participated in Select Committees (which check and report on areas ranging from the work of government departments to economic affairs) and All-Party Parliamentary Groups (which are informal cross-party groups that have no official status within the Parliament) on onshore oil and gas for lobby work, spoken at European and international conferences (e.g. organised by the European Union and Greens/EFA Alliance) about what is happening in Balcombe and the UK. Moreover, connections were forged with several other like-minded groups across the country to exchange knowledge and learning. FFBRA also became a member of the Weald Action group, ‘an umbrella for local groups campaigning against all forms of extreme extraction of oil and gas across the Weald and the Isle of Wight in the South East of England’ (see Weald Action Group website).

‘It’s a very, very informal group [Weald Action Group]. It has to be said... There are no kind of formal officers, no formal organisation at all. The various groups like the Horse Hill Protection Group... all work independently. But we have a system of communication... so that we are able to ask for advice, ask for help and get each other to use each other’s social media when we need to get in objections into various planning applications. But the group does form subgroups at different times to do specific tasks. So very soon we’re going to be bringing a report out which is sort of counteracting many of UKOGs arguments about the need for oil [the report came out in October 2020]. And I’ve been working with a group of people on producing it’ (Interviewee 4).

A lot of the interviewees said that they did not just want to be anti – onshore oil and gas but actually wanted to create an alternative energy future for their village, region, etc. Most of them thought about the possibility to create a cooperatively owned renewable energy project. Some of the Balcombe residents were actually able to set up ‘Repower Balcombe’ that aims to ‘generate the equivalent to 100% of Balcombe’s electricity demand through community-owned locally-generated renewable energy’ (see Repower Balcombe website). On the Repower Balcombe website the cooperative social enterprise explains some of the interlinkages, ‘Balcombe’s recent close encounters with hydrocarbon energy production have certainly been an important factor in making us all think about the energy we use and where it comes from – and helped to give us the idea to start our community power company as a positive way to engage with these issues. But we want to be really clear that Repower Balcombe is in no way a protest group, and you don’t need to be anti-fracking or anti-drilling to support the project’ (see Repower Balcombe website).

In 2017, Cuadrilla announced that it would not continue with their plans before May 2017, which meant they had to apply for further planning permission. The West Sussex County Council unanimously approved the planning application for three years for flow testing at the well in 2018. At the same time, Cuadrilla and Angus Energy announced a partnership surrounding the operation of the Balcombe site. In 2018, Angus successfully took out an injunction against ‘persons unknown’ impeding their work at Balcombe, on pain of imprisonment, fines and seizure of assets. The injunction has since been weakened by legal challenges to other similar injunctions elsewhere in the country. Flow tests started at the end of 2018, including protests by villagers. Angus announced that they could only do two flow tests because of unexpected water in the well and plans to extend the well test application in 2019. The decision for the application was delayed because of coronavirus in 2020. Since then, Angus Energy has withdrawn the Balcombe application but has also said that it would return. This was withdrawn after planning officers recommended refusal on the grounds, a three-year flow test was considered inappropriate in an area of outstanding natural beauty. New application for a one-year flow test is currently before West Sussex County Council. Most of the historical account in this box (i.e. key dates and events) derived from DrillOrDrop.com where a more detailed account can be found.

3. Fossil Free Sussex, University of Sussex, South England

Fossil Free Sussex, University of Sussex, South England

Fossil Free Sussex (i.e. local student-led divestment group) officially started at the University of Sussex in 2014. Before this official start, one of the master students heard about divestment as part of a lecture by Jeremy Legget (British social entrepreneur). He started to conduct his own research and decided to launch a Freedom of Information request to the University of Sussex, asking about their investments and endowment funds. At the same time, a small group of master’s students got in touch with the master’s student once they saw he had launched the request. ‘That’s kind of, yes, where it started really. We were basically just a loose band of students... with some input from various members of academic staff’ (Interviewee 10). Once they had the information from the Freedom of Information request, they tried to liaise with the Finance and Investment Committee at the University of Sussex, who engage with the university’s investment manager. ‘So, one of the early issues that we had is that £8m as an investment fund is a small amount of money compared to a lot of... So, we have £8m, for example, I think Oxford have something like £800m. You know, it’s orders of magnitude larger. Because, relatively speaking, it’s a relatively small fund’ (Interviewee 10). The Finance and Investment Committee explained that the fund was too small to actively manage it and ‘there are no eligible funds that we can put this money in that are fossil free that meet the criteria that you are asking of us’ (Interviewee 10). Most of the students involved in the group had a sustainability/ climate change background and therefore little finance expertise. They had to ‘learn quite a lot of the lexicon of finance in quite short space of time’ (Interviewee 10).

As part of their activities, the group connected with the local Students' Union and People and Planet, who organised a wider national student campaign to pressure universities to remove their investment from the fossil fuel industry. The aim of the campaign has been: 'We call on the university to immediately reconsider its investment in the fossil fuel industry and to establish an ethical investment policy which negatively screens fossil fuels, as well as other sectors which contravene ethical and environmental standards, ideally giving student and staff representation within this policy and fair input into decision-making' (Students' Union website University of Sussex). People and Planet provided less information about the finance sector but became really useful for the group when 'we started to come on to the activism side of it, the actual organising process and campaigning, and learning how to run a student campaign They were able to provide resources to us then, so they came and did like campaigning workshops' (Interviewee 10).

People and Planet also provided an online platform from which the group started their petition – 'the backbone of the campaign' (Interviewee 10). The strategy was to get as many people as possible to sign the petition, including some more high-profile public figures. For example, the group managed to ensure that Caroline Lucas (local Green Party MP) signed it. They wanted to 'demonstrate to the university management that there was a real appetite amongst students and staff to divest their endowment funds from fossil fuel' (Interviewee 10). The group organised a large rally to hand over the petition (which 2045 people signed) to the university management, which they received but one of the interviewees argued that 'it wasn't really a two-way conversation' (Interviewee 10). Some of the other activities included film screenings of 'Do the Math' (i.e. Bill McKibben's film about divestment), banner drops, a critical mass protest as part of the Global Divestment Day in 2015 and 'Red Line Demo' in 2016 and 2017 at the university's square. Eventually, the university agreed to a task and finish group (which had no student representatives) to review their investment policy and introduced a new socially responsible investment consideration of not investing in fossil fuels.

At first, the group started to make an argument based on economic grounds. For instance, oil prices are falling, and it is just getting worse and therefore it might be better to invest in more forward-thinking investments. Similarly, Bill McKibben (i.e. the founder of the divestment movement was arguing 'let's get the oil and gas producers where it hurts, i.e. in their pockets' (Interviewee 10), shaping the overall movement. It became clear to the local group that this framing did not hold up. Two of the students decided to write a blog post about it in 2015, after hearing Harry Saunders (researcher in energy and sustainability economics) argued that 'divestment will not keep carbon in the ground', 'pointing out that shares in a company represent a stake in the ownership of that company, but do not affect the fundamental production economics, even if widespread divestment does occur (see Sussex Energy Group blog 2015). In the blog, the two students argued that this argument assumes that the campaign attempts to bankrupt the industry whereas the main aim is inflicting reputational impact. Similarly conducting research into the divestment movement in the UK, Bergman (2018:10) has argued that 'one of the political impacts of divestment is damage to the reputation and legitimacy of the fossil fuel industry'. The group re-orientated their arguments to say 'the university doesn't invest in arms companies, in gambling, and tobacco, and pornography, and all these other... we do this for moral and ethical reasons.

'I think maybe the 'Do the Math' film was very inspiring, but also I suppose a bit like, we're going to move all this money and it's all going to disappear, I think a lot of campaigners have started to realise as the campaign was going is that, yes it's great you're moving your money, but you now need to actually reinvest it into positive renewable investments. It's that whole constant campaigning argument of not always being against something but also being for something different' (Interviewee 9).

In 2018, the group could announce that the 'finance and investment committee have actually moved their money into a fund which doesn't invest in fossil fuel at all. So, essentially, we've had a victory essentially, a complete victory' (Interviewee 10).

'Divestment means that Sussex University are no longer funding the worst polluters of climate change such as BP and Shell. Instead, Sussex are investing in the future of renewable energies for a just transition. The divestment campaign across the world is winning. A massive congratulations to everyone at Sussex who was involved in the campaign; students, the Students' Union and lecturers" (See People and Planet website, statement made by one of the founders of Fossil Free Sussex)

'After 4 years of students petitioning, awareness raising, protesting and negotiations, Sussex has finally pulled it's money out of the fossil fuel industry! This is a significant step in Sussex starting to live up to its reputation as a progressive university. It goes to show that collective voices are strong and student campaigning has the power to make real change' (See People and Planet website, statement made by one of the leaders of Fossil Free Sussex)

Despite moving their money into Liontrust (Sustainable Futures Management Fund), the University of Sussex have not yet written the explicit exclusion of investments in fossil fuels into university policy.

4. Roseacre Awareness Group & Preston New Road Action Group, Lancashire, North England

Roseacre Awareness Group & Preston New Road Action Group, Lancashire, North England

In February 2014, Cuadrilla announced plans for two fracking sites in the Fylde, Lancashire, North England: Roseacre Wood and Preston New Road. In May 2014, Lancashire County Council published the planning application and later on in the year, set up a public consultation. In early 2015 based on noise and traffic grounds, planning officers recommended the refusal to frack at both sites Cuadrilla asked for a deferral of the Council's decision to be able to provide extra information. After several delays to the process, in June 2015, Lancashire County Council planners recommended the approval of Cuadrilla's application to frack in Preston New Road but recommended refused the application for Roseacre Wood based on traffic grounds. During this time, the UK government had been in regular contact with the council about the planning

application. In the meantime, the Environment Agency granted a permit for shale gas exploration and fracking at Roseacre Wood and protection camps were set up near the Preston New Road site. As early as October 2014, Cuadrilla tried to seek an injunction against anti-fracking campaigners in the High Courts to prevent them from entering land on which the company was applying for planning permission to frack shale gas (for more detailed reporting on both cases see Hayhurst's 2014-2020 work). One of the interviewees described people's experiences of this time,

'Before 2014, I was completely oblivious to any of the issues related to fracking except I've heard in the background that there'd been some earthquakes in Lancashire near where I live, but I haven't taken a lot of notice. What woke me up was the fact that Cuadrilla Resources had been doing some surveys in our local area. Again, I didn't take much notice of it. I just thought they were doing some geophysical survey. And then February, I think it's February the 4th, 2014, we got a letter through our door saying that Cuadrilla were looking to apply for planning permission to frack for gas in our village, basically. So of course, it was quite pertinent to me. So, I wanted to find out more about it. I was completely ambivalent at the time, I didn't know much about it, I didn't know whether it was a good or bad thing' (Interviewee 7).

For some of the interviewees, their journey into anti-onshore oil and gas looked very similar. They had not really heard about fracking and/ or drilling for oil and gas before they were contacted by an oil and gas company and were informed about their local plans. Most of them (including interviewee 7) started to read up about fracking, contacted scientists and their local MP, set up and joined local meetings about the topic between residents (and sometimes set up local groups and joined regional ones), attended the company's local PR events and/ or joined the community liaison group. At the beginning, groups did not 'want to be seen as anti-fracking' but within a 'short space of time', people felt that 'fracking was not appropriate in our location or anywhere for that matter. The more we looked into it, the more worried we became' (Interviewee 6). In the case of Lancashire at the time, the Preston New Road Action Group and Roseacre Awareness Group were created – two sites in the Fylde area that are not far from each other.

'We didn't know much about it. I mean, it was literally hours and hours of research, you know, talking to other groups who knew more about things than we did. And not just anti-fracking groups, you know just looking at the evidence, looking at things, the Internet, social media reports from the USA, because obviously fracking hasn't really taken place in this country all that much... Friends of the Earth were very informative because they had the resources behind them. So, they have people who are able to do the research. And Greenpeace for that matter. So that's lots of information. We got information from Cuadrilla and we asked them lots and lots of questions about what the impacts were. The Environment Agency. We actually had the British Geological Society come to speak to us. Obviously, they're more neutral. But they were really good. It was all very scientific... So, we tended to use the skills that people had in the community to try and look at certain things... And we set up a social media group. We set up a website. We did lots and lots of leafleting around the local area. Door-to-door. We had several public meetings of our own where we got people to come and to discuss things. We actually had Cuadrilla. We had the Parish Council... So, bit by bit, more and more people in the local area joined up to our group and we kept them informed. We had a mailing list. Most of it was done to be honest, because it's such a

rural area was done by door to door leafleting and meetings. We had like coffee mornings...' (Interviewee 6).

Cuadrilla submitted the planning application to Lancashire City Council for Preston New Road in May 2014 and Roseacre Wood in June 2014. The groups got active in preparing objections, informing others about the planning process and how to submit an objection.

'I think the key thing to remember is that we were a group of just normal residents that had no experience in fracking. We had no experience in the planning process. But we basically researched, we became aware that we were very concerned about fracking and we had to learn. It was a huge learning curve, both the planning, how we challenged the process and also understanding what fracking was enough to be able to talk sensibly to the regulators, to whoever about it' (Interviewee 6).

Some of the interviewees also got involved in lobbying activities beyond their own regions and spoke at all party parliamentary groups and spoke to shadow prime ministers. Help and support was gained from NGOs like Friends of the Earth and Greenpeace and political parties that opposed fracking, such as the Green Party. To be able to conduct this planning and lobbying work, fundraising also became a fundamental activity for both groups.

'It was quite small at the beginning but where we became more powerful... there were lots of other groups within Lancashire... Preston New Road Action Group and various local groups. So that's where we became known as Frack Free Lancashire. We met up once a month and shared information and shared knowledge and came up basically with a campaign of how we wanted to move things forward. So, we had a very effective strategy. Frack Free Lancashire is not an actual group as such, it's just an umbrella for lots of other groups coming together and sharing information and sharing actions' (Interviewee 7).

In June 2015, Lancashire County Council refused both planning applications in the Fylde area. The atmosphere at the planning meeting was described by one of the interviewees,

'When the Preston New Road and Roseacre Wood fracking applications came before Lancashire County Council that was an extraordinary event. More than 90,000 people signed a petition against the proposals. There were, I think, something like 70,000 objections. There was at least 70 people making statements in the course of the meeting... It was a very powerful expression of how people felt about fracking in their area. And it was also a very powerful expression of why the industry thought it should happen. So I would say that events that occurred in that planning decision meeting were highly significant and followed very closely by national and international media' (Interviewee 1).

The response of Lancashire County Council and the oil and gas industry can be summed up by a statement from a councillor and UK Onshore Oil and Gas at the time,

'Last week we were put under intense pressure which was giving us no option but to approve the application. We had further information over the weekend and have been able to turn it down... It was not about taking a stand against fracking... but I think you cannot agree to fracking 250m from where people live who have health problems' (Councillor as reported by Hayhurst 2015).

'An important plank of the Government's energy policy and manifesto commitment [The Conservative Party announced in their manifesto...] has been refused to a position that despite all the advice a rejection has been given. This after 15 months of a long drawn-out process cannot be right and I urge the government to urgently review the process of decision-making. There is a growing coalition in this country including manufacturing and trade unions that support the need for shale from an economic, environmental and energy security perspective' (UK Onshore Oil and Gas as reported by Hayhurst 2015).

In August 2015, Cuadrilla handed in its first appeal against the refusal of planning permission for shale gas exploration in the Fylde area of Lancashire. In October, it was confirmed that there would be a public inquiry (these are major investigations into public concerns, scrutinising past decisions and events and convened by a government minister) into Cuadrilla's appeal, which took place from February to March 2016. The recommendation from the planning inspector was sent to the Secretary of State in July 2016.

'Prior to the actual inquiry, we had all the documentation to pull together and get to the planning inspectorate by certain deadlines. So, I think, I had at one point just before Christmas, I had something like 30 files full of documentation lined up and had got them boxed up and couriered to Bristol' (Interviewee 6).

'The planning inquiry into Cuadrilla's appeal on fracking at Preston New Road and Roseacre Wood was highly significant. It was like a primer on fracking. Many of the people that had opposed and supported the planning application at Lancashire County Council spoke again at the inquiry. There were councillors, head teachers, people who worked in hotels in Blackpool, putting both sides to it. It was a six-week public inquiry. And when the decision came to approve Preston New Road that then sparked off a series of legal actions by campaign groups for a judicial review to the appeal in court. In the end, I would say it was highly significant' (Interviewee 1).

This is where the 'pathways' of the two sites (i.e. Roseacre Wood and Preston New Road) go their separate ways...

Roseacre Wood's pathway

It took into October 2016 for the Communities Secretary to announce that he would allow against the refusal of planning permission to frack Roseacre Wood if the traffic problems can be resolved. He reopened the public inquiry so that Cuadrilla could provide evidence on highway safety. The inquiry opened in April 2018, after a failed attempt for a statutory

challenge (i.e. planning decisions can be challenged in the courts through a judicial review; there are instances where a statutory regime governing a particular decision can prevent the decision being challenged in court except in accordance with specific statutory provisions that are known as statutory challenges) against the decision to reopen the inquiry. The inspector of the reopened inquiry submitted his report in September 2018: five months later, Cuadrilla's appeal is refused by the Local Government Secretary.

'Our case was always a silly one to do with traffic. It wasn't much to do with climate change or pollution, although those were all factors. But the big factor at Roseacre were those huge HGVs trundling up and down country lanes. And the fact that it was a totally unsuitable industry in the middle of a very agricultural rural area, which was known for rural tourism. So, it and I think the thing that drove us as a group was the fact that it was being imposed upon us' (Interviewee 7).

Preston New Road's pathway

Rather than reopen the public inquiry as in the case of Roseacre Wood, the Communities Secretary announced that he would overturn Lancashire County Councils decisions on fracking at Preston New Road. At the time, the Preston New Road Action Group (PNRAG) wrote a press release as a response to the decision,

'Preston New Road Action Group are devastated to learn that Sajid Javid, the Secretary of State for Local Government and Communities has upheld the appeals in favour of Cuadrilla, and overruled local democracy. Westby Parish Council, Fylde Borough Council and Lancashire County Council planning committee all said no to these applications. For good reasons based on facts and knowledge, they rejected these sites as totally unsuitable. Over 100,000 people objected to fracking here: unprecedented numbers of the community said no. Due democratic process has been followed but our local community will feel ignored and overruled by this decision. Effectively, an external corporate industry is controlling local democratic planning decisions. The chair of Preston New Road Action Group stated: "There is no social license to proceed with fracking in Lancashire"' (Preston New Road Action Group 2016 on their website).

In November 2016, PNRAG (represented by a law firm) issued formal legal proceedings at the High Court against the government's decision to grant permission to frack at the Preston New Road site. The group had written to the Secretary of State, asking him to reconsider the decision but he refused. They argued the 'government's decision to overrule Lancashire County Council's refusal of planning permission for fracking in Fylde, Lancashire is unlawful because the decision is fundamentally flawed as it failed to properly apply relevant planning laws and policy' (PNRAG, 2016 on their website). In January 2017, Cuadrilla started construction work at the site. Some people involved in anti-fracking increased their lobbying work and took part in preparing the formal legal and regulatory proceedings (which included e.g. engaging with experts, reviewing documents and liaising with regulators and legal teams (such as the Environment Agency)). Other people also got involved in direct action that had been at the site from the beginning, but which now intensified. It consisted of 'slow-walking (in front of delivery lorries), blockading sites (e.g. with lock-on devices, or 'lorrysurfing'), demonstrations, and marches' (Brock 2020:3).

'Our position [PNRAG] was that we were challenging through the official channels. So, we did our challenging through the planning process, through the regulators, through that route. And as a group, we didn't tend to get involved in the direct action although some members of the group obviously did take part. But as far as a whole, the group the challenge was more around the court cases and the liaising with the regulators and that side of things' (Interviewee 6). In addition, the group installed their own monitoring equipment to be able check the water and air quality and noise levels.

'I was always particularly impressed by Preston New Road because it was there for five years and people were there for five years day and night. And there were always people at the gates for years... Because it's quite easy to do an action somewhere and maybe people are arrested and have a trial and that's over. But to really stick on and stay with it for so many years. Every morning getting police abuse, trauma to make yourself come to that gate, sing and knit. I think that is really quite impressive. In the snow, in the rain, in the cold...' (Interviewee 2).

In February 2017, two rallies against fracking were organised, attracting hundreds of people from across the country whilst in May, people arrived from across Europe to support the protests. Local councillors, celebrities, and politicians joined in. In the summer of 2017, the Camp of New Hope held a large energy symposium organised by Biofuelwatch, Coal Action Network and Reclaim the Power. During July, Reclaim the Power held a 'month of rolling resistance'. The Council employed security guards at the cost over £59,000 per month to guard parts of the site. The police 'operation cost almost £13m... less than half of the arrests resulted in convictions' (as reported by Hayhurst 2020).

One of the interviewees reflected upon how the campaign had changed for her over the years, 'originally, it was very local, very focused on specific issues, you know, where we would actually be outside the sites and doing things like for example in Roseacre we did a sponsored dog walk... And then it got bigger. And then, we would have big events set by big locations within Lancashire, particularly in this area in the Fylde, where we're under threat, where we would have literally thousands of people. So, we'd have things like where we have scientists come along to talk and people could question people who've got more experience about these things... And at the same time, we'd also run big campaigns at Preston New Road in particular, where the fracking was starting, where we have people from all over the country... There were really big events where thousands of people turned up. And then we concentrated on getting into London because we realised that to be effective, it's the government, the MPs that you had to effect... We liaised with the national groups as well... like Frack Free United, who are particularly focused on the lobbying of the MPs. There is Talk Fracking with Vivienne Westwood... who did a lot to like the campaigning in London and celebrity engagement and things like that. The Nanas* also some of them were originally part of the Occupy movement' (Interviewee 7).

In June 2017, the court upheld a right of appeal against the decision to allow fracking at the PNR site. PNRAG was able to continue through making a challenge against the Secretary of State's decision to overturn Lancashire County Council's rejection of an application by Cuadrilla to drill for and extract shale gas, stating 'we hope that this appeal will finally

recognise the will and voice of local democracy, and ensure that this application is revoked and the work at Preston New Road terminated' (PNRAG, 2017 website). In August 2017, Cuadrilla began drilling at Preston New Road and applied to vary the planning conditions in November of the same year. The PNRAG's Appeal was rejected by the Royal Courts of Justice in January 2018. 'We will now take time to scrutinise the decision documents and liaise with our legal team. Our end goal has not changed: we are still intent on achieving justice for the Preston New Road community and beyond' (PRNRAG, 2018 website).

In March, the group decided not to progress the challenge in the Supreme Court. The group decided to still, 'contribute to the process. So, there was lots of consultations along the way. So when work on the site first began and the Lancashire County Council had to agree plans with Cuadrilla. So like the noise management plan, the traffic management plan and the plans that basically underpinned the conditions that the planning inspectorate put in place. And we took part in those consultations as well. So at least we got a say in what was happening...' (Interviewee 6).

In June 2019, Friends of the Earth began High Court actions against Cuadrilla to substantially reduce the scale of the injunction against anti-fracking protests. 'At PNR, for instance, the injunction outlaws direct actions including trespass, slow walking, lock-ons, obstruction of the highway, and lorry surfing' (Brock 2020:11). Injunctions used to be 'toothless and ignored by protesters... However, from 2003, the Government supported the bringing of injunctions under the Protection from Harassment Act 1999 (the 'Stalkers Law'/PfHA), which had much tougher penalties and wider powers.' In February 2020, important sections of the injunction were abandoned.

After continuous calls from Cuadrilla to change the seismic trigger levels on the previously agreed Traffic Light System, the government decided not to change them in November 2018. In March 2019, Cuadrilla requested more changes to their Environment Agency Permits. But work came to a halt in August 2019 after Cuadrilla started fracking its second well on site after abandoning the first well following multiple shutdowns because of tremors. On the 21st of August the largest tremor was recorded in the location.

'I stood in my kitchen and you could hear all the pots in my cupboard rattling. So, it was quite scary. And people in the town, which is a little further away, they felt their house is shaking because their houses are built more on sandy grounds' (Interviewee 8).

On the 2nd of November 2019, the Conservative led government announced a moratorium on fracking in the UK because it is unsafe, following a report by the Oil and Gas Authority. The report stated that the current human-induced seismic events could not be accurately predicted. This moratorium came in eight years to the day since the last one on fracking. Cuadrilla has taken equipment off its fracking site. In October 2019, campaigners celebrate 1,000 days of protest at PNR. One month later, a protest camp was evicted with Frack Free Lancashire critiquing the 'aggressive eviction'. At the same time, campaigners closed the monitoring camp outside the site. The planning permission for PNR runs out in 2023. This is

also the time when the site needs to be restored to a green field by Cuadrilla (Interviewee 6).

*The Lancashire Nanas have been part of the Preston New Road resistance from the beginning. 'These ladies come armed with fruit cake and fury. They sing, wave banners and get through a seemingly inordinate amount of tea. Occasionally, there's dancing. On Wednesdays, they wear white as a symbol of peaceful protest and hold a silent vigil' (Independent 2018).

5. Frack Free Isle of Wight renamed their campaign to Don't Drill The Wight

Frack Free Isle of Wight renamed to Don't Drill The Wight

Frack Free Isle of Wight (based on the Isle of Wight, South England) was created when some of the islanders heard about possible onshore oil and gas developments when the 14th round of licences was issued in 2014. At the beginning, the group created a Facebook page and website to be able to raise awareness about the developments. They did not know whether the licence was for oil and/ or gas and whether fracking was needed to extract it. Half of the island is under licence (i.e. 200 square kilometres of an island that is 380 square kilometres). No oil and gas company had taken up the licence at that time. Still, the group decided to participate in the government's habitat/ environmental assessments, being worried about the potential environmental damage to the island. The group started to conduct research, invited speakers (e.g. from Lancashire to share their experiences) and created presentations to inform local residents.

In 2016, UKOG (i.e. oil and gas company) purchased the licences. This is when the group realised that they wanted to extract oil rather than gas and through a process of acidisation. Oil exploration had previously been conducted on the island going back quite some time. At the time, it wasn't considered economical to spend any more time on it.

'So, we discovered it was oil and UKOG started to put out information. They were already drilling at Horse Hill in Surrey and they were drilling in the limestone. They said they weren't fracking, which was a bonus for us because we thought, okay, it's not going to be fracking. But then, subsequently, over the next few years, we did more research and we discovered... it was still not going to be drilling just straight down into the ground, the kind of drilling that they were doing in Horse Hill involved multiple wells and horizontal wells and they used acidisation...' (Interviewee 3).

Nothing happened over the past four years and some people started to lose interest in the topic. Still, Frack Free Isle of Wight decided to formalise, set up a committee and decided on key focus areas for their research. They also kept on presenting their work to the islanders, sending out newsletter and holding meetings. In the meantime, UKOG started other drilling projects in the South East of England. In 2018, the company announced it would put in a planning application in 2019.

'And they were basically making a lot of noise for their investors to help boost their investment prospects. But they didn't come on the island and do anything. They didn't do any seismic analysis. Nothing happened. It was just all in the press at various times. And then suddenly last year, they announced that they were putting in a planning application. And we thought, well, you know, they said that last year. They've been saying that before. But then, it started to become real' (Interviewee 3).

'During all this time, Frack Free Isle of Wight had become a formal group and we affiliated with the Weald Action Group [i.e. regional umbrella organisation for groups]. And we went on four or five occasions over to Surrey in various places to meet with them and find out what had happened with them, find out what was happening on the other sites with UKOG. How did they play the game? And they did inform us that UKOG would have a public meeting' (Interviewee 3).

Through a Freedom of Information inquiry, the group had found out that the planning officer had held pre-planning discussions with UKOG. In December 2019, UKOG announced that it would hold a public meeting (in the format of a drop-in session) and submit a planning application.

'And we'd already prepared an action plan if the planning application was going to be submitted. And it took us about a year to put that together to decide how we would act. What groups would engage? Who would we contact? How would we plan it out? What would we do media wise, etc.? So, one of the big deals was to get together with anybody who had been to that meeting and gather information and things that they [i.e. UKOG] said' (Interviewee 3).

'So, after that meeting, we decided that we were going to organise ourselves better. We needed to get more media out there because none of us knew much about Twitter or Instagram or anything like that. So, we did put that into practice. And then, of course, we had lockdown. So, we weren't able to hold the planned series of 10 meetings in three months around the island' (Interviewee 3).

In March 2020, notices went up on the field, the group only noticed because of one of its members saw it happening. There also was a note in the local newspaper and soon after, the council published the planning application on its website. There was some back and forward about when the consultation should start to happen because of the lockdown. In June, the council announced that the consultation had started. The group decided that 'despite the lockdown, we were going to go into action' (Interviewee 3). Interviewee 3 explained how they needed to re-frame their campaign,

UKOG announced in the press and online: 'We don't know what all these people are worried about, Frack Free Isle of Wight, because we're not going to frack. We're saying that we are not fracking. So, we decided that we would start a new campaign, which would say 'don't drill the Wight' to move it away from the concept of fracking. Even though we seriously

do believe that if this all goes ahead, they would probably want to apply to do acid fracking in the future. For the moment, we're focusing on that we just don't want drilling here whatever the format' (Interviewee 3).

'We've been focusing much more on unconventional oil and gas exploration... other forms of kind of fracking under the radar, basically... we do try not to even mention fracking now, even though we still support the opposition to fracking on the mainland... from the beginning, we wanted to do this our way. We do not want to be seen as being NIMBYs or, you know, XR chaining ourselves to stuff. Although if they want to do that, that's fine. Our job is to educate and inform people' (Interviewee 3).

'We always felt that when things hit the fan, when things started to happen that the public would wake up and what we prepared in advance was what we would have to do to make sure that the public woke up' (Interviewee 3).

The website needed to be changed, banners, postcards, leaflets, online presentations and videos were made, a socially distant meeting was conducted, and the social media work was set in place (including articles in the local newspaper). 'It's still about how you can get to respond to this application... So, I think in the first week or so of the consultation, there were only about 50 or 60 opposition statements and now we've got two thousand two hundred and fifty' (Interviewee 3). The group is currently busy analysing the objections, keeping in touch with the planning officer and preparing their statement for the planning committee.

'We're just holding our breath now. We just want it to be over' (Interviewee 3).